

Low temperature dissipation studies in normal and superconducting electromechanical systems

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To my Family

Declaration

The work presented in this dissertation has been carried out by me under the guidance of Dr. Ananth Venkatesan at the Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Mohali. This work has not been submitted in part or in full for a degree, a diploma, or a fellowship to any other university or institute. Whenever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions. This thesis is a bonafide record of original work done by me and all sources listed within have been detailed in the bibliography.

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In my capacity as the supervisor of the candidate's doctoral thesis, I certify that the above statements by the candidate are true to the best of my knowledge.

Dr. Ananth Venkatesan
(Supervisor)

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Chapter 1

Overview of some important concepts

This chapter deals with some relevant concept to understand the analysis presented in the rest of the chapters in the context of mechanical systems. The nanomechanical resonator can be modeled as the harmonic oscillator, which describes these systems very well. The equations for the resonance frequency and the damping has been obtained using methods of continuum mechanics. The first section deals with the mechanical resonance frequency and damping in these systems and their origin, especially damping due to the two-level system. The rest of this chapter is related to some concepts of superconductivity, flux motion and their dissipation.

1.1 Mesoscopic electromechanical phenomena

The advancement of fundamental physics relies on ultra-sensitive detection. This can be either discovering new subatomic particles (e.g. as Higgs Bosons in CERN) or the discovery of the gravitational wave detected by the ultrasensitive interferometer, which was predicted 100 years back [Abbott et al., 2016]. The improvement in detection has usually led to starting a new field in physics, the prime example being quantum optomechanics and gravitational astronomy. Among the various types of detectors, the NEMS (Nano-electrical Mechanical system) is one of the most sensitive detectors in research. They are transducer which converts electrical energy into mechanical energy and vice versa. Their extreme sensitivity is due to their small mass and large surface to volume ratio. The industrial applications of these devices includes mass sensing in biology (expand bio) and used in accelerometers in cars and mobiles. From the fundamental physics point of view, they manifest themselves as sensitive to tiny forces such as Casimir force, originating from quantum vacuum fluctuation [Chan et al., 2001]. or deviation of classical Newtonian gravity at very small scales [Chiaverini et al., 2003]. With the advancement of nanofabrication, it is

now possible to fabricate devices in very small dimensions, further improving their sensitivity. The mass sensitivity of NEMS device made out of carbon nanotube has gone to such a level that we can now detect molecules with one yectogram of resolution [Chaste et al., 2012].

Apart from their sensing application, they are one of the versatile systems to study fundamental physics. In fact, in recent years, they have been used to study dissipation in metallic systems at very low-temperatures [Imboden and Mohanty, 2014]. The linear dissipation in metallic systems at very low temperatures has been understood more or less by phonon interaction with a two-level system (TLS) [Esquinazi, 2013]. There have been very few attempts to study non-linear dissipation from the fundamental physics point of view. Fortunately, it turns out that these systems can be made non-linear just by driving them hard; hence it acts as a versatile model system to study both linear and non-linear dissipation. The various origin of non-linear dissipation has been studied theoretically by Atalya *et al.* [Atalaya et al., 2016]. This thesis probed the novel mechanism of non-linear damping in the metallic system called Akhizier non-linear dissipation. Apart from that, one can ask the fundamental question of the contribution of normal electron towards total dissipation at very low temperature. To get the dissipation by normal electron, one can take the superconducting NEMS device and measure the dissipation below and above the superconducting transition temperature, which can be used to calculate the normal electron's dissipation. This trick can be used because below 1K, the phonons are almost non-existent, and in the superconductor below the transition temperature, there are no normal electrons.

From the above point of view, one can safely say that NEMS with reduced dimension is a smart probe to bring new ideas into the condensed matter field [Imboden and Mohanty, 2014].

1.2 Mechanical Resonators

It turns out very naturally that many problems in physics can be modeled as a simple harmonic oscillator (*e.g.* atomic vibration, heat capacity at low temperature etc. [Simon, 2013]). A simple harmonic oscillator is a system in which force is linearly proportional to the displacement, and the oscillation frequency is independent of the amplitude of motion. The model system studied (NEMS) in this thesis behaves like a simple harmonic oscillator. By knowing the resonators natural vibrating frequency and damping, much can be elucidated about the physics of these systems. Also, if the system is driven too hard such that the force is not linearly dependent on the displacement, it gives rise to non-linear mechanical resonators. These systems are also interesting from the physics point of view, which has been discussed in chapter 3.

Figure 1.1: The schematic of the doubly clamped beam

1.2.1 Eigen-mode of the doubly clamped structure

The most part of the thesis deals with the doubly clamped beam structure which is one of the most simple object described in the framework of continuum mechanics. One can find the in depth studies about these structures here [Cleland, 2013]. Here we will be discussing about the some of the relevant concept related to this thesis.

The figure 1.1 shows the schematic of simplest rectangular beam of length l , width w and thickness t . The beam is chosen in such a way that it has very high aspect ratio, which means that $l \gg w, t$. The beam has has area of cross section $A = w \times t$, having density ρ , total mass of the beam ($m = \rho A l$), Young's modulus (E). the second moment of inertia along the displacement axis $I = wt^3/12$, beam having in built stress σ . One can arrive at the Euler-Bernoulli equation for the above mentioned rectangular beam by applying the least action principle to the displacement field $u(z, t)$ [Timoshenko and Goodier, 1951].

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 u(z, t)}{\partial z^4} + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial t^2} - \sigma A \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

It is clear that at each end the displacement must be zero because the beam is clamped at both ends. Because of this one can apply the boundary condition as:

$$u \left(z = \pm \frac{l}{2}, t \right) \quad (1.2)$$

The solution to the equation (1.1) can be separated into two parts which consists of spatial part and time dependent part. The displacement can be written as:

$$u(z, t) = \Psi(z)x(t) \quad (1.3)$$

The $\Psi(z)$ represents the displacement profile of the beam, and $x(t)$ represents the oscillation of the mechanical wave set in the beam at frequency ω in such a way that $x(t) = x_0 e^{i\omega t}$. This separation helps us in studying the two limiting cases *i.e.* bending rigidity limit (Low stress) and tensile stress limit (High stress).

Bending rigidity limit

In the low stress limit, one can drop the stress term in the Bernoulli-Euler equation (1.1). This is due to potential term arising from the stress is very small as compared to potential arising from the bending moment. One is left with a simplified version of the Euler-Bernoulli equation which can be written as:

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 u(z, t)}{\partial z^4} + \rho A \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.4)$$

In addition to that we also have a boundary condition (1.2). In case of the ideal flexure mode the beam does not bend at the clamping points. This means that

$$\left. \frac{\partial u(z, t)}{\partial z} \right|_{z=\pm \frac{l}{2}} = 0 \quad (1.5)$$

Since the Euler Bernoulli equation is the 4th order in the partial derivative, which means that we can write the following guess solution:

$$\Psi(z) = b_1 \cosh(\lambda z) + b_2 \sinh(\lambda z) + b_3 \cos(\lambda z) + b_4 \sin(\lambda z) \quad (1.6)$$

The eqn.(1.6) is the solution of the Euler-Bernoulli equation, where the values of λ is defined by the boundary conditions. By applying the boundary condition as mentioned in eqn.(1.2) to the guessed value of the displacement field, one can obtain the following transcendental equation:

$$\cos(\lambda_n l) \cosh(\lambda_n l) = 1 \quad (1.7)$$

The eqn. (1.7) has infinitely many solution *i.e.* where the index n comes into the picture. One can obtain the solution from the eqn. (1.7) by plotting algebraically. The point where the two plots intersect each other, are the solution of the Euler Bernoulli eqn. in the bending limit. The algebraic plot is

Figure 1.2: The plot of the guessed solution of the Bernoulli equation in the bending limit. The blue colour represents the $\cos(\lambda_n)l$ with the $\lambda_n l$ and orange colour represents the $1/\cos(\lambda_n)l$ with the $\lambda_n l$. The intersection of these two curves provides the solution to the equation.

shown in the figure 1.2, in good approximation the wave vector can be defined as in eqn. (1.8)

$$\lambda_n l \approx \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \pi \quad (1.8)$$

Now when $n \gg 1$ and for $n = 1$ to 4, one can get the values of $\lambda_n l = 4.73, 7.85, 11.00, 14.14$ [Cleland, 2013]. From here one can obtain the dispersion relation $\omega(k)$, which will provide us the eigen frequencies of the mechanical structure. This can be obtained by inserting the guessed solution (1.6) into the Euler Bernoulli equation(1.1) and then one gets the following solution.

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}} \lambda_n^2 \approx \sqrt{\frac{EI}{\rho A}} \left(n + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{l}\right)^2 \quad (1.9)$$

String limit or high tension limit

In the high tension limit which is also known as string limit, the potential due to tensile stress is much larger than the potential due to the bending moment. In this limit original Euler-Bernoulli equation(1.1) becomes:

$$\rho A \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial t^2} - \sigma A \frac{\partial^2 u(z, t)}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (1.10)$$

In the high tensile limit the guessed solution (1.6), sinh and cosh represents a nonphysical wave so we discard these terms and we are left with the following equation:

$$\Psi(z) = b_1 \cos(\lambda z) + b_2 \sin(\lambda z) \quad (1.11)$$

Now one can apply the boundary condition as mentioned in the eqn. (1.2) to the eqn. (1.11) and this leads to eigenvectors:

$$\lambda_n l = (n + 1) \pi \quad (1.12)$$

by inserting the eqn.(1.11) into the original Euler-Bernoulli equation (1.1), one gets the natural frequency in the string limit with appropriate boundary condition as given by the equation (1.2).

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\rho}} \lambda_n = \frac{(n + 1)\pi}{\rho} \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\rho}} \quad (1.13)$$

In case of highly stressed beam the relation mentioned in the equation (1.13) holds very well. In case of less stressed films, the eqn. still holds, but it needs some correction to the young's modulus [Lulla, 2011]. The figure 1.3 shows the profile of the first four modes of the mechanical resonator. It is not possible to have the beam perfectly in the string limit because of the discontinuity in derivative of displacement field at the clamping points., it must be smoothen out at those points.

1.2.2 Linear dissipation in harmonic oscillator

In the above section we have discussed the spatial variation of the displacement field (the spatial dependence gives us the eigen frequencies of the mode). In this section we will be discussing the time dependence of the displacement field. The time variation of the displacement field can be written as the simple spring mass system which can be written as:

$$m \frac{d^2 x(t)}{dt^2} + m\omega^2 x(t) = F(t) \quad (1.14)$$

where m is the mass of the beam , $k = m\omega^2$ is the spring constant of the beam and $F(t)$ is the time varying driving force. It must be noted that all the information regarding the beam profile, deformation is described by the variable $x(t)$.

Let us apply a sinusoidal wave to our system. Since there is no dissipation present in the eqn. (1.14), the beam will keep on oscillating without decay in amplitude. This is not what we observe in the real system, because due to many frictional mechanisms the system vibrations tend to decay with time. We

Figure 1.3: The first four lowest modes of the doubly clamped solved by finite element method (COMSOL). The colour represent the displacement of the beam in nanometer from the equilibrium position. Red colour represents the maximum displacement and blue colour represents the minimum displacement.

will be discussing about these friction mechanism later section. In this section we have put all the friction mechanism into one phenomenological constant called damping rate(Γ). Here we have assumed that dissipative force is linear in nature and does not depend upon the displacement. One can introduce the dissipation in the harmonic oscillator equation(1.14) as:

$$F_d(t) = m\Gamma \frac{dx(t)}{dt} \quad (1.15)$$

The Γ in the above eqn carries information about all the dissipation mechanism, plugging the eqn. (1.15) into the eqn.(1.14), one gets the following equation

$$m \frac{d^2x(t)}{dt^2} + m\Gamma \frac{dx(t)}{dt} + m\omega^2 x(t) = F(t) \quad (1.16)$$

By using the appropriate boundary condition one can solve eqn. (1.16) at time $t > 0$ and it can be shown that:

$$x(t) = x(0)e^{-\Gamma t/2} \cos(\omega_r t) \quad (1.17)$$

The eqn. (1.17) depicts that amplitude will decay over the time scale of roughly $2/\Gamma$ to its equilibrium position. The mechanical energy stored in the oscillator will be released to the environment and while relaxing, the resonance

frequency of the system is given by $\omega_r = \omega\sqrt{1 - 1/(2Q)^2}$. Here Q is the quality factor and given as $Q = \omega/\Gamma$. The Q factor gives us the information about the number of oscillation executed by the resonant system before coming to rest. In the under-damped harmonic oscillator $Q \gg 1$, which is mostly the case in our devices. If one applies an oscillating driving force $F(t) = F_0 \cos(\omega t)$, then the generic solution to the equation can be written as:

$$x(t) = X(\omega) \cos(\omega t) + Y(\omega) \sin(\omega t) \quad (1.18)$$

$$X(\omega) = \frac{F_0}{m} \frac{\Gamma \omega}{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \Gamma^2 \omega^2} \quad (1.19a)$$

$$Y(\omega) = \frac{F_0}{m} \frac{\omega - \omega_0^2}{(\omega_0^2 - \omega^2)^2 + \Gamma^2 \omega^2} \quad (1.19b)$$

The $X(\omega)$ is called the absorption and $Y(\omega)$ is called the dispersion of the mechanical response of the beam. From the eqn.(1.19), it has been observed that displacement is maximum at the resonance frequency and at higher frequency the response of the beam starts lagging behind the driving force. At very high frequencies the mechanical response becomes transparent to the driving frequencies. It can be seen from eqn.(1.19a), which is the absorption part of the mechanical response of the beam has a Lorentzian shape and the dissipation in the beam is directly proportional to the full width half maxima of the Lorentzian. To get the quality factor and resonance frequency of the beam one has to fit the absorption and dispersion part of the response of the beam simultaneously. One such sample data is shown in the figure 1.4, the data is fitted with the help of Matlab and before fitting the background has been subtracted from the raw data.

1.3 Dissipation in mechanical system

In this section, we will be discussing the various dissipation scenarios in the mechanical system. The dissipation in a mechanical system is a complex phenomenon as it comprises various sources of dissipation about which we will be leaning as we move along this section. This section aims to have the qualitative idea of the dissipation rather than having quantitative dissipation.

1.3.1 Anelastic Relaxation

It has been shown that relaxation in mechanical deformation occurs when strain (shape) is not proportional to the stress (applied forces). To understand the dissipation in a mechanical system, we will derive some useful relation involving anelastic solid. Most of the discussion here is followed from the classical text by Nowick, and Berry [Markovitz, 1973].

Figure 1.4: A typical data set for the Pd NEMS taken at 4T, when the sample temperature was 110mK. The red line is fit to the data set governed by eqn. (1.18).

What is an Anelastic Material

First of all, let us try to understand the elastic material in the Hookanean limit.

$$\sigma = Eu \quad (1.20)$$

$$u = M\sigma \quad (1.21)$$

$$E = 1/M \quad (1.22)$$

here σ , u , E , and M are the stress, strain, modulus, and compliance. Equation (1.20) implies that stress and strain are related to each other linearly and response instantaneously as the force is applied. In real world, there is no perfectly elastic material. All of the materials requires some small amount of time to equilibrate on the application of stress. An anelastic material has the following properties.

An anelastic material is defined as:

- The stress-strain relationship is linear
- After the application of force (stress), the equilibrium is achieved only after a certain amount of time
- There is a unique value of strain for the particular value of stress and vice versa.

One can easily understand that the difference between anelastic and elastic solid is that an anelastic material requires a certain amount of time to come equilibrium after the force has been applied, which is not the case with elastic

materials. An experimentalist chooses to measure either strain or stress during the measurement as both of them revealed the same information.

Creep function

If an experimentalist suddenly apply a stress σ_0 to the sample at $t = 0$ and observes the change of $u(t)$ as a function of time:

we know that since the relation between stress and strain is linear, the ration $\frac{u(t)}{\sigma_0}$ will be a constant quantity. For a realistic sample one defines above mentioned ratio as creep function:

$$M(t) \equiv \frac{u(t)}{\sigma_0} \quad (1.23)$$

At $t = 0$, this creep function assumes $M(0) = M_u$ is called unrelaxed compliance, and at $t = \infty$ assumes the creep function assumes a value called relaxed compliance $M_\infty \equiv M_R$. The difference between relaxed compliance and unrelaxed compliance is called relaxation of compliance ($\delta M(t)$). In general one could write also as

$$M(t) = M_u + [\delta M](t) \quad (1.24)$$

Dissipation estimates during the dynamics of anelastic solids

Till now we have not discussed why the mechanical energy is lost when the deformation lags behind the applied force. In general both stress and strain are sinusoidally varying with time having a relative phase difference. We can write stress and strain as:

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 e^{i\omega t} \quad (1.25)$$

$$u(t) = u_0 e^{i(\omega t - \phi)} \quad (1.26)$$

one can define complex compliance as

$$M^*(\omega) \equiv u/\sigma = |M|(\omega) e^{-i\phi(\omega)} = M_1(\omega) - iM_2(\omega) \quad (1.27)$$

where $|J|(\omega) = u_0/\sigma_0$ is called absolute dynamic compliance. We can calculate the energy lost during the complete cycle as follows: Let us choose the origin of time in such a way that stress is real: $\sigma(t) = \sigma_0 \cos(\omega t)$ and the real part of the strain will be $u(t) = -u_0 \cos(\omega t + \phi)$. The work done per unit volume for the deformation du is given by σdu . Over a complete cycle the work done can be written as:

$$W_{cycle} = \oint \sigma du \quad (1.28)$$

The above equation can be solved very easily, giving us $\pi J_2 \sigma_0^2$, which means that network is proportional to J_2 . This work is equal to the dissipation of mechanical energy over the same period of time, required to sustain the oscillation. The amount of mechanical energy stored can be written as $\pi J_1 \sigma_0^2$. Thus one can write as

$$\Delta W/W = 2\pi(J_2/J_1) = 2\pi \tan\phi \quad (1.29)$$

Now from the above expression, one can clearly see the J_1 corresponds to the energy stored in the system and J_2 corresponds to the energy lost by the system. The J_1 and J_2 are also called storage compliance and loss compliance. Since for all purposes $J_2 \ll J_1$, which implies that $\tan\phi = \phi$, which is also called loss angle. Thus one can write loss quality factor in terms of loss angle as:

$$Q \equiv \phi^{-1} = 2\pi \frac{W}{\Delta W} \quad (1.30)$$

It is straightforward to calculate dissipation in terms of compliance's, which is given by

$$Q^{-1} \approx \tan(\phi) \approx \Delta \frac{\omega \tau_\sigma}{1 + \omega^2 \tau_\sigma^2} \quad (1.31)$$

Why linear dissipation proportional to velocity

In the introduction, we said that linear dissipation in the system is proportional to the velocity. We will show here that it follows from the simple dynamic response of the anelastic solid. We know that a beams resonance frequency is determined by its effective mass and complex spring constant which is given by $k^* = k_1 + \iota k_2 \propto \frac{M_1}{|M|^2} + \iota \frac{M_2}{|M|^2}$.

Now we know that

$$m\ddot{x} = -F_\sigma \quad (1.32)$$

$$m\ddot{x} = -k^* x = -(k_1 + \iota k_2)x \quad (1.33)$$

$$m\ddot{x} + k_2/\dot{x}\omega + k_1 x = 0 \quad (1.34)$$

now on rearranging the above equation one can see that (recognizing that $\omega x = \dot{x}$), if we eliminate the imaginary part, we will get the dissipation which is directly proportional to the velocity. Using the dynamics of anelastic solids, we can prove that dissipation is directly proportional to the velocity.

The peak in dissipation or Debye peak

If one plots the eqn.(1.31) with frequency, we will be seeing the maxima in dissipation which is centered at $\omega = \tau_\sigma^{-1}$. The type of peak is called Debye peak. If one wants to observe that an oscillator is limited by a particular time constant, one has to make a wide variety of devices. It is not feasible to satisfy such a criterion as it is impossible to make one device that can cover all range of frequency. Another simpler way to loom for Debye peak will be to do a temperature sweep. The dissipation process is temperature-activated, and other dissipation process does not occur in the screened temperature range. If the particular dissipation process is temperature activated then one can find the relaxation time constant using the Arrhenius law which is given below:

$$\tau^{-1} = \tau_0^{-1} e^{E_a/k_B T} \quad (1.35)$$

where E_a is the activation energy and $k_B T$ is the thermal energy in the process

Various sources of the mechanical damping

In general, the Q factor of the devices made in the cleanroom usually is more than 1000, which means that energy dissipation during each cycle is minimal. Although it is small, there is a loss of energy through various channels. In this section, we will discuss these loss mechanisms. The total dissipation can be considered as a sum of all other dissipative sources.

$$Q^{-1} = Q_{Bulk}^{-1} + Q_{Surface}^{-1} + Q_{Design}^{-1} + Q_{Interaction}^{-1} \quad (1.36)$$

where Q_{Bulk}^{-1} refers to the intrinsic loss mechanism due to the material's anelastic deformation. $Q_{Surface}^{-1}$ refers to the anelastic processes in the mechanical resonator's surface layer. Q_{Design}^{-1} refers to the losses due to bad geometric design such as clamping losses. Q_{Design}^{-1} refers to the coupling between mechanical deformation and some fields originating from the probing method such as electric and magnetic field. Let us suppose that we have perfect geometry so that it is free from all geometric losses. In that case, only losses will be due to the Q_{Bulk}^{-1} and $Q_{Interaction}^{-1}$, which can be further divided into following parts:

$$Q_{Bulk}^{-1} = Q_{TED}^{-1} + Q_{Phonon-Phonon}^{-1} + Q_{Phonon-Electron}^{-1} + Q_{Bulk-TLS}^{-1} + Q_{Bulk-Others}^{-1} \quad (1.37)$$

where TED is the Thermo Elastic damping and TLS is the Two-Level System. We will be studying about the damping due to the two-level system.

1.4 Quantum friction due to tunneling two-level system

This subsection will discuss the quantum tunneling mechanism and how the relaxation via tunneling of TLS leads to energy dissipation. We followed the methodology as discussed here [Hunklinger and Arnold, 1976].

1.4.1 Dissipation in tunneling two-level system

The idea of a two-level system is realized in following, one cools down the system to lowest possible temperatures. At this point, the system might not have enough thermal energy to access the other state. One possibility arises from quantum mechanics is that an atom or group of the atom can move collectively to access the two local configurations with minimum energy by tunneling. For example, it could be the movement of oxygen vacancies on the surface of Si/SiO_2 . The energy splitting between the two minima is given by Δ , as shown in figure 1.5. Due to additional tunneling of the defect continuously from one localized state to another, it leads to mixing energy terms. In Hamiltonian language, it is described as an off-diagonal term δ . The value of δ decreases exponentially with the increase in barrier height V and physical distance d . In the real space basis, Hamiltonian can be written as:

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta & -\delta \\ -\delta & -\Delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.38)$$

The eigenstates of the above Hamiltonian in the absence of disturbance by phonons are given by $U_{\pm} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{\Delta^2 + \delta^2}}{2}$, where $U_+ - U_- = U$ denoted the energy splitting. From now on we will be working with the basis spanned by the eigenstate of the above Hamiltonian. Thus we have

$$\hat{H}_0 = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} U_+ & 0 \\ 0 & U_- \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} U & 0 \\ 0 & -U \end{pmatrix} \quad (1.39)$$

In the real experiment one will be applying periodic stress, sets the strain waves inside the material. This strain can modulate the energy splitting, in turn affecting Δ and δ . Assuming that applied amplitude is very small, system will be able to follow the strain. This implies that energies of the unperturbed Hamiltonian will be slightly modified by a parameter D called deformation potential. This can be written as: $D = \frac{2\Delta}{U} \frac{\partial \Delta}{\partial u} + \frac{2\delta}{U} \frac{\partial \delta}{\partial u}$. This might give rise to off diagonal terms which can be written as:

$$\hat{H}' = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} D & 2J \\ 2J & -D \end{pmatrix} u \quad (1.40)$$

It can be realized that this problem can be easily solved by mapping this Hamiltonian to spin 1/2 particle in static magnetic field with a small sinusoidal

Figure 1.5: A typical representation of the two level system, separated by potential barrier V and having asymmetry energy Δ

perturbation. The same technique can be used here. The equivalent magnetic field is given as:

$$\vec{B}_0 = \left(0, 0, -\frac{U}{\hbar\gamma} \right) \quad (1.41)$$

$$\vec{B}'(t) = \left(-\frac{2J}{\hbar\gamma}, 0, -\frac{D}{\hbar\gamma} \right) u(t) \quad (1.42)$$

In order to know that how TLS contribution to the imaginary part of the elastic constant, we can proceed as follows:

$$\delta E = \frac{\delta\sigma}{u} = \frac{1}{u} \frac{\partial U_{TLS}}{\partial u} \quad (1.43)$$

here U_{TLS} is the energy content of ensemble of TLS's per unit volume, and this quantity can be calculated using spin analogy as:

$$\begin{aligned} U_{TLS} &= -\mu_v \cdot \vec{B}' \\ &= -N_v \langle \mu \rangle \cdot \vec{B}' \\ &= -N_v \gamma \hbar \langle \vec{S} \rangle \cdot \vec{B}' \\ &= N_v [2J \langle S_x \rangle + D \langle S_z \rangle] u(t) \end{aligned}$$

In the above expression, v denotes the density of TLS's per unit volume. To eliminate quantities involving spin, we can express angular momentum as the product between susceptibility and field energy.

$$S_i(t) = \chi_i(\omega) \hbar \gamma B_i'(t) \quad (1.44)$$

From the above two equations, one can get

$$\delta E(\omega) = -2N_v [4J^2 \chi_x(\omega) + D^2 \chi_z(\omega)] \quad (1.45)$$

We have seen earlier that dissipation is proportional to the imaginary part of the susceptibilities. In detail we will be calculating susceptibility for the z polarization, corresponding to the loss by relaxation. While solving there will be two-time scales in the problem τ_1 and τ_2 , which is also called the longitudinal and transverse relaxation time. The equation, which is given below is called the Bloch equation.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\langle S_x(t) \rangle}{dt} &= -\gamma [\langle S_y \rangle B_z - \langle S_z \rangle B_y] + \tau_2^{-1} \langle S_x \rangle = 0 \\ \frac{\langle S_y(t) \rangle}{dt} &= -\gamma [\langle S_z \rangle B_z - \langle S_x \rangle B_x] + \tau_2^{-1} \langle S_y \rangle = 0 \\ \frac{\langle S_z(t) \rangle}{dt} &= -\gamma [\langle S_x \rangle B_y - \langle S_y \rangle B_x] + \tau_1^{-1} \langle S_y \rangle = \frac{S_z^{eq}[B_z(t)]}{\tau_1} \end{aligned}$$

here $S_z^{eq}[B_z(t)]$ is the equilibrium z polarization. For the field strength $B_z(t)$, the equilibrium polarization can be written as:

$$S_z^{eq}[B_z(t)] = \frac{1}{2} \tanh[\hbar \gamma B_z(t) / 2k_B T] \approx S_z^0(B_0) + B_z' \frac{dS_z^0}{dB_0} \quad (1.46)$$

where $S_z^0(B_0)$ denotes the equilibrium polarization of the TLS's in the absence of strain. The perturbing field can be modeled as

$$\vec{B}'(t) = 2\vec{B}' \cos \omega t = \vec{B}'(e^{i\omega t} + e^{-i\omega t}) \quad (1.47)$$

In the steady state one can assume that response of the polarization vector only consists of DC component along the z axis and a component at same frequency as the perturbing field. Ignoring the higher frequency components one can write:

$$\langle \vec{S}(t) \rangle = S_z^0 + \vec{S}_1(e^{i\omega t} + e^{-i\omega t}) \quad (1.48)$$

if one includes all the frequency multiples in the expansion

$$\langle \vec{S}(t) \rangle = S_z^0 + \sum_{k=-\infty}^{k=+\infty} \vec{S}_m e^{-im\omega t} \quad (1.49)$$

The Bloch equation can be simplified if one uses $S_{\pm} = S_x \pm iS_y$. By plugging the expression for S and B' into the Bloch equation and separating the component for $m\omega$,

$$\begin{aligned} (m\omega \pm \omega_0 + \tau_2^{-1})S_{\pm}, m = \\ \pm \gamma B'_z (S_{\pm}, m+1 + S_{\pm}, m-1) \mp \gamma B'_x S_z^0 \delta_{m,\pm 1} \\ + (S_{z,m+1})(im\omega + \tau_1^{-1})S_{z,m} = \frac{i\gamma}{2} B'_x [S_{+,m+1} + S_{+,m-1} - S_{-,m+1} - S_{-,m-1}] + B'_z \\ \tau_1^{-1} \frac{dS_z^0}{dB_0} \delta_{m,\pm 1} \end{aligned}$$

By substituting $m=1$, one gets the susceptibility as

$$\chi_z(\omega) = \frac{S_{z,1}/\hbar\gamma}{B'_z} = \frac{dS_z^0}{dB_0} \frac{1}{\hbar\gamma(1 - i\omega\tau_1)} \quad (1.50)$$

since the imaginary component of $\chi_z(\omega)$ corresponds to the dissipation due to relaxation of TLS's. using equation (1.45) and equation (1.46) one can find that:

$$Q_{TLS}^{-1} = N_v D^2 \frac{e^{-U/k_B T}}{k_B T [1 + e^{-U/k_B T}]^2} \frac{\omega\tau_1}{1 + \omega^2\tau_1^2} \quad (1.51)$$

This is the form we expected for the dissipation which will have Debye peak around $\omega = \tau_1$. The devices which we have studied in this thesis have a maximum frequency of 50 MHz. If one notices that we have not discussed the dissipation due to the resonant process in the energy gap of TLS is matched with NEMS device frequency. In our case, it will correspond to maximum 3mK, which is not attainable in our current dilution refrigerator setup.

1.5 Non linear dissipation

In the above section, we have discussed about the linear dissipation which is proportional to the velocity $F_{diss} = \gamma v$. Normally one encounters a situation in which resonator behaves as **simple harmonic oscillator(SHO)**. Here the Hook's law is perfectly valid *i.e* displacement of the beam is directly proportional to x . if the resonators are driven very hard the above case might

not be valid and one might see that force is proportional to the cubic power of displacement αx^3 , these systems are also known as **duffing resonators**.

The linear differential without any dissipation can be written as shown below:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_0^2 x = f \cos(\omega t) \quad (1.52)$$

Now in case of dissipative duffing oscillator, the above equation gets modified and it can be written as

$$m \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} + \Gamma \frac{dx}{dt} + m \omega_0^2 x + \alpha x^3 = G \cos(\omega t) \quad (1.53)$$

here α is the non linear coefficient, Γ is the linear damping force and G is the driving force at the frequency ω . Positive α makes the structure stiffer which results in the right pulling of the beam while negative α makes the beam softer which results in the negative pulling of the beam. The linear damping signifies the rate at which energy is lost by the resonator mode. In addition to the linear dissipation there are other ways of adding dissipation in which dissipative force is not linear in v but may contains term like $x^2 \dot{x}, \ddot{x}^2, x \ddot{x}^2, \dot{x}^3$, all these term gives rise to non linear dissipation [[Schuster et al., 2008](#), [Lakshmanan and Rajaseekar, 2012a](#)]. In the presence of non linear damping one can write the (1.53) as

$$m \frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} + \Gamma \frac{dx}{dt} + m \omega_0^2 x + \alpha x^3 + \eta x^2 \frac{dx}{dt} = G \cos(\omega t) \quad (1.54)$$

The solution to the above equation has been discussed in the scope of secular perturbation theory and the detailed theoretical and experimental analysis has been given in the chapter 3.

1.6 Overview of superconductors

This section will give some general concepts about the superconductors; it will be mainly related to the type II superconductors. One of the aims in this thesis was to study dissipation by the motion of the vortices. I will be arriving at some general formulas or equations which is essential for understanding the type II superconductor, e.g. Ginzberg-Landau theory and BCS theory without going into detail; one can look at other standard text [[Tinkham, 2004](#)] if interested.

First, we will be looking at the two basics theory of superconductivity, and then we will talk about the well-known properties of the vortices.

Figure 1.6: (Left) Phase diagram for the type II superconductor, (Right) Schematic of the mixed phase, here flux is created by circulation of super-current (Sourec [Rose-Innes and Rhoderick, 1970])

1.6.1 Type II superconductor

As one is already familiar with superconductors' main properties *e.g.* lossless conduction, perfect diamagnetism below some values of temperature and magnetic field and electric current (which defines the phase space of superconductors). The type II superconductors are very different from the type I superconductor in such a way that it allows to penetrate the magnetic field on the local scale in the form of vortices. These vortices are unique in the sense that it carries one flux quantum. We will discuss this in detail.

London Model

The magnetic field application can destroy the superconductivity. The more information for the phase diagram of superconductivity with temperature and the magnetic field is shown in figure 1.6. Up-to H_{c1} , sample is entirely superconductor, which opposes any field application. In the region from H_{c1} to H_{c2} sample allows penetration of the magnetic field in the form of vortices as shown in the figure 1.6. These vortices are created by the circulation of supercurrent, which results in the magnetic field's bundling.

These two neighboring circulating currents repel each other, which means that they will for some lattice, leads to the minimization of energy. It was pointed out by Abrikosov [Abrikosov, 1957] that it will form a hexagonal lattice and spacing between two vortices will be given as:

$$d = \left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^{1/4} \sqrt{\frac{\Phi_0}{B}} \quad (1.55)$$

which means that vortices density will increase as the magnetic field increases.

London brothers [London and London, 1935] thought about the problem of superconductivity and they used the experimental fact of perfect diamagnetism and perfect conductivity in the Maxwell's equation and they arrived at the following equations:

$$\vec{E} = \mu_0 \lambda_L^2 \vec{j}_s \quad (1.56)$$

$$\vec{B} = -\mu_0 \lambda_L^2 \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{j}_s \quad (1.57)$$

here $\lambda_L = \sqrt{m/\mu_0 q^2 n_s}$ is the London's penetration depth. From the above equation, it is clear that the first equation considers perfect conductivity, while the second equation accounts for the diamagnetism. It is this equation that leads to the origin of screening current in the superconductor and penetration depth. It can be followed as, taking the curl of the London 2nd equation and using Maxwell's equation $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{j}_s$. One will get

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{B} = \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \vec{B} \quad (1.58)$$

This was followed from after using vector identity $-\vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}) = -\vec{\nabla}(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B}) + \vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{B}$ and $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$. This justifies the presence of exponential screen of magnetic field which is called penetration depth. Experimentally it was found that:

$$\lambda(T) \approx \frac{\lambda(0)}{\sqrt{1 - (T/T_c)^4}} \quad (1.59)$$

It was found that $\lambda(T)$ is always greater than $\lambda(0)$. To solve this problem, it was Pippard stoke genius who introduce another length scale to solve for the discrepancy. He argued that only electron within the Fermi energy ($\sim k_B T_c$) takes part in the superconducting phenomena which defines the momentum as $\sim k_B T_c / v_f$, one can get the estimate of length scale using Heisenberg uncertainty principle as:

$$\xi_0 \approx \Delta \geq \hbar / \Delta p \approx \hbar v_f / k_B T_c \quad (1.60)$$

Using the above equation, it turned out to be an excellent guess, except for the pre-factors.

The two very important results from our point of view is the penetration depth in case of thin film in parallel and perpendicular field. The penetration depth in parallel field is given by:

$$\lambda_{eff} \approx \left(\frac{\xi_0'}{d} \right) \quad (1.61)$$

where as ξ'_0 is the modified Pippard coherence length ([Tinkham, 2004]) and in presence of the perpendicular magnetic field the penetration depth is given as:

$$\lambda_{\perp} \approx \lambda_{eff}^2/d \quad (1.62)$$

here d is the film's thickness, which means that penetration depth is normally increased roughly by order of magnitude in our case which ensures that magnetic field penetration is more or less uniform and vortices are well spaced.

Flux quantization

The one of the most important mesoscopic feature of the superconductivity is flux quantization, which was defined by F. London as follows:

$$\Phi' = \Phi + \mu_0 \lambda_L^2 \oint \vec{j}_s d\vec{r} = \oint \vec{A} \cdot d\vec{r} + \mu_0 \lambda_L^2 \oint \vec{j}_s d\vec{r} \quad (1.63)$$

Now if we assume that Φ' contains the contribution from the screening current and the ordinary flux through the loop. Using the canonical momentum for the charged particle is given by $\vec{p} = m\vec{v} + q\vec{A}$ also recalling the above-defined λ_{L} and current. Applying the Bohr-Sommerfeld condition to the above equation

$$\Phi' = \oint \vec{A} \cdot d\vec{r} + \mu_0 \frac{m}{\mu_0 q^2 n_s} \oint q n_s \vec{v}_s d\vec{r} \quad (1.64)$$

$$\Phi' = \oint \left(\vec{A} + \frac{m}{q} \vec{v} \right) \cdot d\vec{r} = \frac{1}{q} \oint (q\vec{A} + m\vec{v}) \cdot d\vec{r} \quad (1.65)$$

$$\Phi' = \oint (p) \cdot d\vec{r} = n \frac{h}{q} \quad (1.66)$$

Also it was pointed out by experiments [Deaver Jr and Fairbank, 1961, Doll and Näbauer, 1961] that flux quantum is given by $h/2e$ which led to indication that $q = 2e$ in the superconductor (charge of the cooper pair).

Ginzberg-Landau theory

The idea of Ginzberg Landau (GL) theory for superconductivity (1950) came much before the celebrated BCS theory. This theory helps understand the vortices in type-II superconductors. The Ginzberg Landau theory is based on the Landau theory of phase transition, which introduces the order parameter concept. The order parameter may have different dimension depending upon the system. In case of superconductor this order parameter is a complex wave-function $\Psi(\vec{r}) = |\Psi(\vec{r})| e^{i\phi}$. The important quantity which one can observe is the mesoscopic phase ϕ . It is this phase only which gives connection to

Figure 1.7: (a)GL- free energy ($f_s - f_n$) for $T > T_c$, which implies that $\alpha > 0$ (b) for $T < T_c$ for which $\alpha < 0$

the number density $|\Psi(\vec{r})|^2 = n_s(\vec{r})$, here $n_s(\vec{r})$ is the local density of the superconducting electrons. Due to the phenomenological basis, the Ginzberg-landau theory was not widely accepted in the community. This could get attention only after Gor'kov showed that it could be derived from the BCS theory in limiting T tending to T_c . One of GL theory's achievements was the prediction of the mixed state by Abrikosov [Abrikosov, 1957].

The basic idea is very simple that order parameter is zero above the critical temperature T_c and it keeps on increasing below the T_c . In case of slowly varying $\Psi(\vec{r})$, one can expand the free energy density f in a Taylor series as given below:

$$f_s = f_n + a(T) |\Psi|^2 + \frac{1}{2} b(T) |\Psi|^4 + \frac{1}{2m^*} \left| \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \vec{\nabla} - q\vec{A} \right) \Psi \right|^2 + \frac{1}{2\mu_0} \left| \vec{B}_{ext} - \vec{B}_{int} \right|^2 \quad (1.67)$$

Here f_s and f_n describe the free energy density of the superconducting and normal states. The off powers in Ψ has been neglected because this will give negative values of free energy. The second last term describe the spatial variation of the B_{int} and $\Psi(\vec{r})$ and last term describes the energy needed to change the external field B_{ext} to internal field B_{int} . Ignoring the last two terms for some specials cases requires that b(T) must be positive, otherwise it will always leads to superconductivity as $f_s - f_n < 0$. The condition on a is for $T < T_c$ is that it must be negative to allow $f_s - f_n < 0$ for $b(T) > 0$. This scenarios is clearly shown in the figure below:

Minimizing the GL equation for superconductor yields for the case of $T < T_c$ yields $\Psi = -a/b = \psi_\infty$, here ψ_∞ is the order parameter infinity deep inside the material.

Equation (1.67) gives us the free energy density , then minimizing the eq. (1.67) with standred variation method leads to the two famous Ginzberg landau equations:

$$a|\Psi| + b|\Psi|^2\Psi + \frac{1}{2m^*} \left| \left(\frac{\hbar}{i} \vec{\nabla} - q\vec{A} \right) \right|^2 \Psi = 0 \quad (1.68)$$

$$\frac{q\hbar}{2m^*i} (\Psi^* \vec{\nabla} \Psi - \Psi \vec{\nabla} \Psi^*) - \frac{q^2}{m^*} |\Psi|^2 \vec{A} = j_s \quad (1.69)$$

The first term in the above equation is very similar to the Schrodinger equation, except for the non-linear term with eigenvalue $-\alpha$. The second term looks similar to the quantum mechanical current. It is fascinating to note that Ginzberg and Landau already pointed out that mass can be different from the mass of the electron (m_e). It turned out to be that BCS theory predicted $|q| = 2e$. This means that $m^* = 2m_e$ and $n_s = (1/2)n_e$, which will keep the London penetration depth unchanged: $m^*(q^2 n_s) = m_e/(e^2 n_e)$.

The GL theory introduces two length scales, in the presence of the small magnetic field. By taking the curl of second GL eq. (1.68), we will obtain

$$-\frac{q^2}{m^*} |\Psi|^2 \vec{B} = \nabla \times j_s \quad (1.70)$$

The above equation is equivalent to London equation and identifying $|\Psi|^2 = n_s$, will give us London penetration depth

$$\lambda_L = \sqrt{m/(\mu_0 q^2 n_s)} \quad (1.71)$$

Furthermore, BCS theory gives us.

$$\lambda_L(T) = \frac{\lambda_L(0)}{\sqrt{2(1-t)}} (\text{pure limit}), \quad (1.72)$$

$$\lambda_L(T) = \frac{\lambda_L(0)}{\sqrt{2(1-t)}} \left(\frac{\epsilon_0}{1.33l} \right)^{(1/2)} (\text{dirty limit}) \quad (1.73)$$

Now if we consider the GL eq (1.68) in the case of $B=0$, and we take Ψ to be real and normalize the wave function to $f = \Psi/\Psi_\infty$, one will get

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*|\alpha|} \frac{d^2 f}{dx^2} + f - f^3 = 0 \quad (1.74)$$

Looking at the above equation one can introduce a characteristic length scale.

$$\xi_{GL}(T) = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*|\alpha|} \right) \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-t}} \quad (1.75)$$

The above equation represents the natural length scale variation of Ψ , also called GL-coherence length. Pippard first predicted this length scale, and near the T_c , it gives us.

$$\xi_L(T) = 0.74 \frac{\xi(0)}{\sqrt{(1-t)}} (\text{pure limit}), \quad (1.76)$$

$$\xi(T) = 0.855 \frac{\sqrt{\xi_0 l}}{\sqrt{(1-t)}} (\text{dirty limit}) \quad (1.77)$$

It prompts us to define the GL parameter:

$$\kappa = \frac{\lambda_L(T)}{\xi_{GL}(T)} \quad (1.78)$$

The $\kappa = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, represents the boundary where normal to superconducting interface changes sign. Abrikosov pointed out that a higher value of κ for negative surface energies will give rise to mixed state, i.e. type II superconductor.

BCS theory

The BCS theory [Bardeen et al., 1957] is based on the idea of the formation of the cooper pair, which is the presence of attractive interaction between the conduction electron. The attraction between two electrons are thought to be mediated by the positive charge ion. The positive nuclei attract an electron, resulting in the net deformation in the lattice and slightly positive charge, which is felt by another incoming electron, resulting in the attraction between two electrons.

To understand this concept fully, let us start with a well known case of a normal metal. In the free electron approximation, their energy is given by:

$$\epsilon_k = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} (k_x^2 + k_y^2 + k_z^2) \quad (1.79)$$

it is very clear from above equation that energy depends on the wave vector $\vec{k} = (k_x, k_y, k_z)$. The electron is filled up to the sphere of radius k_f called Fermi surface; this sentence is valid for the ground state. As you increase the temperature occupancy of the electron is given by Fermi distribution function

$$f(\epsilon_k) = \frac{1}{e^{(\epsilon_k - \mu)/(k_B T)} + 1} \quad (1.80)$$

here μ is the chemical potential, which is roughly equal to the ϵ_f at very low temperatures. Now if we introduce an attractive potential $-V$, which is of the order of $\pm \hbar \omega_c$, which is tied to the fermi surface. Here attractive potential is mediated by phonons, it is easier to identify ω_c as the Debye frequency ω_D . The net result is the formation of pair between electrons with opposite spin and

momentum $\{k \uparrow, -k \downarrow\}$, whose energy is lower compared to the two unpaired electron particles:

$$\epsilon_{pair} \approx 2\epsilon_f - 2\hbar\omega_c e^{-2/N(0)V} \quad (1.81)$$

here $N(0)$ is the density of state at the Fermi energy. The wave function predicted by the Bardeen, cooper and Schrieffer is given by:

$$|\Psi_0\rangle = \prod_k (u_k |0\rangle_k + v_k |1\rangle_k) \quad (1.82)$$

here $|0\rangle_k$ denotes the unoccupied state with momentum k and $|1\rangle_k$ denotes the occupied state with momentum $-k$. The coefficients u_k and v_k are occupation probability which can elucidated by solving the Schrodinger equation and minimizing the energy with respect to u_k and v_k

$$|v_k|^2 = 1 - |u_k|^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_k - \epsilon_f}{\sqrt{|\Delta|^2 + (\epsilon_k - \epsilon_f)^2}} \right) \quad (1.83)$$

The parameter Δ is called pairing potential and is a complex number $\Delta = \Delta_0 e^{i\phi}$ and more generally Δ is given by $\Delta = -V \sum_k u_k v_k$. Normally the order of Δ_0 is the order of 1 meV.

The superconductivity can be destroyed by breaking the cooper pairs into two independent electrons. These independent electrons along with interaction is called quasi particles, whose energy is given by $E_k = \sqrt{(\epsilon_k - \epsilon_f)^2 + \Delta_0^2}$. This means that one has to give $2\Delta_0$ energy in order to excite the quasi-particle out of the gap. The quasi-particle density of state for the superconductors can be written as:

$$N_s(E_k) = N_n(\epsilon_f) \cdot \frac{|\epsilon_k - \epsilon_f|}{\sqrt{(E_k - \epsilon_f)^2 + \Delta_0^2}} \quad (1.84)$$

Here $N_n(\epsilon_f)$ is the normal density of states near Fermi energy and $N_s(E_k)$ is the superconducting density of states. It is clear that it is the temperature dependent term and $n_s \propto \Delta_0^2$, which in turn implies that mesoscopic wave-function Ψ is proportional to Δ .

The BCS theory provides us practical results which can be verified by experiments directly. One can relate $N_n(\epsilon_f)$, $\hbar\omega_c$ and V as given below:

$$T_c = 1.13 \frac{\hbar\omega_c}{k_B} \exp\left(\frac{-1}{N_n(\epsilon_f)V}\right) \quad (1.85)$$

It is easier to explain the isotope effect if one plugs the expression for Debye frequency ω_D and Ω_c , heavier atoms result in smaller oscillation frequencies, and thus T_c is reduced.

The gap Δ is related to transition temperature and zero temperature as given below:

$$E_{gap} = 2\Delta_0(T = 0) = 3.528k_B T_c \quad (1.86)$$

One of the other important relations which came out from the BCS theory is the connection between B_{c1} and B_{c2} , which is given by

$$B_{c1} = B_{c2} \frac{\ln k}{2k^2} \quad (1.87)$$

for higher k , $B_{c1} \ll B_{c2}$.

Magnetic flux dynamics

In this section, we will be dealing with the concepts of forces acting on the vortices. When you applied current through the type II superconductor in the presence of a magnetic field, it leads to vortices' movement, which leads to dissipation.

when the vortices start to move

Suppose a type 2 superconductor slab is in the xy plane and magnetic field is applied along the z -axis. When a sufficient amount of current is applied along the x -axis j_x and the magnetic field is applied along the z -axis. Flux lines start moving with velocity v_ϕ with an angle θ with the y -axis. For more clarity, look at the figure below:

at equilibrium the equation of motion becomes:

$$j_x \times \phi_0 - \epsilon n_s e v_\phi \times \phi_0 - \eta v_\phi - f_p = 0 \quad (1.88)$$

Where j_x is the current density along the x -axis, ϵ is the fraction of the force, η is the vortex motion viscosity, e is the charge of the electron $1.6e^{-19}C$, v_ϕ is the velocity of flux line, ϕ_0 is the fluxoid constant, f_p is the pinning force, n_s is the superconducting number density.

In equation (1.88) origin of the first part is the Lorentz force, the origin of the second force is Magnus force, and the third part is the dissipative force due to viscosity of the medium. It is important to note that all of the forces are given per unit length of the flux line to be consistent with the units.

The Lorentz forces tend to move the vortices perpendicular to the applied current and magnetic field, and on the other Magnus force tends to move the vortices in the direction of the applied current. Still, this force is much more visible in the presence of very clean material *i.e.* that materials which have no pinning and dissipation. Since there is a competition between these two forces, vortices tend to move at a certain angle θ to the original velocity, as shown in figure 1.8. The materials used by us are in the dirty limit ($l \ll \xi_0$), so the active fraction of the Magnus force is always much smaller than 1; hence, we neglect this term's contribution.

Figure 1.8: forces-on-the-flux-line

1.6.2 Dissipation in superconducting resonators

Superconducting resonators have very low dissipation. The reason for very low dissipation is due to the zero resistance state below the transition temperature. It is well known that there is some resistance for the alternating current in superconducting materials. Still, the skin depth in superconducting material is minimal as compared to normal metals. In general, the surface impedance is a complex quantity and is frequency dependent. The surface impedance is related to complex skin depth as:

$$\delta_s = \iota \frac{Z_s(\omega)}{\omega \mu_0} \quad (1.89)$$

Where $\omega \cdot \mu_0$ is the angular frequency and the magnetic permeability of the material, since the surface impedance is a complex quantity it can be represented as $Z_s(\omega) = \iota X_s + R_s$, here X_s is the reactive part of the impedance, and R_s is the real part of the impedance.

The superconducting transition at microwave frequencies is not very sharp compared to their DC counterparts. one gets different resistance depending upon the frequency of measurement. For $\omega = 0$ and $T < T_c$. The resistance drops very sharply, but as the frequency keeps increasing, the resistance drop becomes broader and broader. At very high frequency there exists a finite surface resistance, and the resistance drop is very minimal. The dependence of the surface resistance on temperature and frequency is given by:

$$R_s \approx A \frac{\omega^{1.7-2}}{T} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta(0)}{kT}\right) + R_0 \quad (1.90)$$

here A is material dependence parameter, and R_0 is the part of the resistance independent of the temperature. The origin of the residual resistance R_s is still a mystery and has not been understood till now. Typically the R_0 goes as ω^γ , here γ varies between 0 and 2. It has been established that material's with more purity and fewer surface defects have very low residual resistance. It has also been established that material with the very high value of T_c has minimal residual resistance compared to the material with smaller T_c , e.g. Nb_3Sn has R_0 3 order orders of magnitude smaller than the Niobium (Nb).

The quality factor of the superconducting resonator depends upon the oscillation mode and distribution of the electromagnetic field inside the resonator cavity. It is easier to predict the analytic expression for the quality for the electromagnetic resonator using skin depth and surface resistance.

$$Q_e = \frac{2}{\delta} \int H^2 dV \left| \int H^2 dS \right|^{-1} \quad (1.91)$$

By using the equation for skin depth and surface resistance, the quality factor for the superconducting resonators can be written as:

$$Q_s = \frac{\mu_0 \omega}{R_s} \int H^2 dV \left| \int H^2 dS \right|^{-1} = \frac{\Gamma}{R_s} \quad (1.92)$$

here Γ is the geometric factor, which is determined by the geometry and oscillation mode. In case the resonator cavity is filled with a dielectric, and then one has to take into account the dielectric loss. In that case, the quality factor is given by

$$Q_e^{-1} = Q_R^{-1} + Q_d^{-1} \quad (1.93)$$

1.6.3 Role of normal electron in dissipation at very low temperatures probed by superconducting NEMS

It has been a long-standing issue to measure the dissipation contribution by dissipative sources, e.g. the most notable one being the dissipation due to electron-phonon interaction and electron-electron interaction. Below 1K, the main dissipation source is supposed to be electron-electron interaction because phonons are almost non-existent at these temperatures. One should be asking a fascinating question of how to measure the dissipation due to electron electron interaction. One of the straightforward answers would be looking for the materials in which the electron interaction mechanism freezes out, what can be better than superconductivity. As we know that below the transition temperature, cooper pairs exits and hence electron-electron interaction can be ruled out, and one can know the dissipation due to normal electron. According to the BCS theory [Bardeen et al., 1957] below the transition temperature

the electronic dissipation caused by electron-phonon dissipation will vary with temperature as:

$$\frac{\Gamma(T)}{\Gamma(T_c)} = \frac{2}{\exp[\Delta(T)/k_B T] + 1} \Delta(T) = 3.52 \frac{k_B T_c}{\sqrt{1 - T/T_c}} \quad (1.94)$$

One of the experiments performed by Lulla *et al.* has probed the normal electron's role in detail in superconducting Aluminum NEMS devices [Lulla *et al.*, 2013]. They measured the dissipation in the Aluminum in the superconducting state as well as the normal state. It was found that dissipation in the normal state is proportional to $T^{0.65}$, which is typically observed power law in most metals and dissipation in the superconducting state is proportional to $T^{1.5}$. They pointed out that still, the theory needs to work out to explain such power law.

In another set of experiments performed by Suchoi *et al.* on Aluminium trampoline just below and above, the superconducting transition temperature of aluminium [Suchoi and Buks, 2017]. They fitted their result following BCS theory and found that the total contribution of the normal electron to the total damping is 20 per cent.

In other experiments performed by the Kiesel *et al.* ([Kisiel *et al.*, 2011]) to measure the normal electron's contribution, they measured the friction between the Niobium surface and AFM tip. They fitted their data in accordance with BCS theory which is quite in agreement, and results are very similar to the experiments done by suchoi *et al.* The above mentioned experiments was inspired from the experiments performed by Dayo *et al.* ([Dayo *et al.*, 1998]) in which they also observed the decrease in dissipation below superconducting temperature, although they did not talk about about the physics.

One can quickly elucidate the dissipation due to normal electrons by using the superconducting device. It is important to note that we also know that vortices exist in type II superconductor. We also know that movement of vortices create dissipation. There has been a tiny study to find the contribution toward dissipation by vortices. It will be an excellent idea to measure vortices' dissipation in type II and normal state. We are proposing to measure the dissipation due to vortices either by superconducting NEMS or by depositing type II superconductor on Quartz crystal which is very easier to handle and measure.

Chapter 2

Systems Studied and Measurement setups

This chapter summarizes the device fabrication and some generic setups repeatedly used in this thesis. I will provide additional details with the experiments in subsequent chapters. The various mesoscopic devices studied in this thesis are

- Palladium (Pd) beams. These are sub-micron in thickness, width and $4\mu m - 5\mu m$ long miniature analogs of a bridge clamped on both sides.
- Superconducting electrodes of Tantalum on a shear mode quartz oscillator.
- NbGe alloy based sub micron beams to study vortex dynamics.

In this chapter, we will be first discussing device fabrication. The latter part of this chapter focuses on the measurements of the devices since our measurements involved the RF+DC measurements and pumping of the sample space (which we will call IVC here). The sample environment involved adding H_2 . We designed and made a homemade cold finger to combine all these measurements, which we will be discussing in detail.

2.1 Device Preparation by Electron beam lithography

E-beam lithography involves using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) to write a pattern. Instead of imaging with the SEM a pattern is fed to the scan coils (similar to imputing graphics on a TV screen)

To study the dissipation in the superconducting NEMS devices, we chose two different materials. A type II superconductor Nb_3Ge , where the dissipation due to the vortices can be studied because the Nb_3Ge is a well-known type II superconductor. For dissipation studies in type I superconductor Tantalum (Ta) was chosen, the reason for choosing Ta was because of high electron-phonon coupling in the material. It will be easier to detect the strength of

electron-phonon coupling across the superconducting phase transition by the dissipation measurements [Barends et al., 2007].

Ta has a high boiling point (Ta-5731K). Hence it cannot be thermally evaporated. We deposited these materials onto the Si/SiO_2 using e gun evaporation. Nb_3Ge is deposited on the Si/SiO_2 by the co-sputtering of Niobium (Nb) and Germanium(Ge) together. The Germanium (Ge) target was sputtered with an RF power supply, and Nb was sputtered with DC power supply.

The two strategies were used to make the suspended device out of Nb_3Ge and Ta. The first strategy was to do positive lithography (direct evaporation), and the other strategy was to do negative patterning with positive resist (using reactive ion etching).

The structures were exposed by e beam lithography (make XENOS GmbH). In the figure below, I will be showing the design made for exposing the structures using XENOS software. We planned to have multiple probes so that we can do Hall and linear measurements; unfortunately, we had some problem and could bond only RF probes (which is three in number for bridge device). This will help us elucidate various material parameters like H_c , T_c , which is very important for the analysis.

2.1.1 Positive Patterning

The Palladium beams in this study were made before I joined the lab. The beams were made by simple positive patterning as discussed below. However the positive patterning did not work for several of the hard metals that need to be evaporated in an e-gun system.

In the figure 2.1 we have shown the schematics of the device designed by XENOS software. The different colour shows the different layers of e-beam lithography. Here red colour shows the first layer of lithography, and smaller green colour in the figure 2.1 shows the 2nd layer of lithography used for defining windows.

In the positive patterning, we start with standard Si/SiO_2 (250nm) 10 mm by 10 mm substrates. Then we coat a bi-layer of two resists LOR3A (bottom layer) and PMMA or ZEP520A (top layer). In the first step of lithography, we aimed to get markers, so we expose the pattern. After the developing, Ti(3nm)/Au(50nm) was deposited using thermal evaporation followed by lift-off in NMP or PG remover.

Figure 2.1: Schematic for positive patterning by the XENOS software(a) shows the image of the full device (b) shows the zoomed part of the device, smaller green colour shows the opening of window (which is exposed in 3rd layer of lithography)

Figure 2.2: Various steps involve in positive e beam lithography

In the 2nd layer of lithography, we follow the same pattern except, we wrote the bigger pattern with 500 pA current and smaller structures were written with 100 pA current. After the exposure, we deposited Nb or Ta using e beam evaporation followed by developing and lift off. In the 3rd layer of lithography, we wanted to open the window in order to release the beam; the beam was released by HF based Buffered oxide(BOE)¹ etch. The BOE is rinsed in DI water. Drying the device in DI water would collapse any nano-beams due to surface tension of the evaporating water film. A critical point dryer or freeze dryer is usually used for this purpose. We found rising the device in methanol eliminated the issue with surface tension. The whole process side view is shown in the figure 2.2.

Tantalum (Ta) is a refractory material, which means a very high melting point. An e-gun evaporator was used where a high electron current is focussed on to the material in a graphite crucible. With the e-beam evaporation, higher substrate temperature raises to 50 deg C for these materials and thus lift-off are terrible in these materials. Figure 2.3 shows some extra material still left behind even after the lift-off. Also X-rays produced by the e-gun evaporation also hardens the resist, which is an issues. This is a well-known problem in the device community and has been well documented in a paper [Soler-Delgado, 2019].

¹BOE cannot be handled without another person around for safety reasons. We used a fume hood with plastic sinks to neutralize and dispose the etchant.

Figure 2.3: Fish flip on the side of Nb structure after lift off in positive e beam lithography

2.1.2 Negative patterning

Here we deposit the film on the whole or a significant part of the wafer. Then the metal is etched in a Plasma etch system. This method is known to produce fine sub-micron features but the acquirement to isolate the device from rest of the film is troublesome.

Figure 2.4: XENOS e-beam design (a) full device, (b) zoomed view of the device

In general, it used to take me 7 hours to write four devices in one chip, but I have come up with a method to reduce the writing time to 1 hour, which is very feasible. I have to use three lithography steps and both dry and wet etching to get the final structure. I made two kinds of devices, one of which was a bridge device, and the other one was a multiprobe device. The Bridge device involves two layers of lithography, and after the 2nd layer of lithography, samples were directly dipped into HF. Since pads are much bigger than the beam size, beams will be suspended after some optimized time. Figure 2.4 shows the design of the device, which is made by the XENOS software.

The schematic view of the bridge device, as shown in figure 2.5, shows the various steps involved in the fabrication. To start with, we have Si/SiO_2 substrate coated with Nb or Ta. Over this, we deposit a single layer of ZEP 520A. The first step in the process is to get the marker for the alignment. We get the alignment marking after dry-etching the Nb or Ta with SF_6 or CF_4 (recipe is given in appendix A). The ZEP was stripped of with ZDMAC. For the second layer of lithography, we used the same steps except that for the bigger structure, we used 500 pA, and smaller structures were done with the help of 100 pA current. In the last step, beams were released using HF, followed by rinsing and drying.

Figure 2.5: Various steps of two layer lithography in negative patterning

An almost similar routine was used in three layer lithography, except that smaller windows were open to release the beam. Unlike the whole structure, only the intended part is released. Schematic for three-layer lithography using negative patterning is shown in figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Various steps of 3 layer lithography during negative patterning

The final result is evident as compared to positive e-beam lithography we did not observe any fin type of structure. The final image of the device after releasing is shown in the figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Ta beam made by Reactive ion etching and negative patterning

The most challenging problem during the fabrication of the device was releasing the beam. Most of the time, I found that beams were breaking or swinging around during the releasing of the beam. I also found that HF was eating up the window and thus making releasing the beam very difficult. The figure 2.8 shows the various kinds of beam after releasing with HF.

Figure 2.8: Various problem encountered with releasing the beam with HF

It turned out that the most straightforward solution was to post-bake the resist after developing. The figure 2.8f shows the suspended device after using the post-bake solution. Indeed, this device is much better than the rest of the devices as shown in the figure 2.8.

2.2 Transduction scheme

The challenging task in these systems is to detect the motion of the beams. The transduction here refers to converting mechanical motion into the electrical signal or vice versa, which we will be using for the actuation and detection of the beam. Till now, most of the successful techniques to detect the motion of the beam are electrical in nature *e.g.* electrodynamics, electrostatic, thermoelastic, piezoresistive, piezoelectric. The nano-mechanical beam coupled with these electrical means is known as a nanoelectrical mechanical system or, in short, as NEMS devices. In this chapter, we will be briefly talking about the two methods, which are electrodynamics transduction and piezoelectric transduction.

2.2.1 Magnetomotive method (Actuation and Detection)

To actuate and detect the motion of the NEMS devices magnetomotive method was developed by Roukes and Cleland [Cleland and Roukes, 1999]. This method has been used in fundamental research for decades, and it is very famous among the superfluid He^3 community, and it has been used in the transduction of thermometers and viscometer [Bäuerle et al., 1998, Guénault et al., 1986]. This technique is most widely used in the research community because of its simplicity.

The actuation mechanism in the magnetomotive method is the Lorentz force. Here the current $I(t)$ flows through the suspended beam, which is in the z -direction. The applied magnetic field (B) is in the y -direction. As a result, the beam experiences a Lorentz force that forces the beam to flex out of the plain. Suppose that a sinusoidal current $I(t)$ flows through the beam with frequency closer to the fundamental mode, and the applied field is in the y -direction. The schematic for the magnetomotive setup is described in the figure 2.9.

Then the force experienced by a small portion dl of the beam can be written as:

$$dF_{Lor}(z, t) = I(t)dl(z) \times B \quad (2.1)$$

The maximum amplitude of the beam in our case is 0.001% as compared to the length of the beam. Then the above eqn. (2.1) can be simplified for the n^{th} mode as:

$$dF_{Lor}(z, t) \approx I(t)B\Psi_n(z)dz \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.9: The schematic for the transduction with magnetomotive method for the fundamental mode. The applied magnetic field is along Y axis which is out of plane and applied alternating current is along the z axis. This results in the alternating Lorentz force which points towards x axis. As a result of which, beam moves in and out of the equilibrium position and the magnetic flux changes because of the movement of beam. This gives rise to an induced e.m.f, which can be used to calculate the maximum displacement of the beam at the resonance frequency.

one can calculate the Lorentz force on the beam (which is along x axis) by integrating over the whole beam. Then one gets

$$F_{Lor}(L, n) = \epsilon_n I(t) B l \quad (2.3)$$

where ϵ_n is the mode shape factor, the mode shape factor accounts for the non uniformity of the force along x axis. The mode shape factor in the case of string limit can be written as:

$$\epsilon_n = \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} \Psi_n(z) dz \quad (2.4)$$

In case of the doubly clamped beam in the string limit, $\Psi_n(z)$ can be written as: $\Psi_n(z) = \sin(\lambda_n z)$. The λ_n is the eigen vector and plugging the value of Ψ_n in the eqn. (2.4) which gives us $\epsilon_n = 2/[(n+1)\pi]$. It must be noted that n is odd here because the shape factor for even mode does not contribute.

As we know that for a wire moving inside a uniform magnetic field, the charges inside the wire experience Lorentz force. When the beam moves, the areas beam swept when at rest and in motion differs, which means that the amount of flux swept is changing with time. If we used the forced oscillating excitation, then one can write the magnetic flux crossing a certain area as:

$$d^2\phi(t) = B \cdot d^2 A(t) dx \quad (2.5)$$

In the small deflection limit the eqn. (2.5) can be simplified as:

$$d^2 A_n(t) \approx \Psi_n(z) dz dx(t) \quad (2.6)$$

After integrating the eqn (2.5) over the whole length of the beam, differential magnetic flux can be written as:

$$d\Phi_n(t) = \epsilon_n I B dx(t) \quad (2.7)$$

Since the excitation of the beam is time-dependent, the motion of the beam is also time-dependent. This oscillating motion of the beam produces an oscillating area of magnetic flux swept by the beam. According to the Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction, this change in the magnetic flux produces emf (electromotive force) $e(t)$ in addition to the ohmic response of the beam, which is given as:

$$e(t) = -\frac{d\phi}{dt} = -\epsilon_n l B \frac{dx}{dt} \quad (2.8)$$

The eqn.(2.8) gives us an interesting point of view that the resulting voltage which we are measuring is directly proportional to the velocity of the beam. In the frequency domain this velocity will also be sinusoidal with an angular frequency ω and will have the form $v(\omega) = i\omega x(\omega)$. It can be seen that in this case, the detected voltage drop $e(\omega)$ is proportional to the complex amplitude of the $x(\omega)$, which means that displacement lags behind the velocity by $\pi/2$; hence displacement and velocity form the quadrature. Overall this technique is very convenient, and it is mainly because of few reasons.

- The same principle does the actuation and detection of the beam, and it can be integrated on the same device, so it is effortless to implement.
- The magnetomotive method is very linear because the applied force is independent of the displacement. The method is uniform as the applied magnetic field is uniform compared to the NEMS device scale.

There are few drawbacks of this method, and definitely, for very sensitive measurements, some other methods will have an edge over the magnetomotive method.

- One can detect only the odd mode of the resonance, and even modes are undetectable with this method. The spatial profile for even mode contributes nothing towards the integrated detected voltage, so even mode shape factor $\epsilon = 0$.
 - The voltage developed is directly proportional to the applied magnetic field, and hence one needs a magnetic field with a higher strength to resolve the signals from noise. For this purpose, one need superconducting magnets, which are very expensive.
-

- The magnetomotive sensitivity is poor, and it decays quadratically with the applied magnetic field. The lowest limit for the detection of averaged NEMS device is a few fractions of a manometer. For more sensitivity one should look for other means *e.g.* optical method [Hadjjar et al., 1999].
- This method induces external dissipation due to Lenz's law, which we will be discussing later.

External loading due to the electrical circuit

As we know that in presence of the magnetic field, an electromotive force (e.m.f.) is generated to oppose the motion of the beam due to the Lorentz force. The e.m.f. is generated in addition to the ohmic dissipation. The induced e.m.f. electrically looks like parallel LCR characteristics, which makes it interesting because electrically, it looks like a parallel LCR circuit loaded by external impedance as shown in the figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: LCR representation of the mechanical resonator in combination with external impedance, this external impedance include the device resistance and rest of the circuit which was used in the measurements.

In the reference [Cleland and Roukes, 1999], a direct correspondence between the equivalent electrical circuits (which are R_m, L_m, C_m) with the mechanical parameter (ω_m , linewidth, mass and length) has been shown in the presence of magnetic field. The equivalent electrical circuit can be written as:

$$\omega_m = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L_m C_m}} \quad (2.9a)$$

$$\Gamma_m = \frac{1}{R_m C_m} \quad (2.9b)$$

The total impedance as seen by the VNA or lock-in amplifier can be written as $Z_{ext} = R_{ext} + \iota X_{ext}$, which can be obtained as:

$$Z_{load}(\omega) = \frac{\iota\omega/C_m}{\iota\omega \left(\gamma_m + \frac{R_{ext}}{C_m |Z_{ext}|^2} \right) + \omega_m^2 - \omega^2 + \omega \frac{X_{ext}}{C_m |Z_{ext}|^2}} \quad (2.10)$$

One can write one to one correspondence between the observed e.m.f and external loaded circuit as:

$$\frac{\epsilon_n^2 l^2 B^2}{m_n} = \frac{1}{C_m} \quad (2.11a)$$

$$Z_c = \frac{\xi B^2 l^2}{2\pi f_0 m} \quad (2.11b)$$

$$\Gamma = \Gamma_m + \frac{R_{ext}}{|Z_{ext}|^2} \frac{\epsilon_n^2 l^2 B^2}{m_n} \quad (2.11c)$$

$$f_{res}^2 = f_m \sqrt{1 + \frac{X_{ext}}{|Z_{ext}|^2} \frac{\epsilon_n^2 l^2 B^2}{m_n \omega}} \quad (2.11d)$$

here Z_c is the characteristic impedance of the measurement system and Z_{ext} is the external impedance of the circuit. The loaded quality factor can be written as $\Gamma = \Gamma_m(1 + \alpha B^2)$ which implies from the eqn. (2.11c) $\alpha = \frac{\xi l^2}{2\pi f_0 m} \frac{R_{ext}}{|Z_{ext}|^2}$

Similarly we get the resonance frequency of the device which also get loaded by the application of magnetic field and has quadratic B dependence. The loaded resonance frequency is given by equation (2.11d). Loaded frequency simply can be written as $f_{res}^2 = f_m^2(1 + \beta B^2)$, here $\beta = \frac{\xi f_0 l^2}{2\pi m} \frac{X_{ext}}{|Z_{ext}|^2}$.

This value of α and β is used to get the intrinsic quality factor and resonance frequency of the device [Rebari et al., 2017, Venkatesan et al., 2010]. The equation 2.11 roughly means that our measurement is normalized by the applied field and external electrical circuit. The relative change in frequency in the measured beam is very small, which is of the order of 10^{-5} , but the relative change in the case of damping can be comparable. It can be seen from eq.2.11 that a longer beam is more affected by these losses.

The properties of the measured beam are the response of the coupled system, which is the mechanical system with the external magnetic field and external electrical circuit. Hence we always measure the hybridize response. If the coupling of the NEMS device is more with the electrical circuitry, it will lead to more dissipation, but high coupling leads to a good resolution. This leads to the trade-off between high-quality factor device (high impedance) and coupling strength to do some meaningful measurement by this method.

Figure 2.11: Measurement scheme for the magneto-motive method. The input lines were attenuated by 10 dB at each stage and output line was attenuated with 1 dB to avoid the reflections, which makes the total attenuation 41 dB (inside the dilution refrigerator). This 41 dB is shown by the big blue dot after the splitter. The input lines were further attenuated externally by variable attenuator which is kept at the room temperature.

The internal wiring of the fridge during the non-linear measurement of the Palladium nanomechanical beam is shown in the figure 2.11. The input line was attenuated at each stage with 10 dB of attenuation to maximize the thermalization. To get the base temperature and the output line was attenuated with 1 dB to minimize the reflection. The bias tee was added to each

line to save the sample from the static; we can also do the DC measurements. The signal from the output line was amplified with low noise preamplifier (make MITEQ and mini circuits), before being measured by VNA (make Rhode Schwartz ZVB-14). The input signal was split (mini circuit power splitter) to provide the bridge device's signal. The signal was attenuated to the desired level using variable attenuator so that the temperature of the dilution fridge does not rise above the base temperature achieved.

The typical response of the Pd NEMS device in the vacuum as measured by the VNA in transmission configuration is shown in the figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12: Response of the Pd NEMS device in vacuum measured in the above mentioned configuration. The measurement was done at 9T and the temperature was 110mK. The blue dots is the raw data and red line is the Lorentzian fit to the raw data.

2.2.2 Piezoelectric method

Piezo-electricity is the property of the material such that whenever material is deformed it generates charge. Mathematically speaking it is the coupling between the elastic and electric constitutional equations, it can be written as:

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \tilde{\sigma}_{kl} + d_{ijk} E_k \quad (2.12a)$$

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_i = C_{ij} \sigma_j + d_{ij} E_j \quad (2.12b)$$

$$D_i = \epsilon_{ij} E_j + d_{ij}^T \sigma_j \quad (2.12c)$$

Here ϵ are the stress vectors, σ are the strain vectors (1×6 vectors), and the $\tilde{\sigma}$ are their counterparts which are tensor (3×3 matrix), E is the electric field, and D is the displacement field. C is the compliance matrix (6×6 matrix), and

\tilde{C} is the fourth rank compliance tensor. ϵ is the dielectric permittivity, and d is the piezoelectric matrix (3×6) matrix.

The eqn.(2.12c) represents the coupling between the electric field and displacement field; this part is zero for non-piezoelectric material.

Actuation with piezoelectric method

The application of a voltage across the two electrodes of the piezoelectric material generates an electric field. The equation (2.12b) represents that an application of voltage generates an electric field. The resultant electric field will create strain in the structure. This will force the beam out of equilibrium. The coefficient d_{31} and d_{33} gives the direct information about the deformation in the thickness or lateral modes. The actuation of shear modes of the quartz crystal with the alternating voltage is shown in the figure

Figure 2.13: Actuation of the Quartz crystal (A) Quartz crystal without application of AC voltage, (B) Shear mode of the quartz crystal with the application of AC voltage.

Detection with piezoelectric method

If one looks carefully at the equation (2.12c), it tells us that there will be a displacement field even in the absence of an electric field. From Maxwell equations, we know that changing the displacement field will induce a displacement current.

$$I_D(t) = \int \frac{\partial D(t)}{\partial t} dA \quad (2.13)$$

The resulting current from changing displacement field can be easily measured [Schmid et al., 2016].

2.2.3 Measurement setup for actuating and detecting the quartz crystal response

The electric friction measurement with quartz crystal was done with RF lock-in amplifier (SR 844). We deposited 2 nm of Nb over the quartz substrate

with Au, which acts as the adhesion layer for the Ta. Then 50 nm of Ta was deposited over the Nb. Both Nb (seed layer) and Ta were deposited with the help of e-gun evaporation. In the last 3-5 nm of Pd was deposited over it with the help of thermal source place in the same chamber. All these deposition were done in-situ without breaking the vacuum. The schematic diagram for the measurement of quartz crystal with lock-in amplifier in both reflection and transmission measurement is shown in figure 2.14

Figure 2.14: Transmission mode measurement with high frequency lock in amplifier (LIA). The signal from the signal generator was split into two equal halves. One half of the signal was used for referencing the lock in amplifier, while the other half (which is 180 degree out of phase with reference to first half) was sent to the input of the quartz crystal which was attenuated externally with variable attenuator to keep the quartz crystal in the linear regime. The other electrode of quartz crystal was connected to the input of the lock in amplifier.

The typical response of the Quartz crystal in the transmission configuration is shown in the figure 2.15. It can be seen from the figure 2.15 that there are two modes of resonance which corresponds to series resonance and parallel resonance.

Figure 2.15: The logarithmic response (absolute magnitude R part of the lock in amplifier) of the quartz crystal in the transmission configuration at room temperature. The arrows in figure shows the series and resonance mode of the quartz crystal which corresponds to the minimum and maximum impedance of the quartz crystal response.

Transmission measurements are equivalent to performing conductance measurement, which is why at series resonance, transmission (as the impedance is minimum) is maximum. On the other hand, transmission is minimum in the parallel (as the impedance is maximum) configuration. In our measurement, we were mainly interested in the series resonance as it represents the actual change in the properties of quartz crystals. The Q factor of the series resonance usually is lower than the parallel resonance frequency. This is because the series mode is strongly coupled to the system while the parallel mode is weakly coupled. The parallel resonance frequency typically depicts the change in geometrical capacitance.

We have measured the response of the Ta coated quartz crystal with the temperature. This was done in order to study the sliding friction across the superconducting transition of Ta. The quartz crystal was cooled in commercial (make Janis Research Company) made He^3 wet refrigerator which is capable of reaching 300 mK with the hold time of 90 hours. In our experiments we had to introduce hydrogen in order to study the sliding friction, these commercial system provides very reliable solution by providing Inner vacuum can (IVC) which is isolated from the rest of system. This can be a huge problem in case of dry refrigerators. The later section is devoted to sort out this issue with dry

refrigerators. Image of the He^3 refrigerator used during the measurements is shown in the figure 2.16

2.2.4 Coldfinger with RF and DC feedthru for diffusion and non linear damping experiments

Modern-day dry refrigerators have only a single vacuum space. Experiments that have to be done in the presence of some atmosphere require a can that has to be hermetically sealed (which is called Inner Vacuum Can (IVC) in wet fridges). Hermetic seals are generally made with rubber gaskets. To do transport measurements, one needs to have leak-tight electrical conductors. Most of the transport measurements are done at liquid Helium temperatures. At these temperatures, usually, gaskets do not survive. One must be aware of Richard Feynman's famous investigations on O-rings that became less resilient at ice temperatures causing failure of NASA's challenger shuttle disaster [Erdody, 1986].

At liquid helium temperatures, vacuum seals are generally made with material like soap/glycerine [Mota, 1971], pliable metals like Indium (In) [Willis, 1958], Aluminium (Al), or epoxies. we did not find soap/glycerine reliable, epoxies normally tend to overflow, which damages the flanges, and they are hard to remove [Richardson and Smith, 1988, White and Meeson, 1959]. We wanted to study the dissipation in the metallic resonator in the presence of the Hydrogen H_2 atmosphere. More detail about this, you can find here [Rebari et al., 2017]. We needed to send an RF signal through a leak-tight vacuum can because the experiments have to be done in H_2 environment [Kumar et al., 2020]. To send an RF or microwave signal, the commercial solution is to use an RF connector that uses rubber-O-ring. This Hermetic RF connector sits on the top of the cryostat, which is at room temperature. Another commercial solution is to provide weldable connectors, which are permanent. While welding, they also change Oxygen Free High Conductivity (OFHC) copper properties, which is of paramount importance for thermal conductivity at low temperatures.

We designed a simple inner vacuum can (IVC in wet refrigerators) to work with commercial RF feedthru's. This feed-through could work at Liquid He temperatures. This is a simple solution to the weldable connectors, which tends to change the material's thermal properties. It is also hard to find the dielectrics of RF connectors, which will withstand high temperatures while welding.

In figure 2.17, we have the CAD design of the full cold finger, which was made with AutoDesk Fusion 360 [Hirschtick, 1995]. In figure 2.18, we have shown the CAD of the lid, which has a smaller 1/8" countersink hole. We decided to use two of them for the DC lines and one for the pumping line to evacuate the can. The extruded central part is 6 mm threaded, which was to be made from a single brass piece, which will be connected to the mixing

Figure 2.16: He^3 refrigerator. (A) Full image of the He^3 refrigerator with the Dewar, (B) shows the indium sealed IVC can, (C) shows the inside part of the IVC which encloses the sample, (D) shows the hermetic sealed RF connector (rubber sealed) at the top of the cryostat.

chamber of the dilution refrigerator through the 12 mm solid rod, made out of OFHC copper. The three bigger holes (13mm) was to mount the hermetic RF connector.

We have used stainless steel-316 (SS) 1/8" tube as a medium to create the vacuum inside the can and also to create the H_2 atmosphere. The reason for choosing SS is that this SS line goes from the room temperature to the IVC can, so the amount of heat transfer will be huge, but because SS has low thermal conductivity with a combination of smaller tube size 1/8" decrease its thermal conductivity. This SS-316 line was brazed into the brass can. DC feed-through was made by brazing a 1/8" brass tube into the can and then twisted pair cable was passed through it. Then we used low viscous stycast, which we filled inside the DC feedthru's [Henkel, 1876b, Henkel, 1876a], and it was kept overnight to cure the stycast.

RF feed-through was made by using SMA Jack-to-Jack adapter hermetic connector bought from Huber-Suhner [Huber, 2015]. The problem with connectors is they provide Viton o-ring for the sealing, which will crack at low temperature, so we use indium as a sealing material, which forms a very well known sealant material [Richardson and Smith, 1988].

The vacuum can seal was made with standard Indium wire, where the indium O-ring was squeezed by screws tightening the lid. The lid of the can have an almost 0.5 mm protruding structure, which was made with the purpose to crush the Indium, while tightening the screws of the lid. In the lid, we made three countersink holes of diameter 13mm to fit the hermetically sealed Huber-suhner connector. We replaced the Viton-O ring of the connector with a 1.5 mm diameter Indium. This thickness (1.5 mm) of the Indium wire was not available, so we made a homemade Indium extruder, with the help of which one can make Indium wire of any diameter, just by changing the size of the hole in the die. A socket was made to hold the connector from the top, and the bottom nut was tightened with the help of a wrench. This connector was left to relaxed by itself as Indium can reflow after putting too much pressure, the connector was retightened after few hours, and this process was done 4-5 times. This assembly was connected to the Adixen ASM 182 TD+ leak detector at room temperature. At room temperature the leak rate was $2-7 \times 10^{-9} \text{mbarl/s}$. This leak rate is already better than the RF connector's leak rate $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{mbarl/s}$, as mentioned in the connector's technical datasheet. This could be because the Viton -O ring is permeable to Helium. Then we checked the whole assembly in the liquid Nitrogen for the leaks, and the leak rate was similar to the leak rate at room temperature, i.e. $2 - 7 \times 10^{-9} \text{mbarl/s}$. Then we attached the whole unit to the dilution refrigerator, and the assembled can was pumped to 10^{-5}mbar . Then we introduced 10 mbar of H_2 gas inside the IVC, and then it was pumped down to 10^{-2}mbar . If there are leaks in the IVC, it will disturb OVC's (Outer Vacuum Can) vacuum, resulting in the swift cooling of the dilution refrigerator. Pirani and Penning gauge's readings in the OVC will

Figure 2.17: Full image of the cold finger with RF and DC feedthru, including the IVC. The left side of the figure shows the full coldfinger with Faraday cage which was slitted (holes which is shown by white cylinders) at some portions in order to minimize the eddy current damping. The middle figure shows the coldfinger after removing the Faraday cage which includes IVC, central rod which is attached to the mixing chamber, vacuum and DC lines feedthru. The right figure shows the section view of the Indium sealed IVC where the sample is kept. The golden part represents the PCB and red part is the sample.

Figure 2.18: Zoomed in view of the main part of coldfinger with hermetic SMA connector with pumping line and DC lines. The four D shape cut is made by wire cut which is suppose to hold the SMA's. There are four SS lines which have copper at both top and bottom. The upper copper is brazed to the SS in order to fill the stycast and the bottom copper was brazed in order to give uniform pressure to crush the indium equally. Out of four, the plan was to use three for DC lines and one for the pumping the IVC.

Figure 2.19: Left figure shows the front side of the RF+DC feedthru. The black part is the stycast and wire used for the DC connection was made of Manganin. The right figure shows the back side of RF+DC feedthru. The 12 pin male cryogenic connector from the CMR direct is also visible.

also be affected as leakage in IVC, which will vary due to varying ionization of H_2 from Nitrogen. We did not see any of the effects, as mentioned above. After warming the refrigerator, we rechecked the leak, and we did not find any leak, which proves the stability of hermetically sealed RF connectors.

It must be noted that a full working setup with RF+DC feedthru is complicated to make, the reason being that there are too many connections. Ensuring that all the joints are leak-tight is very challenging. One such try for doing RF+DC feedthru work is shown in the figure 2.19. Figure 2.19 shows both the front and the backside of the connector. The extra stycast was put on the hermitic SMA to ensure that it does not leak while retightening.

We know that doing both RF and DC measurement together can be challenging, and maintaining that kind of IVC is also tricky. We also designed an IVC lid with a DC feedthru and a vacuum line. This was much easier to make as there were fewer connections to make. It must be noted that making RF feedthru is not straightforward, as connector tends to leak from the joints. On the other hand, DC wire can be fixed permanently with stycast. Figure 2.20 shows the DC feedthru with a vacuum line.

It must be noted that all the three SS lines here were directly brazed to the copper and then stycast was applied on the sides, to make sure that it remains leak tight. The measurements on the topological insulator which is mentioned in the appendix is done by this coldfinger.

Figure 2.20: Left figure shows the front side of the DC feedthru and right figure shows the back side of DC feedthru. The black part is the stycast which was coated on the sides in order to make sure that the brazing part remains leak tight.

2.3 Low frequency wiring for dilution refrigerator

The main challenge in doing low-frequency measurement is to avoid it with high frequency. In our case, DC lines were filtered at room temperature as well as low temperature. Schoelkopf *et.al.* [Spietz *et al.*, 2006] devised a low pass filter that will work at cryogenic temperature, which is just the manganin wire wrapped in copper tape. The copper tape filter works as an excellent low pass filter placed at the mixing chamber plate of the dilution refrigerator.

The filter at room temperature was placed inside the breakout box to avoid noise. It is a coil type EMI filter manufactured by Panasonic (part no. ELEK 103FA). It is a T type filter consisting of a capacitor and 2 ferrite inductors. The PCB was made by home-made setup, and the figure 2.21 shows the landing pattern of the filter designed using Inkscape. The landing pattern of the filter was printed on the transparent sheet, and then by optical lithography (home-made setup), the circuit was fabricated on the PCB. The last filter was stuck to PCB using solder paste.

These low pass filters were enclosed in a breakout box made out of a 2 mm thick aluminium sheet (to avoid em interference). A CNC machine made the hole for mounting the BNC. The gaps in the breakout box were covered by the combination of copper and aluminium tapes to avoid the interference of the external em waves with the actual signal. The image of the breakout box is shown in the figure 2.22. All the BNC's were connected to the two 25 pins D-sub female connectors, which in turn was connected to the Hermetic

Figure 2.21: The top figure shows the landing pattern of the filter printed on the transparent sheet. The middle figure shows the landing pattern fabricated on the PCB and the bottom figure shows the low pass filter on the PCB. This low pass filter decrease the overall noise of the system which was shown by the increase of overload range of the AC gain. These filters were used successfully in the measurement of topological superconductors (mentioned in the appendix) and on low frequency characterization of other material used in the group.

Figure 2.22: Image of the breakout box enclosing low pass ferrite filters.

Fischer connector. The wiring from the breakout box to the Fischer connector was done with low noise cable bought from the CMR Direct [Haselwimmer, 2021] and this portion of wiring was done by my labmate Shyam Sundar. The Hermetic Fischer connector was connected on the top of the cryostat, from the top plate to the mixing chamber of the dilution refrigerator wiring (in the form of ribbons) was done by oxford instruments.

Figure 2.23: Frequency response of the low pass filter

The low pass filter works really well, and the cut of this filter is around 50kHz, as shown in the figure 2.23. The data for the low pass filter was acquired using a lock and amplifier.

Chapter 3

Non-linear dissipation in the Palladium Nano-mechanical beams

This chapter will discuss the non-linear response of doubly clamped Palladium (Pd) nano-mechanical beams. We happen to observe non linear damping in damping in these systems and this forms the central part of this chapter. In the first section of this chapter, we had reviewed the linear dissipation studies on the Pd beams in vacuum, which were soaked in low pressures of H_2 followed by nonlinear response.

Nano-electrical-mechanical systems (NEMS) have found applications in filters, oscillators, and switches [Schmid et al., 2016, Blencowe, 2004]. Hooke's law for a linear spring $F = -kx$ with a potential of the form $U = kx^2/2$ describes a variety of linear oscillatory systems and not limited to a mass and spring [Halliday et al., 2013]. In a system like a beam the k can be a k_{eff} describing a normal mode of the beam [Landau and Lifshitz, 2000]. When any continuum mechanical system is driven hard one has to consider the effective potential beyond the linear terms. This leads to restoring forces of the form $F = -kx - \alpha x^3$. Such systems are the well know Duffing Oscillator systems [Lakshmanan and Rajaseekar, 2012b, Lifshitz and Cross, 2008]

Because of the aspect ratio of nano-mechanical device structures (e.g, like width or thickness of doubly clamped beams or cantilevers), it is easy to observe duffing type non-linear behaviour in nano-mechanical structures [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008].

Few applications of nano-mechanical devices operating in the non-linear regimes includes applications like logic gates [Guerra et al., 2010], stochastic resonance [Badzey and Mohanty, 2005], electromechanical frequency mixers [Erbe et al., 2000], controlling the residual strain [Samanta et al., 2019], mass and force sensing [Ekinici et al., 2004]. A quantized harmonic oscillator states are evenly spaced but an anharmonic oscillator states are not [Merzbacher, 1998] making it easy to distinguish states. Hence any non-linear NEMS device is a candidate for engineering quantum states [Katz et al., 2007]. Therefore the understanding of non-linear response of nano-mechanical resonators is of

fundamental importance.

In general, damping in resonators is described by linear damping force, which is normally proportional to the velocity ($f_l \propto \gamma v$) [Halliday et al., 2013].

The collision of the gas molecules with the Pd NEMS device will also create dissipation. In our case, the measurements were done below 1K. At these temperatures, the cryo-vacuum is very good, and everything freezes at this temperature except Helium. Before cooling down the sample, the sample space was pumped to 5×10^{-4} mbar when $T \sim 170\text{K}$, which is already good vacuum for NEMS devices due to its small cross section. The walls are expected to cryo pump at lower temperatures and H_2 also solidifies below 10 K.

On the other hand, nonlinear damping has not been studied extensively and it is due to the product of position and velocity ($f_{nl} \propto x^2 v$). In this chapter, we have studied the non-linear damping in the palladium resonator cooled down in vacuum and low pressures of H_2 .

Palladium's ability to adsorb H_2 is well known and it is expected to form protons in interstitial sites of the Pd lattice. The ability of Pd to adsorb H_2 has been used to make ppm level nano-mechanical H_2 sensors [Huang et al., 2005]. The adsorption of H_2 in the Pd interstitial sites causes the stress. This was used in previous experiments in our lab to tune quantum friction scenarios [Rebari et al., 2017]. We found devices exposed to low pressures of H_2 also showed enhanced non-linear damping as well as Duffing non-linearity.

Many sub-micron mechanical systems have shown non linear damping such as carbon nanotube [Eichler et al., 2011], graphene beams [Singh et al., 2016], long beams of AuPd [Zaitsev et al., 2012], graphene drums [Miao et al., 2014] and diamond resonators [Imboden et al., 2013]. Theoretically, understanding the physical origin of these systems is still very minimal. In systems like graphene, the origin of non-linear damping has been attributed to the inter-modal coupling [Croy et al., 2012]. Graphene being an ultra thin solid with defects like crinkles can support several closely spaced modes to which energy can be dissipated.

We studied the effect of temperature on the non-linear damping coefficient η and non-linear coefficient α from 110 mK to 1.35K. We found the strong temperature dependence of non-linear damping in Pd beams soaked in H_2 as well as enhancement of the Duffing constant α .

3.1 Introduction

3.1.1 Overview of linear dissipation TLS phenomena in Pd nanomechanical beams

Quantum friction caused by TLS has been seen in several metallic nano-mechanical systems [Sulkko et al., 2010, Hoehne et al., 2010, Venkatesan et al., 2010]. Surprisingly there was massive interest in studying the mechanical

properties of dielectrics, superconductors, and metallic systems at very low temperature using the vibrating reed method [Esquinazi, 2013]. Despite the diversity of systems ranging from crystalline to amorphous solids there is some universal behaviour. This universality is not like a scaling in a phase transition but more of the order of magnitude of dissipation. These systems also show similarity to glassy systems.

At low temperatures there are few excitations of quasi-particles like phonons. As explained in the previous chapter excitations to higher energy levels at low temperatures are very less probable. Hence any imperfections like a foreign atom, a vacancy *etc.* can be modeled by mapping it to a TLS (Two level system). What is a TLS and how can it be tuned is an interesting problem.

In our group's past work on Pd NEMS devices, we could tune the TLS-phonon interaction by adding H_2 over a Pd nanomechanical beam. The resulting stress due to adsorption of H_2 acts like a pseudo-Zeeman field on the TLS, which allows one to tune the TLS-phonon interaction [Rebari et al., 2017]. The adsorption of H_2 can relieve the built-in stress due to the difference in thermal contraction between the metal beam and a silicon wafer. The above-mentioned effect has been used in the sensing of H_2 in the Au-Pd beams [Huang et al., 2005]. In this experiment, we studied the doubly clamped Pd beam from 0.11K to 2 K. To extract the tune-ability of TLS interaction, experiments were performed on the Pd NEMS device with and without the addition of H_2 . The Pd NEMS devices showed the typical logarithmic dependence of the resonance frequency below 1K, and quality factor follows a sub-linear power-law, which can be described by standard tunneling model (STM) [Raychaudhuri and Hunklinger, 1984, Esquinazi, 2013]. The typical power law for the earlier studied Pd beam both in presence of H_2 and absence of H_2 ranges from 0.55 to 0.36 [Rebari et al., 2017] which is shown in the table below.

Device	Power law	T_{co}
Vacuum 19 MHz	0.39	1K
Vacuum 29 MHz	0.41	1K
2e-3 mbar of Hydrogen (19 MHz)	0.37	0.7K
2e-3 mbar of Hydrogen (20 MHz)	0.43	0.7K
1e-2 mbar of Hydrogen (20 MHz)	0.44	0.6K

The difference between the experiments performed with Pd beam with and without H_2 was the cross over temperature, which shows the shift with the addition of H_2 . The cross over temperature is defined as the temperature at which $\omega\tau = 1$, where ω is the beam resonance frequency, and τ is the phonon relaxation rate. The T_{co} is defined as the temperature at which the resonance frequency of the device changes slope. The observed T_{co} is 1K for the experiment done on the sample without H_2 , while the soaked samples in the H_2 atmosphere showed the T_{co} around 700 mK. This indicates the enhanced TLS-phonon interaction based on the standard tunnelling model. There is

also a saturation in dissipation at lower temperatures in the sample with H_2 compared to their counterpart in vacuum, which may be due to super-radiant interaction between phonon and TLS [Rebari et al., 2017, Ahn and Mohanty, 2003].

3.2 Measurement Scheme and Devices

We discussed the details of the Lorentz force based magneto-motive transduction schemes in the last chapter. Each device has a set of two sub-micron beams forming a balanced bridge. One device from each set was measured.

- Sample B1 in Set B

The sample B1 had dimensions of $4.35\mu m \times 390nm$ and sample B2 with dimensions of $4.5\mu m \times 366nm$, both with 80 nm thickness. We have put 2×10^{-3} torr of H_2 at the room temperature and pumped to lower $\sim 10^{-4}$ torr when the fridge was at around 170 K. The power to drive this sample in to the non-linear regime was as low as $-93dBm$.

- Sample A1 in Set A

Sample A1 of dimensions $4.5\mu m \times 430nm$ and A2 $4.5\mu m \times 470nm$. This sample was cooled down in vacuum without any exchange gas of H_2 . This sample required a power of $-80dBm$ to reach non-linear behaviour.

The young modulus of the Pd is $\approx 115GPa$ [Vaz et al., 2003] which was used in estimating the frequencies along with thermal contraction induced tensile stress with respect to the substrate [Li et al., 2008] as discussed in previous chapter. Our beams always showed some Euler buckling after measurements (irrespective of whether it was cooled with H_2 or in vacuum.) We cannot know the true state of our beams at low temperatures. Small imperfections in width or sub-micron burrs in device boundary may alter frequency.

The resonators were cooled down to 110mK in the dilution refrigerator, and the experimental setup for the measurements is shown in the figure 2 of chapter 2. The sample was also heated to a higher temperature to see the effect of temperature on the non-linear damping. We have measured the transmission (also known as S_{21}) through the bridge device. The bridge helps minimize the background, and the output of the bridge is proportional to the e.m.f. generated by the beam's motion.

The signal reaching the resonator was heavily attenuated at both room temperature as well at low temperature as discussed in last chapter. One cannot apply too much power to the NEMS devices as it easily gets damaged. The bias T was used in order to save the samples from the static discharges while cooling down. The Q factor of the device changes from ~ 9800 to ~ 19000 , when the temperature of the resonator is varied between 110 mK to 1.35K. In order to observe the nonlinearity in these devices, the maximum

Figure 3.1: SEM image of the prepared devices (sample set B and A) before and after the measurements. (A) represents the SEM image of the hydrogenated device before the measurement and (B) represents the SEM image of the device after the measurements. (C) represents the SEM image of the device in vacuum before measurement while (D) represents the SEM image of the device after the measurements.

power applied was -93 dBm for the hydrogenated sample and -80 dBm for the non-hydrogenated sample.

Figure 3.2: The S_{21} response of the device with varying power in VNA. At different deriving powers all the curve fall on top of each other which indicates that device is still in the linear regime. The measurement was done at 110mK and applied magnetic field was 4T

The power applied to our sample is very small ($\approx -80dBm$) at maximum, so there is no question of Joule heating. Here we have studied the detailed response of the Pd NEMS device, both in the presence and absence of H_2 . We were mainly interested in the temperature dependence of the non-linear dissipation rather than the linear dissipation. The measurement schematic of the device has been discussed in the chapter 2.

3.2.1 Response beyond linear regime

We use measurements from a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) to explain how to identify the shift from linear to non-linear behaviour. The VNA measures the S_{21} parameters of the S-matrix in transmission mode [Pozar, 2011]. The measured $S_{21} \propto \left[\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \right]$ where P_{out} is the output response power of the device and P_{in} the drive power. Hence all responses are scaled by drive powers. Since

VNA measures the normalized amplitude of the device, which means that if the device is in the linear regime, the response curve should fall on top of each other as shown in figure 3.2. This data has been taken at approximately 110mK, and the applied magnetic field was 4T.

Figure 3.3: The S_{21} response of the device with varying power in VNA. The clear drop in amplitude in the response is observed which is the signature of non linear damping. The measurement was done at 110mK and applied magnetic field was 4T

It must be noted that the total attenuation of the line including the cryogenic stages and external to the cryostat was around (-101 dBm) when the applied VNA power was 0 dBm. The maximum power applied was around -80 dBm. The maximum applied in our whole experiment setup was around -84 dBm which corresponds to around few picowatts of power. An amplification of approximately 67 dB was used to read the signals.

When one increases the power one expects to see a frequency pulling (an increase in frequency meaning a tension in the beam and a decrease meaning a compressive strain). With our data we see an increase in frequency as well as a drop in S_{21} amplitude 3.3. The drop could be inferred as due to a non-linear damping. A simple Duffing system is expected to show a frequency pulling and nearly same normalized amplitude [Lulla et al., 2012]

The effect of the non-linear damping also widens the response curve simultaneously. This decrease in the amplitude with variation in power is the classical signature

of non-linear damping present in the system [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008]. The next section discusses this data in detail. We also show simulations that behave similarly.

3.3 Theory of non linear dissipation

In most cases damping is described by the linear damping force in a damped driven resonator as shown in equation (3.1). The damping term is proportional to the velocity of the resonator ($f_l \propto \gamma v$). This damping term signifies the rate at which energy escapes the particular resonator mode. The easiest way to add nonlinearity is given by the Duffing equation, which includes the higher order terms in x

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \gamma \frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_0^2 x + \frac{\alpha}{m} x^3 = \frac{F}{m} \cos(\omega t) \quad (3.1)$$

Here α is the nonlinear Duffing coefficient, γ is the linear damping term, and F is the driving force at the frequency ω . Positive α makes the structure stiffer, resulting in the right pulling of the beam, while negative α makes the beam softer, resulting in the beam's negative pull. After a certain threshold of the driving force, the resonator displacement behaves in a bizarre fashion where the resonator's displacement depends on the history of the resonator. By changing the sweep direction, you can see the hysteresis in the displacement of the resonator [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008]. This itself has led to the study of exciting work like switching between stable states [Guerra et al., 2008] and control of nonlinearity in these devices [Karabalin et al., 2009]. Normally the non linear spring constant α is very small and it only becomes significant at very large driving power *i.e.* at large amplitudes [Baierlein, 1983, Pippard, 2007, Lakshmanan and Rajaseekar, 2012b].

There are two main reasons for the system's nonlinearity, the first being the external potentials, which are generally nonlinear, the other being the geometrical effects. Here we are not considering the potential effect as the device is magneto-motive driven. Geometrical non-linearities occur when the amplitude of vibrations is less than the thickness of the beam. Normally the displacements are less than 10 nm, and thickness is generally of the order of 100nm or more than that [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008].

We can also include the additional term like $x^2\dot{x}$, and x^3 ; all these terms give rise to nonlinear dissipation as they are made up of velocity and position. In this work, we have used $x^2\dot{x}$ for the nonlinear dissipation. The proportional coefficient with $x^2\dot{x}$ is called the nonlinear dissipation coefficient; the resulting equation is called Vander-Pol duffing equation (3.2).

$$m \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + m\gamma \frac{dx}{dt} + \omega_0^2 x + \frac{\alpha}{m} x^3 + \eta x^2 \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{F}{m} \cos(\omega t) \quad (3.2)$$

Here nonlinear damping coefficient (η) decreases the amplitude of the beam with increasing nonlinear damping; the above equation can be solved in the limit of the weak damping and small oscillation using secular perturbation theory, assuming that amplitude is very small of the resonance.

3.3.1 Solution using Secular perturbation theory

We solve the eqn. (3.2) using **secular perturbation theory**, which is closely followed as given in the reference [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008]. In order to solve the (3.2), we have to rescale all the parameters to make it computationally simpler and they can be derived later just by simple substituting. So substituting $t = \omega_0 \tilde{t}$, (2) $x = \tilde{x} \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{\alpha}}{\omega_0^2}}$ and (3) divide the whole equation by $\omega_0^3 \sqrt{\frac{m^3}{\alpha}}$. This will yield us a scaled duffing equation of the form.

$$\ddot{x} + Q^{-1}\dot{x} + x + x^3 + \eta x^2\dot{x} = F \cos(\omega t) \quad (3.3)$$

We solve the (3.3) in the weak linear damping $Q^{-1} \ll 1$. We also define a small expansion parameter $Q^{-1} = \epsilon$. In most of the cases in practical life $Q = 100$, it is easier to satisfy this condition especially at very low temperatures. In case of weak oscillation, limit displacement is equal to \mathbf{FQ} . We choose $x = \sqrt{\epsilon}$.

$$F = f \epsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} \omega = 1 + \Omega \epsilon \quad (3.4)$$

substituting the above values in equation(3.3) we will get

$$\ddot{x} + \epsilon \dot{x} + x + x^3 + \eta x^2 \dot{x} = f \cos(1 + \Omega \epsilon)t \quad (3.5)$$

We try solution of the form

$$x(t) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon}}{2} (A(T)e^{it} + c.c.) + \epsilon^{\frac{3}{2}} x_1(t) + \dots \quad (3.6)$$

The lowest order contribution to this solution is based on the solution to the linear equation of motion of a simple harmonic oscillator (SHO) $\ddot{x} + x = 0$, where $T = \epsilon t$ is a slow time variable, allowing the complex amplitude $A(T)$ to vary slow in time. Using the relation

$$\dot{A} = \frac{dA}{dt} = \epsilon \frac{dA}{dT} = \epsilon A' \quad (3.7)$$

now calculating the time derivative of the trial solution

$$\dot{x}(t) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon}}{2}([\epsilon A' + iA]e^{it} + c.c.) + \epsilon^{\frac{3}{2}}\dot{x}_1(t) + \dots \quad (3.8)$$

$$\ddot{x}(t) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon}}{2}([\epsilon^2 A'' + 2iA\epsilon - A]e^{it} + c.c.) + \epsilon^{\frac{3}{2}}\ddot{x}_1(t) + \dots \quad (3.9)$$

by picking all the terms of the order of $\epsilon^{\frac{3}{2}}$ we get the following equation for the first perturbative correction

$$x_1\ddot{(t)} + \dot{x}_1(t) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon}}{2}([-iA' - i\frac{A}{2} - \frac{3+i\eta}{8}A|A^2| + \frac{f}{2}e^{i\Omega t}]e^{it}) - \frac{1+i\eta}{8}A^3 \quad (3.10)$$

The collection of the term e^{it} on the right hand side of the above equation is called **secular term** and they act like a force, driving the **SHO** exactly at its resonance frequency. The sum of all these terms must vanish, other perturbative correction to $x_1(t)$ will diverge. This will give us

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{A}{2} + \frac{i3}{8}A|A^2| - \frac{\eta}{8}A|A^2| - i\frac{f}{2}e^{i\Omega t} \quad (3.11)$$

We will be using this equation to study the duffing resonator. We assume a steady state solution of the form

$$A(T) = ae^{i\Omega T} = |a|e^{i\Omega T} e^{i\phi} \quad (3.12)$$

By substituting equation(3.12) in equation(3.11),we will get

$$[(\frac{3}{4}|a^2| - 2\Omega) + i(1 + \frac{\eta}{4}|a^2|)]a = f \quad (3.13)$$

The magnitude and the phase of the response is given by

$$|a^2| = \frac{f^2}{(2\Omega - \frac{3}{4}|a^2|)^2 + (\frac{x}{y})^2} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\tan\phi = \frac{1 + \frac{\eta}{4}|a^2|}{\frac{3}{4}|a^2| - 2\Omega} \quad (3.15)$$

By reintroducing the original physical scales we will get solution to the master equation. Notice that I omitting the tilde here to make my life easy.

$$x_0^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{F}{2m\omega_0^2}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{\omega-\omega_0}{\omega_0} - \frac{3}{8}\frac{\alpha}{m\omega_0^2}x_0^2\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}Q^{-1} + \frac{1}{8}\frac{\eta}{m\omega_0}x_0^2\right)} \quad (3.16)$$

To recapitulate the terms in this equation, ω_0 is the linear resonant frequency, ω is the driving frequency, x_0 the amplitude of vibration, m mass of resonant system, F force term, α the Duffing term or cubic elastic constant and η the non-linear damping term. The frequency pulling is given by the first term in the denominator of the above equation going to zero. One can see it depends only on the amplitude and the cubic elastic constant. The frequency can be written as

3.3.2 Simulation

The algebraic solution to the equation (3.16) does not provide the dynamic information about the system *e.g.* hysteresis in the system. The dynamic response is studied by performing numerical integration of the equation (3.1). The second order differential was simplified and written as the set of two linear differential equations and which was solved with the help of the python's SciPy library [Virtanen et al., 2020].

Figure 3.4A shows the classic duffing equation in which the amplitude remains the same, irrespective of the driving force. Figure 3.4B shows the response of the oscillator for the finite ratio of η/α , which shows that the driving force to get the bifurcation increase with the increasing value of η . The role of the η is limit the amplitude to explore the bifurcation state. Figure 3.4C shows the response of the oscillator for $\eta/\alpha = 2$; we do not see any bifurcation curve at the highest applied driving force. It is very clear that there is a window of force where the amplitude decreases very sharply without hysteresis, and hysteresis becomes apparent after applying the specific amount of force. The hysteresis can be avoided if one is in the very nonlinear damping limit. One should not see the bifurcation if ratio of $\eta/\alpha \geq 3^{1/2}$ [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008], which we do not see bifurcation for the case $\eta/\alpha = 2$.

There is a fascinating point about the above simulation because we see the sudden drop in the resonator's response without bifurcation. This is interesting from the point of view that our data shows this sudden drop without bifurcation. Random noise can also force the oscillator to choose one of the bifurcation states, making the analysis harder. When a system is well beyond the secular approximation the Duffing regime is expected to give unsteady solutions that can show sharp jumps with drop of amplitude also.

The reason being one does not know that you are in the lower branch or the upper branch of bifurcative states [Erbe et al., 2000, Badzey and Mohanty, 2005, Maillet et al., 2018]. We will be discussing this in detail in the results and discussion section.

Figure 3.4: Simulated response of the device with varying forces with varying ratio of η/α (A) $\eta/\alpha = 0$, (B) $\eta/\alpha = 0.5$, (C) $\eta/\alpha = 2.0$, while the arrow in each curve indicate the force at which bifurcation appears

In addition, this chapter deals with the calculation of the nonlinear spring constant α and non linear dissipation η with varying temperatures. In the later part of the chapter, we will be discussing the variation of both α and η for both hydrogenated and non -hydrogenated samples.

3.4 Results

This section is divided into two parts. In the first part, we will be discussing the hydrogenated sample, and in the other part, we will be discussing the data related to the non-hydrogenated sample.

3.4.1 Hydrogenated sample

The typical response of the hydrogenated beam is depicted in the figure 3.5(i-iii) in the temperature range from 110 mK to 1K. The beams clearly show the positive frequency pulling at the onset of nonlinearity. This shows the presence of tensile stress in the beam. Although we do not know the exact state of the beam, we see the beam's buckling after warming to room temperature. The resonance frequency of the metallic beams tends to be on the higher side due to the difference in the thermal contraction of the substrate and metal.

The difference in thermal contraction leads to tensile stress and enhances the resonance frequency, and it is well-known phenomena in the metallic beams [Hoehne et al., 2010, Venkatesan et al., 2010, Rebari et al., 2017, Li et al., 2008]. The expected resonance frequency for Pd beams of our dimension should be around ≈ 13 MHz, but it turns out to be ≈ 21 MHz due to tensile stress in the beam upon cooling. As we have in our simulation figure 3.4 that in the presence of η , the amplitude of the device decreases, which is exactly what we have seen in the figure 3.5. By looking at the figure 3.5 more closely, we found two more effects which needs special attention

Enhancement in Normalized response

We see a slight increase in the response of the resonator with driving power at a lower temperature (from 110mK to 800mK), while this effect is not visible at ≈ 1 K. The enhancement of the amplitude can be seen just after crossing the linear regime at the onset of non-linearity. The effective Q-factor is comparable to linear as the non-linearity also broadens the peak. In the metallic system the the phenomenon is a bit complicated than insulators as it involves the electron-TLS interactions. In metallic glasses the critical strain field required to saturate the TLS is enhanced, this is because of the relaxation time in metals are much smaller. The enhancement of the quality factor with the Two-Level System (TLS) saturation has been observed at higher driving powers [Phillips, 1987, Brehm et al., 2017]. There are two competing phenomena occurring at

Figure 3.5: Normalized response of the double clamped structure at (i)110 mK,(ii)400mK and (iii)1K.Clear drop in the magnitude of maximum amplitude can be seen.

this point, the first one being the enhancement in the Q factor due to TLS saturation and the other being broadening due to the nonlinear damping. The enhancement of the Q factor has been observed in the quartz crystal and SAW device in the linear response regime [Manenti et al., 2016, Goryachev et al., 2012].

The two-level system interacting with an external field (can be strain field, electromagnetic field *etc.* depending on the system and devices studied) may give rise to exciting features due to the broad distribution of energies and relaxation times of TLS's and the strong TLS-phonon coupling. This interaction between TLS's can be discussed in the two regimes.

- When the applied external field is small and ignoring phase coherence of the two levels and can be solved using perturbation theory on the same footing as the atom's interaction with electromagnetic waves in a cavity.

The attenuation coefficient from the interaction of TLS's and weak field can be written as [Phillips, 1987]:

$$\alpha = C \frac{\pi p_0^2 \omega}{3c\epsilon} \tanh(\hbar\omega/2k_B T) \quad (3.17)$$

where p_0 is the dipole moment, c is the speed of light, ϵ is the dielectric constant, ω is the applied angular frequency, T is the temperature and C is the density of TLS's.

- When the applied field is large: Then the phase coherence of the two levels becomes extremely critical and in that case perturbation theory cannot be used, in that case attenuation is given as [Phillips, 1987]:

$$\alpha = C \frac{\pi p_0^2 \omega}{3c\epsilon} \frac{\tanh(\hbar\omega/2k_B T)}{(1 + P/P_c)^{1/2}} \quad (3.18)$$

where P is the applied power which is proportional to the strain field.

One can write the transmission coefficient from the above absorption coefficient as:

$$t = 1 - \alpha \quad (3.19)$$

If we take into all the constants and write down only the variables then eqn.(3.18) can be simplified and one can write the transmission coefficient simply as:

$$t = 1 - \frac{1}{(1 + P/P_c)^{1/2}} \quad (3.20)$$

Figure 3.6: The simulated transmission as a function of applied power.

If one tries to plot eqn(3.20), then one get the data as shown in figure3.6. It is clear from figure 3.6 that transmission increases initially, and then it saturates at very high powers. The data taken in our case is transmission measurement, so one can predict that initially, there is the excitation of TLS, which leads to the enhancement. When all the TLS is excited, then there is saturation. In our case, when TLS's have been saturated, then it leads to non-linear damping. for reproducibility we could see the enhancement in one more sample, the sample data for that is given in the figure3.7

Calculation of normalized response to the Beam displacement in linear response regime

Next, we are interested in some quantities like amplitude, force, which is derived indirectly from the vector network analyzer(VNA) normalized data. It turns out that if you know your attenuation accurately, one can calculate these quantities. These quantities are important in order to calculate the value of spring constant (k), nonlinear spring constant (α) and nonlinear dissipation (η). Let us discuss this in detail.

VNA measures the relative quantities to convert it to the absolute quantity; we first change the reference power from VNA (which is in Watt) to V_{rms} and multiply it to the maximum linear magnitude of the VNA. In the transmission measurement, S_{21} linear magnitude is converted to power by multiply by linear magnitude itself *i.e.* by squaring the signal. The resulting power has been used for the calculation. The linewidth (also called full width at half maxima) has been used for the calculation of nonlinear damping η .

Figure 3.7: The enhancement in the Q factor as seen in other Pd sample

The resulting signal after squaring the amplitude is converted to the V_{rms} using $V_{rms} = \sqrt{PZ}$ with $Z \sim 50 \Omega$. To calculate the displacement of the beam from the equilibrium position, we have used the following relation from [Kozinsky, 2007]

$$z_{max} = \frac{V_{max}}{Ll|\mathbf{B}|w_0\xi} \quad (3.21)$$

Where V_{max} was calculated as mentioned above by just taking the peak value of the, B is the applied magnetic field, L is the length of the beam, w_0 is the resonance frequency, and ξ is the geometric constant depends on the mode shape, for the fundamental mode and in the case of the doubly clamped beam, the value of $\xi = 0.81$.

The driving force in our magneto motive measurement was calculated using the formulae.

$$F = B \times I \times L \quad (3.22)$$

Where B is the applied magnetic field, I is the current through the Beam, and L is the length of the beam. Please note that this is calculated by taking into account the total attenuation *i.e.*, then total applied power was converted to the V_{rms} . I_{rms} was calculated by dividing the V_{rms} by 50Ω .

In our setup, we have used the amplifier Narda Miteq AU-1291 for the enhancement of signal, which has a power gain of 67dB under the bias condition of 12V.

Figure 3.8: Calculated beam's displacement vs frequency of the double clamped structure at (i) 100mK, (ii) 400mK and (iii) 1K. The right axis of 1K data shows the induced voltage in the beams which is measured by the VNA

The actual 67dB can be smaller due to the line attenuation for the cupernickel coaxial cable and cold attenuator itself, which are placed at the different stages of the amplifier. We plotted the force versus displacement to calibrate for the real power gain, calculated as mentioned above. The intercept calculated from the plot has a magnitude one order smaller than the minimum displacement. The correction of 1 dB to the preamplifier gain was needed to obtain the zero intercept. The above estimate for the real amplifier gain might be offset by 2-3 dB because it is very hard to know the exact attenuation when the sample is cold. Although there may be a small error, all the estimates must be consistent within small errors. The above-mentioned calibration was used to derive parameters in the nonlinear regime. The above calibration was used to convert normalized response to displacement, and then one can convert the figure 3.5 data to the displacement and voltages, respectively which has been shown in the figure 3.8.

Calculation of spring constant

We have plotted the force versus displacement for the hydrogenated sample, shown in the figure 3.9. The value of the spring constant from the slope turns out to be 129 N/m. This value of spring constant is very similar to the other systems studied in the past [Zolfagharkhani et al., 2005] which tell us the estimation of the goodness of the calibration.

Figure 3.9: Force versus displacement for hydrogenated sample. The applied power was kept small to keep the sample in the linear regime. The sample was actuated and detected magnetomotivally. The applied magnetic field was 4T and sample temperature was around 110mK

3.4.2 Estimation of α

The solution of the eq.3.2 in the limit of the weak damping and small oscillation using **secular perturbation theory** [Lifshitz and Cross, 2008] can be written as:

$$x_0^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{F}{2m\omega_0^2}\right)^2}{\left(\frac{\omega-\omega_0}{\omega_0} - \frac{3}{8}\frac{\alpha}{m\omega_0^2}x_0^2\right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{2}Q^{-1} + \frac{1}{8}\frac{\eta}{m\omega_0}x_0^2\right)} \quad (3.23)$$

Now the amplitude of equation (3.23) will be maximum if we equate the first part of the denominator of equation (1.3) to zero and rearranging it, one will arrive at the eqn. 3.24.

$$\omega_{max} = \omega_0 + \frac{3}{8}\frac{\alpha}{m\omega_0}(x_{0max}^2) \quad (3.24)$$

To make the picture clear, we show a typical data set as in figure 3.10, here peaks are marked f1 (which is our f0), f2, f3, f4, f5. The difference between all these f_{max} from f0 is calculated and plotted against x_0^2 and the slope of which will give us α according to (2.11c).

Figure 3.10: Frequency shift of the NEMS device with various driving powers which is used for calculating the α

In the figure 3.11 we have shown the α for all the temperatures for the hydrogenated sample. From the fit to z^2 to the above figure we calculated that the value of α varies from $\approx 0.92 - 1.9 \times 10^{17} \text{ kgm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-2}$. The non monotonic nature of α in temperature, showing it is of geometric origin.

Figure 3.11: Parabolic fit to the resonance frequency versus displacement at various temperatures in order to get α . These fits also show that the system is well described by a secular perturbation approximation.

The parabolic fits also ensure that the system is still reasonably within the limits of secular perturbation approximation.

Figure 3.12: Forward and Backward sweep at maximum applied power to check for the hysteresis, although there is sudden drop in amplitude has been observed but there is no visible hysteresis has been seen.

Absence of hysteresis and Line shape in Non-linear regime

One critical observation was that we did not see hysteresis while sweeping the frequency in the forward and backward direction, which is clearly shown in the below figure. The other systems are known to show large hysteresis while sweeping the device in forward, and backward directions [Maillet et al., 2018]. Any hysteresis is of the order of step-size which is 18 to 20 Hz for different sweeps.

It is very important to understand the absence of hysteresis in the data as our calculation is based on the maximum amplitude of the response. The whole aim of this section is to understand the absence of hysteresis and how it is justified that even when the amplitude decrease suddenly, there is still a small range of force for which maximum amplitude can be reckoned quantitatively.

Any classic duffing oscillator in the bifurcation regime has an upper branch (which we might call +) and a lower branch (which we might call -). We also know that critical force (which directly translates to the critical amplitude) is needed to achieve the bifurcation, as shown in the figure 3.4. Bifurcation in the duffing system will happen when [Maillet et al., 2018]

$Z \geq \frac{2Z_s}{\sqrt{3}}$ with $Z_s = \frac{1}{3^{1/4}} \sqrt{\frac{\delta f}{\alpha}}$ where δf is the line width.

$$f_+ = f_0 + \alpha Z_+^2 + \sqrt{(\alpha Z_+^2)^2 - \frac{\delta f^2}{4}}$$

and for the lower

$$f_- = f_0 + \alpha Z_-^2 - \sqrt{(\alpha Z_-^2)^2 - \frac{\delta f^2}{4}}$$

for $Z_- \leq Z_c$ and a second case of $Z_- > Z_s$ the frequency shift is

$$f_- = f_0 + \alpha Z_-^2 + \sqrt{(\alpha Z_-^2)^2 + \frac{\delta f^2}{4}}$$

As it can be seen clearly that quadratic frequency dependence of frequency pulling is not possible when one reaches the bifurcation regime. The upper branch increases monotonically, and the lower branch shows a decrease in frequency peak and then starts increasing after achieving the critical amplitude. Indeed we do not see any this kind of crossover behaviour in our data, and also, our data shows the quadratic frequency pulling as shown in the figure 3.10. The minimum step size in sweeping the frequency is 18 Hz in the sample's with H_2 ; if there is any hysteresis present in the system, it must be less than 18 Hz.

It can be argued that random noise can force the system to choose one of the branches of the bifurcation, *e.g* it can be due to the drastic sweep rate. This normally increases the noise. In our case, all the data was collected with an IF (Intermediate Frequency) bandwidth of 1Hz; this reduces the overall noise. The very fact that our data shows the quadratic dependence on the frequency pulling shows that we are well within the secular perturbation limit.

3.4.3 Analogue of Backbone analysis for estimating η

The frequency shift follows a parabolic curve with respect to position. This is sometimes called back-bone curve, as one notices when all the responses are plotted together the points joining the peak looks like curved like a spine. The solution for peak amplitude can be solved

We have solved the (1.3) algebraically using Mathematica and we got 6 possible solution which are given below:

$$\left\{ Z \rightarrow \frac{2 \cdot 2^{2/3} k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega^4} \right)^{1/3}} - \frac{2^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega^4} \right)^{1/3}}{3^{2/3} Q \eta \omega} \right\}$$

$$\left\{ Z \rightarrow - \frac{2 \cdot 2^{2/3} k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega^4} \right)^{1/3}} \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left. \frac{2^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}}{3^{2/3}Q\eta\omega_0} \right\} \\
& \left\{ Z \rightarrow \frac{2^{2/3}(1+i\sqrt{3})k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}} \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{(1-i\sqrt{3}) \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3}Q\eta\omega_0} \right\} \\
& \left\{ Z \rightarrow - \frac{2^{2/3}(1+i\sqrt{3})k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{(1-i\sqrt{3}) \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3}Q\eta\omega_0} \right\} \\
& \left\{ Z \rightarrow \frac{2^{2/3}(1-i\sqrt{3})k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}} \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3}) \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3}Q\eta\omega_0} \right\} \\
& \left\{ Z \rightarrow - \frac{2^{2/3}(1-i\sqrt{3})k}{3^{1/3} \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{(1+i\sqrt{3}) \left(-9FQ^3\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3} \sqrt{16k^3Q^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2Q^6\eta^4\omega_0^4} \right)^{1/3}}{6^{2/3}Q\eta\omega_0} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

The imaginary roots, and the solution that gives a negative amplitude for a given η , drive force, and Q are discarded. The physically plausible solution is given below.

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{max} = & \frac{\sqrt[3]{\frac{32}{3}k_0Q^{-1}}}{\left((-9F\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3}\sqrt{(16Q^{-3}k_0^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2\eta^4\omega_0^4)}) \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}} \\
& - \frac{\sqrt[3]{\frac{2}{9}} \left((-9F\eta^2\omega_0^2 + \sqrt{3}\sqrt{(16Q^{-3}k_0^3\eta^3\omega_0^3 + 27F^2\eta^4\omega_0^4)}) \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}}{\eta\omega_0}
\end{aligned} \tag{3.25}$$

Since we know the maximum displacement and driving force experimentally, by fitting experimental data to the eqn. 3.25, one can get the η at various temperatures

Calculation of η

For the calculation of η , we have followed two methods, which we will be discussing one by one.

Figure 3.13: Backbone fitting for all temperatures to get the values of η for the hydrogenated sample. The sample was actuated and detect with magnetomotive method and applied magnetic field was 4T.

- **Backbone method**

In the figure 3.13 we have plotted the displacement with force for different temperatures. The red line is fitted to the above equation (3.25).

In the figure 3.14, we have plotted the calculated value of eta with temperature and red line linear fit to the plot. It turns out that slope of η with temperature for this method turns out to be $-1.70 \times 10^8 \text{kgm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}/\text{K}$ and the intercept is $2.2 \times 10^8 \text{kgm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$

3.4.4 Non Hydrogenated sample

This section deals with the sample measured in the vacuum *i.e.* without any presence of H_2 atmosphere. It must be noted that samples in H_2 environment became softer and it was easier to drive them non linear.

Calculation of spring constant

We have plotted the force versus displacement for the non-hydrogenated sample, which is shown in the figure 3.15. The value of the spring constant from the slope turns out to be 197.5 N/m. This value of spring constant is very similar to the other systems studied in the past [Zolfagharkhani et al., 2005]

Figure 3.14: Temperature dependence of η with temperature for the hydrogenated sample. The sample response was actuated and detected with magnetomotive method. The applied magnetic field was 4T.

Figure 3.15: Force versus displacement to get spring constant for the non hydrogenated sample. The applied power was kept small to make sure that sample is in the linear regime. The applied magnetic field was 4T and the sample was kept at around 160mK.

Figure 3.16: Frequency shift versus line width to get η and inset shows the frequency shift versus z^2 to get α . The applied magnetic field was 4T and temperature of the sample was around 160mK.

Calculation of α and η

The sample cooled without H_2 showed a higher linear spring constant and weaker nonlinear damping. A fit of line width versus frequency shift yields a value of $\eta - 2.148 \times 10^7 \text{kgm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, while the inset shows the frequency shift with amplitude which gives us $\alpha - 9.5 \times 10^{15}$. The Duffing constant for a beam cooled in vacuum is at least an order of magnitude smaller than the sample cooled in H_2 .

The figure below shows the backbone method for calculating the value of η , and it does not depend inherently on the *alpha*. The value of η by this method is $1.16 \times 10^7 \text{kgm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$.

3.5 Discussion

The nonlinear effect has been observed in carbon nanotube (CNT) and the graphene resonators under tensile strain [Eichler et al., 2011], and they claimed that the absence of hysteresis is due to nonlinear damping. No particular mechanism is discovered yet, but the coupling of geometrical nonlinearity with clamping losses (phonon tunneling [Wilson-Rae, 2008]) may contribute to this effect. Other sources of nonlinear damping may be phonon-phonon interaction. It could also stem from the large amplitude of the motion as mentioned earlier, but a theoretical analysis done till now is not sufficient. On the other hand, a thorough study has to be done on the experimental side, including the study of

Figure 3.17: Backbone fitting to get η for non hydrogenated sample. This measurement was done at 4T and sample temperature was around 160mK.

the resonators with different clamping configurations and different geometry.

3.5.1 Non-linear Akhizier damping

A recent theory [Atalaya et al., 2016] proposed several mechanisms involving flexural modes, exciting thermal two-phonon scattering processes within a NEMS or MEMS device, causing nonlinear damping in various scenarios.

Nonlinear damping due to the various phenomenon is inspired from their linear counterparts, e.g., nonlinear damping due to the nonlinear thermoelastic damping is supposed to increase the η with temperature.

A non linear Akhizer mechnism [Atalaya et al., 2016] might be a plausible origin of non linear damping which involves the phonon coupling to strain fields much faster than the thermal relaxatine time of the system, because of this different phonon modes attain different temperature. As a result there is heat flow between different mode, which in turn leads to entropy production and damping [Kunal and Aluru, 2011]. The non linear damping due to Akizier mechanism has been shown in the equation given below:

$$\Gamma_{Akh}^{nl} = \frac{2\omega_0}{\hbar} C_v T \frac{\tau_r}{1 + 4\omega_0^2 \tau_r^2} \times \int dr \left[|\nu_{\alpha(r,k)}|^2 - |\nu_{\alpha(r,k)}|^2 \right] \quad (3.26)$$

where $\nu_{\alpha(r,k)} = V_{\alpha} / \hbar \omega_{k\alpha}$ which is related to the Grüneisen parameter.

Condition to observe non-linear Akhizier damping

The condition to observe Akhizier damping

- $\omega_0 \gg \frac{v_s l_{phonon}}{L^2}$

where speed of sound $v_s = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\rho}} \sim 3100 \text{ m/s}$ with Young's modulus $E \sim 120 \text{ GPa}$ of Pd, ρ is the density, l_{phonon} is the mean free path of phonons and L is the device length. Assuming $l_{phonon} \sim t$ as device thickness than estimated minimum frequency is $\frac{\omega_0}{2\pi} \gg 2 \text{ MHz}$ and we are at $\frac{\omega_0}{2\pi} \sim 20 \text{ MHz}$ so the criterion is clearly satisfied.

Measurements on *AuPd* films reports $l_{phonon} \sim 25 \text{ nm}$ for temperatures around 1K [Kanskar and Wybourne, 1994]. We also know that in case of pure metal l_{phonon} is greater than their alloy counterpart so it is practical to assume the thickness of the beam as a limiting factor.

Enhancement in the condition to observe nonlinear Akhizier damping

- Since we have seen in our data that Pd beams are becoming softer with the exposure of H_2 , which means the smaller value of young's modulus, this relaxes the criterion to observe Akhizier nonlinear damping in these systems.
- In the nonlinear Akhizier damping mechanism, an important parameter comes into play, known as Grüneisen parameter. It has been reported that there is an increase in the Grüneisen coupling for the acoustic phonon modes, from 2 for bulk *Pd* and 3 for α -hydride state, i.e., less than $Pd_{1-x}H_x$ $x < 0.6$ [Abbenseth and Wipf, 1980]. We have also proved that in these systems (Pd beam soaked in the H_2 atmosphere), there is enhanced phonon-TLS coupling [Rebari et al., 2017].

More discussion on the nonlinear Akhizier damping

In the nonlinear regime, TLs get excited beyond two levels, and we see the saturation of two levels system at higher powers [König et al., 2002]. This could correspond to the simultaneous onset of the nonlinear damping taking over as the dominant mechanism. The nonlinear Akhizier mechanism predicted by [Atalaya et al., 2016] seems like the most plausible reason. They also have predicted the decrease in nonlinear damping with increases in temperature. We have verified this decrease in nonlinear damping with an increase in temperature by three different methods.

The linear Akhizier damping, as in reference [Iyer and Candler, 2016], predicts very weak damping if we substitute our experimental values of young's modulus. The Linear Akizier damping has been shown by the equation given below:

$$Q_{Akh}^{lin} = \frac{E_{eff}}{\Gamma_a^2 C_v T} \frac{1 + \Omega^2 \tau^2}{\Omega \tau}$$

$$Q_{Akh-linear}^{-1} = \frac{\Gamma_a^2 C_v T}{E_{eff}} \frac{\Omega \tau}{1 + \Omega^2 \tau^2}$$

where $\Gamma_a^2 = \alpha^2(\langle \gamma_{i,1}^2 \rangle - \langle \gamma_{i,1} \rangle^2)$ is the mean value of Grüneisen parameter.

We have also observed that in our case sample which were soaked in H_2 atmosphere showed the enhance cubic constant by one order of magnitude (order of $\alpha \sim 0.92 - 1.9 \times 10^{17} kg m^{-2} s^{-2}$) as compared to their counterpart (samples without H_2 has an $\alpha \sim 9 \times 10^{15} kg m^{-2} s^{-2}$). From the reference [Atalaya et al., 2016], it is clear that coupling parameters for the nonlinear phonon modes are proportional to the system's cubic elastic constant. We also observed that nonlinear damping η is lower by one order of magnitude, which points towards the possibility of a nonlinear Akhizier mechanism.

Figure 3.18: (a) SEM micrograph for the grain size of palladium, (b) SEM micrograph for the grain size of gold

Prediction based on the observed nonlinear Akhizier damping

Palladium thin films have been known to form large grain $\sim 5 - 10nm$ which has been used to fabricate cryogenic resistors reliably [Nakagawa et al., 1992]. Materials like gold [Venkatesan et al., 2010], and aluminium [Huang et al., 2005] have not shown nonlinear damping, probably due to the smaller grain size, an example of which is clearly shown in the figure 3.18. Thus one can expect a reduction of nonlinear damping in alloys of palladium, e.g., AuPd. At the same time, the epitaxial or oriented films might show an increase in the enhancement of nonlinear damping.

Chapter 4

Diffusion induced dissipation phenomena due to excess H_2 over Palladium NEMS devices

In this chapter we have studied the dissipation in Palladium (Pd) NEMS device soaked with H_2 . We have observed the elastic anomaly in the device, which can be explained by the surface diffusion of H_2 atom over Palladium's surface. This elastic anomaly can be explained by the existence of a gap (Δ), separated by a localized state and an extended state in which H_2 atom can move by thermal excitation. The value of the energy gap (Δ) obtained in our system is very close to the energy gap (Δ) obtained in the He^4 , which suggests that our system may be on the verge to show quantum phase transition.

4.1 Introduction

The search for superfluidity in the H_2 is now a long-standing puzzle. The search for superfluidity other than He^4 (superfluid transition temperature is 2.1 K) and He^3 (superfluid transition temperature is 2.4 mK) are extremely difficult to observe. To understand the superfluidity, it is essential to observe the superfluidity in systems other than He^4 . The first discussion of superfluid H_2 was discussed by Ginzberg et al. [Ginzburg and Sobyenin, 1972]. They predicted the superfluid transition temperature of H_2 to be 6K. Unlike helium, the intramolecular interactions in H_2 are very strong, so the triple point temperature of H_2 is 13.8K, and since then, there has been an attempt to super-cool the H_2 . Nearly all the methods involve the confined geometry to reduce the intramolecular interaction or addition of impurities to the H_2 to lower down the Debye temperature of the solid both experimentally and theoretically [Maris et al., 1983, Gordillo and Ceperley, 1997]. Most of the efforts to realize the superfluidity in H_2 has failed [Vilches, 1992, Tell and Maris, 1983].

The Nano-electrical mechanical systems (NEMS) can be used as an excellent device to explore the basic physical phenomena. The basic physics which has been explored with NEMS device are single spin detection [Rugar et al., 2004], the realization of superposition of macroscopically distinct quantum states [Armour et al., 2002], Spin-Mechatronics phenomenon [Matsuo et al., 2017, Zolfagharkhani et al., 2008] are to name a few. NEMS devices are also excellent mass sensors [Chiu et al., 2008], which means that sensitivity to detect the frequency change is very high. NEMS devices can also have very little dissipation, which can be significantly enhanced by choosing high tensile material and smart designs. Dissipation in the NEMS device can only be limited due to the intrinsic nature of the material.

The various attempt to measure the superfluidity in He^4 and He^3 using vibrating substrates have been very successful [Bishop and Reppy, 1978, Bishop and Reppy, 1980, Makiuchi et al., 2018]. Mechanical measurements in NEMS device are very similar to the experiments performed in vibrating reed setup, except now dissipations in NEMS devices are equivalent to the attenuation of sound and frequency shift in the NEMS device is equivalent to the change in velocity [Enss and Hunklinger, 2005].

We have studied the Palladium (Pd) nanomechanical resonator's mechanical properties in the presence of H_2 . This device was heated with DC current of 500nA during the cooldown. The affinity of H_2 towards Pd is well known. H_2 sits inside the Pd interstitial sites as H^+ ions, which causes stress. This property of H_2 towards Pd was used to tune the dissipation due to two-level systems (TLS) at very low temperatures [Rebari et al., 2017]. Thus this system provides us the natural environment to look for the superfluid transition in H_2 . We soaked the Pd NEMS device with 2×10^{-2} Torr of H_2 gas, and then we measured the dissipation and frequency response of the device with temperature. We observed the anomalous diffusion of the H_2 over the Pd surface. The mere presence of the peak in the dissipation indicates the gap in the system (denoted by Δ), which can be explained by thermal activation of H_2 from localized state to extended state. This gap can be tuned by ($\Delta \propto (n - n_c)^\alpha$) coverage of the surface, and the Δ can be made zero as the surface coverage approaches critical coverage which ultimately leads to quantum phase transition (QPT) [Makiuchi et al., 2018]. The very fact that the value of the gap ($\Delta/k_B = 9$) in our system, which is very close to the ($\Delta/k_B = 13$) for He^4 and He^3 [Makiuchi et al., 2018], which suggests that our system is on the verge of quantum phase transition. Our system might provide a noble way to achieve superfluidity in H_2 .

4.2 Experimental Procedure

System under study

The system in this study is a doubly clamped nanomechanical resonator (we have referred to it as the beam from here onwards) made out of Palladium (Pd) in which we added Hydrogen (H_2), which is well known to sit inside the interstitial sites of Pd. Our nanomechanical resonator is made by e beam lithography, and beam was suspended using standard HF wet etch. The dimension of the beam is $l \times w \times t = 4.35\mu m \times 366nm \times 80nm$. The device's resonance frequency is strongly affected by the differential thermal contraction of the substrate and the metal, which means that the beam is always under tensile stress. Normally the fundamental frequency of the beam under tension T_0 is given by equation (4.1)

$$f_0 = \frac{2\pi}{l^2} \sqrt{\frac{Et^2}{36\rho} + \frac{l^2T_0}{12\pi^2\rho A}}, \quad (4.1)$$

ρ is the density of the palladium ($12093kg/m^3$), A is the cross sectional area of the beam, t is the thickness of the Pd beam, E is the young modulus of the Pd beam [Vaz et al., 2003] which is 124 GPa, T_0 is the tension in the beam which is given by $T_0 = EA[(\Delta l/l)_{Pd} - (\Delta l/l)_{Si}]$. Experimental value for the thermal contraction of Palladium is 2.37895×10^{-3} [Arblaster, 2012] and the thermal contraction of the Si is 2.0×10^{-4} [Li et al., 2008].

Since our devices were breaking during the thermal cycling, we decided to put the H_2 exchange gas at room temperature. Before adding H_2 we pumped the system to a high vacuum (10^{-6} Torr). Then 2×10^{-2} Torr of H_2 gas was introduced into the can, and then it was pumped down to 10^{-4} Torr when the mixing chamber was below 160K.

Experimental setup and measurements

The experiments were performed in a dry dilution refrigerator, which is a single vacuum can. To put the hydrogen gas, we have designed a home-made can (also known as IVC in wet systems) made out of brass containing RF feed-thru (SMA connectors), DC feed-thru (Manganin wires), and a 1/8 inch SS 316 tube to pump the can, which was connected on the top of the cryostat through KF-25 feed-thru. The input lines were attenuated by 10 dBm at every stage. In total, we put 40 dBm to thermalize the incoming input signal. The output line was attenuated by 1dB to avoid reflections, followed by a preamplifier and bias Tee, kept at room temperature. The bias Tee also acts as a shield against electrostatic discharge (ESD). The input and output cables were made of 50 Ω Cupronickel (CuNi) semi-rigid cables.

Figure 4.1: The power from the port 1 of vector network analyzer is splitted equally, which is sent to the device. The input signals are out of phase of each other because of the power splitter. The cryogenic attenuators are used to minimize reflection and heat load from the room temperature. The output signal from the bridge device is amplified before feeding it to the port 2 of the vector network analyzer. In the S_{21} measurement the power at the port 2 is normalized to the port 1. The blue line depicts the signal line for the measurement of S_{21} and the red line depicts the signal line for the measurement of S_{12} . The switch allows gives us the freedom to choose between S_{12} or S_{21} measurements, while the directional coupler is used for the comparison of power, which helps in keeping the track of phase and amplitude

The standard method of the magneto-motive technique was used to measure the response of the beam [Cleland and Roukes, 1999]. The magnetic field was applied parallel to the beam to excite the beam's motion out of the plain. The response of the system was measured with the help of the vector network analyzer (VNA). The vector network analyzer was very carefully calibrated for the correction of error (to nullify the effect of cable and connectors). By fitting Lorentzian to the transmission data obtained from VNA, one can get the system's resonance frequency and dissipation. The schematics of the measurement setup has been shown in the figure 4.1.

The Pd NEMS devices with 10^{-3} Torr of H_2 have linear response up-to -93 dBm, in the case of sample with 10^{-2} Torr of H_2 have linear response up-to -112 dBm. This means that beams have become much softer. Since we can apply very less power to the the NEMS device, it means that our signal is also very noisy. This problem can be overcome using three strategies:

- By increasing the input power from the network analyzer (VNA) synthesizer. But this will cause the system to warm up and might lead to burning the device.
- Decreasing the IF bandwidth to the smallest value, but it can lead to serious increase in the time for each sweep.
- The directional coupler which is used to compare the signal strength of input and output power, the coupled signal got attenuated by minimum of 20dB to the input signal. The better solution could be by avoiding the directional coupler, which will lead to significant enhancement in the signal.

It is clear that directional coupler in the VNA is used to compare the signal's strength as shown in the figure 4.1. By avoiding the directional coupler, one can lead to significant enhancement in the signal. This can be done by using the direct receiver access of the Rhode Schwartz ZVB14 VNA, where the ref out from the port 1 is fed to the ref in of the port 2 of the direct receiver access. The bridge output from the sample is fed to the **meas In** port of the port 2 of the direct receiver access. The input to the sample is provided through the port 1 of the network analyzer and all other ports of the direct receiver access is terminated with a 50 ohm ground. The schematic and the practical realization of performing the experiment as mentioned above has been shown in the figure 4.2.

In the VNA, switching of S_{21} to S_{12} is done with the help of directional coupler. The directional coupler is used to separate out the incoming and outgoing signals. The cost of using these directional coupler is paid by reducing the dynamic range of the VNA. The response of the device with the use of the directional coupler is shown in the figure 4.3.

In our VNA, there is option of tapping out the signal bypassing the directional coupler. This helps in the gain of dynamic reserve by 10-15 dB. It is clear from

Figure 4.2: The top figure shows the schematic for performing S_{21} measurement using direct receiver access of the vector network analyzer and the bottom figure shows the real life operation of the performing S_{21} measurement using ZVB14 Rhode and Schwartz vector network analyzer

Figure 4.3: The figure shows the response of the device without using the direct receiver access of the vector network analyzer. The left figure shows the real part of the amplitude and right figure shows the imaginary part of the amplitude. It can be observed that data is very noisy. The applied magnetic field was 6T and the stabilized temperature was 110mK. Red line is the fit to the raw data.

the figure 4.4 that without using the directional coupler our signal is clearly enhanced.

It can be observed from the figure 4.4 that phase of the device's response is not correct, that is the price paid for working without direct receiver access. The phase problem can be taken care by fitting the data carefully.

The sample temperature was measured using a generic RuO_2 , which was calibrated against a calibrated RuO_2 . The sample was heated with a 110-ohm heater, which is mounted on the mixing chamber on the dilution refrigerator. For temperature stabilization, we waited approximately 15-20 minutes for each run. Since we know that RuO_2 film has magnetic field dependence, especially at lower temperatures [Watanabe et al., 2001]. In the magnetomotive method, one applies a magnetic field to excite the beam, which means that one can be reading the wrong temperatures. After each run, we brought the magnetic field to 0T and waited around 10 minutes (temperature naturally increases due to sweeping of the magnetic field due to the eddy current) to record the correct temperature.

The data was taken during the dilution refrigerator's warming process while circulating both He^3 and He^4 .

By fitting loaded dissipation factor with B^2 which will give us α (as discussed in the chapter 2), which is clearly shown by figure 14.5. For particular beam α is $1.83043 \times 10^{-6} \pm 1.04386 \times 10^{-7}(1/T^2)$.

Similarly we get the resonance frequency of the device which also get loaded by the application of magnetic field and has quadratic B dependence (as

Figure 4.4: The figure shows the response of the device with using the direct receiver access of the vector network analyzer. The left figure shows the real part of the amplitude and right figure shows the imaginary part of the amplitude. We can be observe the improvement in the signal quality by avoiding the directional coupler, although the phase information is lost. The applied magnetic field was 6T and the stabilized temperature was 110mK. Red line is the fit to the raw data.

discussed in the chapter2),

By fitting loaded frequency shift with B^2 one can get β , which is clearly depicted in the figure 4.5b. For this particular device β is $-2.63712 \times 10^9 \pm 4.98515 \times 10^7 (Hz^2/T^2)$. This value of α and β is used to get the intrinsic quality factor and resonance frequency of the device.

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Raw-data

As mentioned in the magneto-motive measurement for the suspended beams, we have measured the resonant frequency and dissipation of the device with temperature, as shown in figure 4.6a and figure 4.6b. As the temperature increases, dissipation in the device increases. It reaches a maximum of around 1.1K, and at this temperature, we find drastic changes in slope for the resonant frequency. Usually, one expects dissipation to increase with temperature and frequency to decrease smoothly with an increase in temperature. We observed that dissipation is peaking around 1.1K. It takes a downward turn while frequency stays almost constant and then starts decreasing with an increase in temperature, and this is why we have called this as an elastic anomaly.

Around 0.86K there is a jump in resonance frequency, as shown in figure 4.6a, while dissipation shows the upward trend, although the change in the

Figure 4.5: The top figure shows the dissipation with the square of magnetic field and the bottom figure shows the square of the resonance frequency with the square of the magnetic field. From these figures one can calculate the external loading parameters

dissipation is not as drastic as the resonance frequency. Atalaya *et. al.* [Atalaya *et al.*, 2011] predicted that in the driven doubly clamped nano-mechanical resonator, there will be frequency fluctuation if the diffusion coefficient of the adsorbent is substantial. This led to the belief that an increase in the temperature leads to an increase in the slippage of the H_2 inside the Pd interstitial site, which leads to the sudden increase in the resonance frequency of the device [Krim and Widom, 1988, Highland and Krim, 2006, Dayo *et al.*, 1998], which will be discussed somewhere else.

The inset of figure 4.6a shows the frequency shift of the form $df/f_0 = C \ln(T/T_0)$ till a temperature called crossover temperature T_{co} and after that slope becomes negative. The slope of C before T_{co} is $3.59 \times 10^{-5} \pm 9.44 \times 10^{-6}$, which is very similar to the values reported in the literature [Raychaudhuri and Hunklinger, 1984]. In the inset of the figure 4.6b, we have plotted the dissipation of the device with temperature. The solid red is the power-law fit to the dissipation up to 0.4K (due to TLS). By fitting, we found a very weak power dependence of dissipation with the temperature of $\delta Q_0^{-1} \propto T^{0.18}$. Weak power-law dependence of dissipation with temperature has been shown in metallic systems due to the two-level system [Venkatesan *et al.*, 2010, Rebari *et al.*, 2017, Hoehne *et al.*, 2010, Imboden and Mohanty, 2014].

Since we recorded the dissipation and frequency shift while warming up the dilution fridge, we also recorded the dissipation and the frequency shift of the device while cooling down the dilution fridge. To our surprise, we found that the dissipation of the device has decreased. The dissipation of the device at 1.5 K has the same value as the dissipation at the 250 mK. We will not discuss this data as we do not understand the origin of this decrease in dissipation.

4.3.2 Normalized data and background subtraction

To see the apparent change in the resonance frequency and dissipation with temperature, we have defined 1.57K as our base temperature. We have chosen the highest temperature for background subtraction because, at the highest temperature, one does not expect any anomaly. The background subtraction for resonance frequency is done according to equation (4.2), and for dissipation, background subtraction is done according to equation (4.3).

$$\frac{\delta f}{f_0} = \frac{f(T) - f(T = 1.57K)}{f_0(T = 1.57K)} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\delta Q^{-1}(T) = Q^{-1}(T) - Q^{-1}(T = 1.57K) \quad (4.3)$$

Figure 4.7a shows the change in $\delta f/f_0$ with change in temperature and the figure 4.7b shows the change in δQ_0^{-1} with temperature. There is some background contribution to the dissipation data. Ideally, we expect the excess dissipation to be symmetric around some peak temperature. To see the background

Figure 4.6: Raw data of the device (a) Resonance frequency with increasing temperature, the inset in the figure shows the normalized shift in frequency with the logarithmic change in temperature. The solid red line is a linear fit to the curve, (b) Intrinsic dissipation of with increasing temperature. The solid red line is the power-law fit to the device up-to 0.6K to account for the background in dissipation.

in the dissipation, one usually sees typical power-law behavior in the dissipation due to the two-level system (TLS), which we have shown clearly in the same system here [Rebari et al., 2017]. The inset of figure 4.6a, we have plotted the resonance frequency of the device with temperature, which clearly shows the signature of TLS (which is the resonant frequency of the system decrease with an increase in temperature). This behavior is apparent in this system up-to 0.4K. Then the resonant frequency of the device behaves normally as it should (*i.e* resonance frequency of the system decrease with an increase in the temperature).

The background in the dissipation due to TLS is clearly visible in the figure 4.6b, which is shown by solid red line. We have subtracted this background from the dissipation data which is shown in figure 4.7b and the resulting data was used for fitting.

4.4 Analysis

We can explain the observed experimental data in frequency shift and dissipation by assuming anelastic relaxation in the solid. [Crowell et al., 1997] In anelastic processes, the equilibrium is achieved only after a particular time (also known as the relaxation time) after the system is disturbed from the equilibrium position, whereas it is instantaneous in ideal elasticity. One can assume that the adsorbed atom forms two energy bands separated by energy gap E , and the two energy bands forms the localized ground and extended excited states. At $T = 0K$ all the adsorbed atoms are assume to occupying the localized ground state, which means it behaves like a stiff solid. Due to thermal excitation at finite temperature, the adsorbed atoms can gain enough energy, and they can be excited from the ground state to the excited state. The thermal excitation time is given by $\tau = \tau_0 e^{E/k_B T}$ and τ_0^{-1} is the attempt frequency jump from the ground state to the excited state. The dynamic response function for the anelastic relaxation of the solid is given by [Nowick, 2012]

$$\frac{2\delta f}{f_0} = \frac{\delta Y}{Y_0} \left[1 - \frac{1}{1 + (\omega\tau_0 e^{E/k_B T})^2} \right] \quad (4.4)$$

$$\delta Q^{-1} = \frac{\delta Y}{Y_0} \left[\frac{\omega\tau_0 e^{E/k_B T}}{1 + (\omega\tau_0 e^{E/k_B T})^2} \right] \quad (4.5)$$

Where δY is the relaxed young modules and Y_0 is the young modulus of the Pd beam, k_B is the Boltzman constant, ω is the angular frequency ($\omega = 2\pi f$). Dissipation is usually the competition between relaxation time and mechanical period. One gets the maximum in dissipation when $\omega\tau = 1$, and the temperature corresponding to this maximum in dissipation is called peak temperature (T_P). When $\omega\tau \gg 1$, it means that adsorbent atoms are localized, which contributes to the elasticity of the material, and when $\omega\tau \ll 1$, it means

that adsorbent atoms are jumping in excited state and ground state frequently. As a result, it will not contribute to the elasticity of the system.

Another natural question that arises is whether $\tau(T)$ is single-valued or has some distribution. Now if $\tau(T)$ is single-valued, then the plot between $2\delta f/f_0$ and δQ_0^{-1} will be a semicircle, and a deformed semicircle will tell us that there is a distribution of relaxation times. Also if $\tau(T)$ is single-valued or distribution, then the ratio of $[2\delta f(T_{min})/f_0]/\delta Q_0^{-1}(T_P) = 2$, but in our case, it is always greater than 2. Specifically, we found that in our case, it is 4.81, which means we have a distribution of relaxation time. Now we can choose a log-normal distribution for the relaxation time, as shown in the equation (4.6). Here Δ is the median, which is the energy gap, and σ is the dimensionless parameter related to the shape of the curve.

$$F(E) = \frac{e^{-[\ln(E/\Delta)]^2/2\sigma^2}}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma E} \quad (4.6)$$

The reason for choosing log-normal distribution is that it allows the possibility of all kinds of relaxation time, unlike box-type distribution, which will give a sudden cut off in relaxation times. The dynamic response function in the complex form can be written as equation 4.7.

$$\frac{2\delta f}{f_0} + \delta Q^{-1} = \frac{\delta Y}{Y_0} \left[1 - \int_0^\infty \frac{F(E)}{1 + i\omega\tau_0 e^{E/k_B T}} dE \right] \quad (4.7)$$

Now we fitted our experimental data with equation 4.7, which is the solid red line as shown in figure 4.7. Both of the dissipation and frequency shift were fitted simultaneously with common parameters. We get the the ratio of $\Delta/k_B T_P = 8.94$ (Here in our case $T_P = 1.12$)K. It must be noted that while fitting the data in frequency shift and dissipation, we did not take into account the jump in frequency shift and corresponding data in dissipation. The relaxation time τ_0 for the above data is 0.8ps, and the parameter σ is 0.3 during the fitting.

Makiuchi et al. have done series of experiments where they prepared a thin film of H_2 , D_2 , HD , He^3 , He^4 , Ne and measured the elasticity of the material with temperature [Makiuchi et al., 2018, Makiuchi et al., 2019a, Makiuchi et al., 2019b]. Since we know that H_2 loads the surface of the Pd, which means that elastic anomaly around 1.1K can be due to the diffusion of the surface molecule [Sukhatme et al., 1996, Bloss and Wyatt, 2000]. It was also pointed by makiuchi et al. that gap vary according to the equation (4.8)

$$\Delta(n) \propto \left| 1 - \frac{n}{n_c} \right|^a \quad (4.8)$$

here Δ is the gap, n is the coverage, n_c is the critical coverage at which gap closes (*i.e.* $\Delta = 0$) and a is the power coefficient for the equation (4.8).

Figure 4.7: (a) Normalized frequency shift and fit of data using equation 4.7 (b) Intrinsic dissipation after removing the excess background and fit of the data using the equation 4.7. The fitting parameters employed during fit were $\delta Y/Y_0 = 4.7 \times 10^{-4}$, $\tau_0 = 8.0 \times 10^{-13}$ (3.5×10^{-13}) s, $\Delta/k_B = 10.01(0.61)K$ and $\sigma = 0.3$

For Makiuchi et al. the ratio of $\Delta/k_B T_P = 12$ for H_2, D_2, HD which is very close to our experimental value, which also agrees well with the experimental value of He^3 and He^4 where $\Delta/k_B T_P = 13$. The smaller discrepancy in the value of $\Delta/k_B T_P$ in our case can be due to more coverage of the surface of the Pd with H_2 as depicted by equation (4.8).

4.5 Conclusions

We found an elastic anomaly (as suggested by the peak in dissipation and slope change in the resonance frequency) in our system. This peak in the dissipation is due to the diffusion of H_2 molecules on Pd's surface. This elastic anomaly can be explained by the thermal excitation model, suggesting a gap in the system Δ . Since the gap can be tuned by the amount of H_2 molecule, it could be possible to achieve QPT (which is already on the verge of attaining superfluidity). We are only seeing a gap in Diff of H_2 but not evidence for superfluidity. Despite of having a solid film we see a diffusion. This might be due to surface adsorbed H_2 on Pd diffusing along the grain boundaries forming a nano scale network. Our system provides a natural way to realize the superfluidity in H_2 .

Chapter 5

Electronic friction across a superconducting transition probed in a mechanical device

The sliding friction measurement using quartz crystal micro-balance has been used to estimate the electronic dissipation at very low temperatures. The superconductor provides an easy route to access the electronic friction as the number of electron decreases across the transition. The sliding friction measurement has been very controversial, and reproducibility has always been the problem. We measured the transition temperature of Ta by a planar inductor method which generally behaves like a magnetometer. Here we probe the sliding friction of solid H_2 across the superconducting transition of Tantalum (Ta) using the standard 10 MHz quartz crystal.

To perform these experiments a thin layer of the Ta was deposited over the quartz crystals. The H_2 was used as a adsorbent which is suppose to slide. It must be noted that H_2 becomes solid at approximately 14K. The transition temperature of the bulk Ta is 4.48K and it can vary for the thin films. Ta was used as a superconducting layer because it has high electron-phonon coupling, which makes this phenomena more visible. A thin layer of Pd was deposited in situ, just after the deposition of Ta. The purpose of the deposition of Pd was to acts as a host material for H_2 .

We have observed the decrease in dissipation across the transition and the resonance frequency of the device increase. The friction measurement was done for the two different concentration of H_2 *i.e.* (1×10^{-3} Torr and 1×10^{-2} Torr). By increasing the concentration we could see the transition very clearly. We also observed that we could suppress the sudden decrease in the dissipation by adding 3nm of silicon after the Ta deposition so that H_2 does not directly see the Ta. We also observed the sudden decrease in dissipation by applying a small magnetic field (15G).

5.1 Introduction

Nano-tribology is the field that addresses the question of the origin of friction from the microscopic point of view. One can always ask the origin of frictional dissipation, which is created by phononic excitation or electronic excitation.

It is quite interesting to note that the solid monolayer of Krypton sliding on the Au, exhibit less friction than the liquid monolayer [Krim et al., 1991]. The answer to this question was provided by Robbins et al., when they established the friction is due to the phonon's excited in the adsorbed layer [He and Robbins, 2001].

In a nutshell, on the microscopic scale, one can describe the frictional dissipation by the electrical dissipation or phononic dissipation. The electrical dissipation can be due to the excitation of electron-hole pair or electron-electron interaction. Till now, many mechanisms of electrical dissipation has been suggested. One of the most prominent ones is where the sliding tip or sliding adsorbate can drive the charge through the adsorbent, experiences electric resistance. This, in other words, is called ohmic heating due to the creation of electron-hole pair [Persson, 2000, Novotný and Velický, 1999, Sokoloff et al., 2000].

To quantify the electrical frictional dissipation, mainly three different types of the experiments have been tried. The very recent one being using the NEMS device [Lulla et al., 2013, Suchoi and Buks, 2017]. The second one is FFM or LFM (Frictional or Lateral Force microscopy), which is the modified version of AFM (Atomic Force Microscope) [Kisiel et al., 2011, Wang et al., 2020] and the last being Quartz crystal (as they are easier to work with). Here we will be focusing on the measurement performed using a Quartz crystal. The most notable experiment to target the electrical friction dissipation was done by Dayo et al. [Dayo et al., 1998, Highland and Krim, 2006]. In their experiment, the superconducting lead electrode was deposited on the Quartz crystal, and the solid Nitrogen (N_2) was being used as the adsorbent. They measured the dissipation across the superconducting transition temperature of lead while solid Nitrogen sliding over it, and they observed a decrease in the electronic friction. Considerable amount of experimental and theoretical interest arose due to this work [Persson and Tosatti, 1998, Park and Salmeron, 2014]. Still, Renner et al. [Renner et al., 1999] could not repeat the observed decrease in dissipation as observed by Dayo *et al.* [Dayo et al., 1998], later on, this was settled by understanding that N_2 may be pinned on the surface of lead (Pb) [Krim, 1999, Renner et al., 2001].

The most fundamental thing to observe during these experiments will be the change in the dissipation during the superconducting phase transition. We know that the number of normal electrons decreases gradually during the superconducting transition temperature, resulting in a continuous decrease in the electronic excitation. Still, a sudden decrease in the dissipation has worsened that matter which is challenging to explain [Persson and Tosatti,

1998].

This chapter aims to look for the sliding dependent dissipation across the superconducting phase transition.

5.2 Theory

Using the Quartz crystal micro-balance (QCM), one can measure the sliding friction in adsorbed mono-layers [Krim and Widom, 1988, Watts et al., 1990, Rodahl et al., 1995]. In the limit where the amplitude of vibration is more than 0.4nm [Bruschi et al., 2002], one can write the viscous frictional as , $F = (m/\tau)v = -m\eta v$. Here F is the frictional force which acts as a resisting force that resists the sliding; m, τ, η, v are the mass, slip time, drag coefficient and the sliding velocity of the adsorbent. The drag coefficient η can be written as the coefficient of phononic as well as the electronics part; hence one can write $\eta = \eta_{el} + \eta_{ph}$. The drag coefficient can also be defined as the $\eta = 1/\tau$. The measurement of τ is easier, and hence one can gauge the drag coefficient from slip time measurements. The slip time can be defined as the time required by the adsorbed film so that its speed decrease to 1/e times its maximum value. The value of slip time is 0 for the locked adsorbed film, and it is ∞ for the superfluids.

The observed change in the dissipation δQ^{-1} and the observed change in the frequency shift δf can be related to each other as given by eq.(5.1)

$$\begin{aligned}\delta Q^{-1} &= 4\pi\tau\delta f, \\ \eta &= \frac{1}{\tau}.\end{aligned}\tag{5.1}$$

The phononic contribution to the friction always masks the electronic contribution to the friction. At lower temperature, the phononic contribution decreases drastically. At lower temperatures, the electronic contribution can be gauged directly. The best material to probe the contribution due to electronic friction can be a superconductor. Across the superconducting phase transition, the contribution of normal electron decreases and only cooper pairs are active.

To understand the origin of electronic friction due to the sliding adsorbed film, many theories have been put forward; here, we will be mentioning a few of them.

- The one on the earliest theory has been put forward by Persson *et. al.* [Persson, 1991], here they proposed that the electronic friction is a surface phenomenon and its origin is due to the non-specular diffusion. It means that scattering off the conduction electron adsorbed film/metal interface. This scattering causes the excitation of electron-hole pair, and energy is dissipated in the form of heat. The problem with the theory is that it

does not explain sudden disappearance in the friction because there is a gradual decrease in the normal electron across T_c .

- There is another assumption that as the resistance of the material decrease abruptly, this could be one of the origins of electronic friction. It was proposed that adsorbed molecule acts as a charged particle and it moves along the surface of the metal, an image current due to sliding of adsorbed film produces ohmic heating [Persson, 2000, Novotný and Velický, 1999, Sokoloff et al., 2000, Tomassone and Widom, 1997].
- Bruch *et al.* proposed that electronic friction is associated with whole adsorbed films rather than as individual charged particle. They also proposed that field due to the quadrupole moment of the adsorbed film can produce electronic friction of the same order as observed in some experiments [Bruch, 2000].

5.3 Experimental Procedure

System under study

The system under study was AT-cut Quartz crystal of resonant frequency around 10 MHz, coated with 60 nm of Tantalum and 3 nm of Palladium. The superconducting material chosen was Ta, as it has high electron-phonon coupling strength. The higher electron-phonon coupling improves the dynamic reserve of this experiment as the higher electron-phonon coupling across the transition gives a higher signal in the Quartz crystal microbalance experiment. We start with a bare Quartz crystal whose fundamental resonance frequency is 10 MHz. These crystals were bought from open QCM GmbH; these crystals were AT-cut, and the crystal thickness was around 165 μm [Open QCM, 2020]. First, we have deposited 2-3 nm of Nb as the seed layer, over which we have deposited the 60 nm of Ta, followed by 3 nm of Palladium by e-gun evaporation. It must be noted that during the deposition of Ta, a seed layer of 2-3 nm of Nb was deposited. This was done to prevent the formation of α phase whose transition temperature is around 1K. With the help of seed layer, b.c.c phase of Ta can be obtained whose transition temperature is around 4K [Face and Prober, 1987]. The ultimate vacuum in our e-gun evaporation chamber was around $5\text{e-}7$ Torr, and the evaporation was done in the partial pressure, $1.5\text{e-}6$ Torr. We also used the Titanium as a gettering element to remove the oxygen from the chamber; we evaporated the Titanium for around 15 minutes to get rid of the oxygen from the chamber. We also used a charcoal cloth inside the vacuum chamber to get rid of moisture from the chamber. To achieve the ultimate vacuum, we used the cold trap, which was dipped into the LN2 to achieve a better vacuum. The device's final image before and after the deposition is shown in figure 5.1. During the measurement, Quartz crystal

Figure 5.1: The left side of the figure shows the bare quartz crystal as purchased. The right side of the figure shows the quartz crystal after deposition of Ta and Pd. The golden color is the electrode deposited on the quartz crystal on both sides of it.

coated with Nb/Ta/Pd was loaded with various pressures of H_2 . The whole point of putting Palladium (Pd) was to adsorb the H_2 as we know that Pd has a massive affinity for the H_2 and it sits inside the interstitial sites of Palladium (Pd). We should also notice that H_2 becomes solid at around 13K.

Experimental setup and measurements

Various methods can be used for the detection of the resonance in the quartz crystal *e.g.*, reflection, transmission, impedance, and self-sustained oscillation. For this chapter, all the data have been taken in the transmission mode. The experimental set-up for the transmission method has been discussed in chapter 3.

The addition of H_2 in the Inner Vacuum can (IVC)

We have measured the dissipation of Quartz coated with Tantalum (Ta) and Palladium (Pd) in the Hydrogen atmosphere (H_2). The measurement was done up to 1K, and for this, we used JANIS He^3 refrigerator. It has an outer vacuum jacket (also called OVC) which sits inside the Helium bath and inner vacuum can (IVC), where the sample sits, and it is leak-tight with an Indium seal. The check for the leaks was done with the help of the Adixen TDS 182 leak detector, and the leak rate was found to be less than the 3×10^{-9} mbar l/sec. The addition of H_2 to the IVC, where the sample sits, is a little bit tricky. The reason is H_2 , itself is not very dangerous, but if released in the excess amount in the atmosphere and enough activation energy can be provided. It can react with oxygen which is a very exothermic reaction. We made sure that the area is fully ventilated before the addition of H_2 and there is no ignition

source. We also have to worry about keeping the sample clean and free from the other residual before adding the H_2 . A custom made set-up was made for the addition of H_2 inside the IVC. All the lines were first evacuated with turbopump (nEXT 400 made by EDWARDS), and pressure up to 10^{-5} Torr was achieved. The line connected to the H_2 source cylinder was passed through the LN2 trap; this was done in order to ensure the minimization of impurity. The lines were flushed with H_2 with pressure to 10^{-1} Torr, and then it was pumped to 5×10^{-3} Torr with scroll pump (nXDS 20i made by EDWARDS). This process was done two times to ensure that there is minimal impurity. After this, lines were evacuated to 10^{-6} Torr with turbo. Finally, the desired amount of H_2 was added to the IVC, and the pressure was measured with Pirani gauge, which was connected very close to the IVC (There is freedom of choosing various gases in the Pirani gauge as each gas have different thermal conductivity while adding H_2 we made sure that we have chosen He which was closest available. This was done to ensure that we are reading the correct pressures).

5.4 Results

5.4.1 Transition temperature of Tantalum

We required a setup in which we will be able to measure the dissipation and superconducting transition temperature simultaneously, as it is done here [Dayo et al., 1998]. Generally, one will go for one of the two strategies, one being the four-probe measurement (which is also known as the low-frequency method). The other is the mutual induction method. Since our device has Pd on the top of Tantalum, we might miss the superconductivity by four-probe, so we thought of an idea similar to mutual induction or put in other words, we used planar inductor.

We made a simple microstrip, and the idea was to stick the substrate with PMMA on the PCB having a microstrip. The PCB which we have used is made by Arlon [EMD, 2019]. The figure 5.2 shows the home-made microstrip PCB with SMP connectors.

We used insulating Si_3N_4 for the deposition of superconducting films. We deposited around 5 nm of Niobium as an adhesion layer before the deposition of Tantalum. 60 nm of Tantalum is deposited over Niobium by e gun evaporation. The last 5 nm of Pd was deposited, and this Pd deposition was done by thermal evaporation. We did the transmission measurements (described in chapter 3 in detail), and the input power was supplied using SMB100A. The corresponding response was measured with SR830 RF lock in amplifier. The input applied power was 15dBm at 200MHz, and we varied the temperature and response of the sample is shown in the figure 5.3. It is clear from figure 5.3 that the Tantalum's transition temperature (T_a) is around 4K.

Figure 5.2: Top part of the figure shows home made PCB having tracks in microstrip geometry with SMP connectors on the both ends. Below part of the figure shows the Ta sample on the microstrip PCB. The sample has been put upside down and it is stuck with GE varnish to avoid the shortage with copper microstrip.

Figure 5.3: Transition temperature of Ta by planar induction method.

Clearly, there is a very broad transition, but we think that it might be due to the imperfections in the measurements. We are doing more measurements on this method to establish it to find the exact transition temperature of any material.

5.4.2 Linearity check of device

All the measurement discussed here is done in the transmission method. The essential part of doing any measurement is to make sure that the device is in the linear regime. The device must be in the linear regime as it will make sure that one is not getting unexpected results due to the device's non-linearity. Figure 5.4 shows the linearity check for the device by varying the power. It is clear that as the applied power increases, dissipation starts to increase after the applied power increases above -25 dBm. Keeping this in our mind, all our measurements were done at -60dBm.

5.4.3 Quartz crystal micro-balance friction measurement with different concentration of H_2

In all the mentioned measurements below, the Quartz crystal is coated with 3 nm of Nb as the seed layer, followed by 60 nm of the Tantalum layer. This Tantalum layer is our main superconducting layer, and the Niobium was coated to obtain the bcc phase of Tantalum, for which superconducting transition temperature is around 4K. After the deposition of the Tantalum layer, a 5 nm

Figure 5.4: Linearity check of the Quartz crystal, it can be observed that the Quartz crystal becomes non linear above -25 dB of the applied power.

of palladium layer was deposited. The Palladium (Pd) layer was deposited in order to adsorb the H_2 as Pd has a massive affinity for H_2 . This will be our sample during all the measurements unless specified.

Bare quartz crystal soaked in 1×10^{-3} Torr of H_2

The dissipation of the bare Quartz crystal (with no deposition) with the variation in temperature is shown in figure 5.5(i). It is clear from the figure 5.5(i) that there is almost no change in dissipation at the transition temperature.

The resonance frequency of the bare Quartz crystal (with no deposition) with the variation in temperature is shown in figure 5.5(ii). It is clear from the figure 5.5(ii) that there is almost no change in resonant frequency at the transition temperature.

Ta coated quartz crystal soaked in 1×10^{-3} Torr of H_2

The process of adding H_2 inside the IVC has been discussed in the measurement section. Here we have omitted the redundant steps, and only critical steps are discussed. The IVC (Inner Vacuum Chamber) was pumped down 1×10^{-6} Torr; then we added 1×10^{-3} Torr of H_2 . After the addition of H_2 , the sample was cooled down to 300 mK in the JANIS He^3 refrigerator.

The dissipation of the Quartz crystal (Ta-Pd) coated with 1×10^{-3} , with the variation in temperature is shown in figure 5.6. It is clear from figure 5.6

Figure 5.5: (i) Dissipation of the bare quartz crystal with variation of temperature and (ii) Resonance frequency of the bare quartz crystal with the variation of temperature

that there is a change in dissipation at the transition temperature due to the sliding of H_2 as found by Dayo *et al.* [Dayo *et al.*, 1998]. Clearly, there is a small discrepancy in the transition temperature of Tantalum; we think it might be due to the thermalization issue. It means that there is a temperature lag between the actual temperature and the Quartz crystal temperature.

The resonance frequency of the Quartz crystal (Ta-Pd) with the variation in temperature is shown in figure 5.6(i). It is clear from the figure 5.6(i) that there is a change in resonant frequency at the transition temperature.

It is clear from figure 5.6(i,ii) that change in the $\delta Q^{-1} = 2.67 \times 10^{-7}$ and the corresponding frequency shift is given by $\delta f = 2.7\text{Hz}$. Using the eqn. (5.1) one gets characteristic slip time (τ), which is 7.9^{-9}s . The characteristic slip times gives an idea how much the film is slipping across the adsorbent. The more slipping time means lesser the dissipation. The drag coefficient η for the adsorbed film is $1.27 \times 10^8 \text{s}^{-1} \cdot (H_2)$ over the Ta is

Ta coated quartz crystal soaked in 5×10^{-2} Torr of H_2

At 77K, the IVC (Inner Vacuum Chamber) was pumped down 1.0^{-6} Torr; then we added 5.0^{-2} Torr of H_2 . After the addition of H_2 , the sample was cooled down to 300 mK in the JANIS He^3 refrigerator. We will discuss the dissipation and frequency shift of each type of sample in detail.

The dissipation of the Ta-Pd Quartz crystal with the variation in temperature is shown in figure 5.7(i). It is clear from the figure 5.7(i) that there is clear change in dissipation at the transition temperature.

Here we can clearly see from the figure 5.7(i) that the dissipation decreases in the superconducting phase of the sample. The dissipation attains a constant value after the transition temperature. Again the transition temperature according to the friction measurement is slightly lesser than the 4K. We think it is again due to the thermalization issue.

The Quartz crystal (Ta-Pd) resonance frequency with the temperature variation is shown in the figure 5.7(ii). It is clear from the figure 5.7(ii) that there is a clear increase in the resonant frequency after the transition temperature.

It is clear from the figure 5.7(ii) that there is an increase in the resonance frequency of the quartz crystal across the superconducting phase transition, which is measured by the friction measurements. It can be clearly seen that change in the $\delta Q^{-1} = 5.45 \times 10^{-7}$ and the corresponding frequency shift is given by $\delta f = 22.77\text{Hz}$. Using the eqn. (5.1) one can see the characteristic slip time (τ), which is $1.9 \times 10^{-9}\text{s}$. The drag coefficient η for the adsorbed film (H_2) over the Ta is $5.26 \times 10^8 \text{s}^{-1}$

Figure 5.6: (i) Dissipation of the Ta-Pd (1×10^{-3} Torr of H_2) coated quartz crystal with variation of temperature and (ii) Resonance frequency of the Ta-Pd (1×10^{-3} Torr of H_2) coated quartz crystal with the variation of temperature

Figure 5.7: (i) Dissipation of the Ta-Pd (5×10^{-2} Torr of H_2) coated quartz crystal with variation of temperature and (ii) Resonance frequency of the Ta-Pd (5×10^{-2} Torr of H_2) coated quartz crystal with the variation of temperature

Figure 5.8: (i) Dissipation of the quartz crystal (Ta-Si-Pd) with variation of temperature and (ii) Resonance frequency of the quartz crystal (Nb-Ta-Si-Pd) with the variation of temperature.

Effect of Si screening layer on the Quartz crystal coated with 5×10^{-2} Torr of H_2

We wanted to suppress the sliding friction by means other than the application of the magnetic field, so we coated the quartz crystal with the 3 nm of silicon (Si) so that H_2 does not see the Tantalum directly. It means that Si acts as a screening layer. It means that our quartz crystal configuration is Ta-Si-Pd (1-60-3-3 nm).

The dissipation of the Ta-Si-Pd Quartz crystal with the temperature variation is shown in figure 5.8(i). It is clear from the figure 5.8(i) that there is no sudden change in dissipation at the transition temperature. The dissipation keeps on decreases with a decrease in temperature, which is usually what one expects.

The resonance frequency of the Quartz crystal (Ta-Si-Pd) with the temperature variation is shown in figure 5.8(ii). It is clear from figure 5.8(ii) that there is

no sudden change in resonant frequency at the transition temperature. There is an increase in the resonance frequency as the temperature decreases.

The effect of adding Si layer is that it suppresses the sliding friction that is happening across the superconducting transition temperature of Ta.

5.5 Conclusions

It is observed from the experimental data that there is a decrease in sliding friction across the superconducting transition of Ta as the H_2 , slides over the Ta. The friction measurement was done for the two different concentration of H_2 *i.e.* (1×10^{-3} Torr and 1×10^{-3} Torr). By increasing the concentration we could see the transition very clearly. We could also show that we could suppress the superconductivity transition by adding 3nm of Silicon (Si) between Tantalum (Ta) and Palladium (Pd), which means that H_2 could not directly see the superconducting surface. The drag coefficient η for the adsorbed film (H_2) over the Ta is found to be $(\sim 1 - 5.26) \times 10^8 s^{-1}$.

Chapter 6

Linear dissipation studies in superconducting NEMS device

We have studied the dissipation due to the movement of vortices in the NEMS device (made out of Nb_3Ge) by the magnetomotive method. The dissipation due to the vortices has been studied mainly by the vibrating reed method. The NEMS devices provide excellent sensitivity and driving them non-linear is very easy. This way, it is easier to study both the linear and non-linear dissipation by the vortices. Here we have shown the dissipation and resonance frequency of the NEMS device, with the variation in temperature and magnetic field due to vortices motion. The observed data is in agreement with the observation done by the vibrating reed method.

6.1 Introduction

The mechanical measurement in the doubly clamped beam of the superconducting material can provide very sensitive measurement on the vortex dynamics and pinning centre. The reason is that the interaction between vortices and the pinning centres, which is normally the case in type II superconductors, leads to a considerable change in the resonance frequency and the dissipation. With the advancement of technology *e.g.* lockin amplifier, it is possible to measure very accurately and precisely the dissipation and frequency. [De Long et al., 2020, Esquinazi, 1991, Esquinazi et al., 1986]. Historically the elastic measurement on the superconductors was done to measure the pinning force [Brandt et al., 1986a, Esquinazi et al., 1986] The defects in the type II superconductors acts as the pinning center, and usually, the vortices are tied to it. If a type II superconductor is cooled below its transition temperature, one can see the drastic increase in the resonance frequency of the vibrating beam. The origin of this increase in resonance frequency has been attributed to the increase in the magnetic restoring force due to the perfect diamagnetic behaviour of the vibrating structure in the presence of strongly pinned vortices. If the vortices

are allowed to move now, the perfect diamagnetism reduces. As a consequence of that, resonance frequency decreases [Brandt et al., 1986b, Esquinazi et al., 1986], this also leads to the peak in the dissipation below the upper critical field [Brandt et al., 1986b].

It has also been observed that dissipation increases due to the increase in the strength of the magnetic field. The damping due to the magnetic field is dominated by two loss mechanisms:

- Viscous loss: The regime is active when the displacement of vortices with respect to the pinning centers are small
- Hysteric loss due to inelastic instabilities: This regime is active when the displacement of vortices with respect to the pinning center is very large [Brandt et al., 1986a].

To study the dissipation due to the movement of vortices, one should choose a material, where the pinning forces are low. Although a strong pinning force has its own advantages, it allows one to have a large critical current, which is the most important factor while making superconducting electromagnets. In the crystalline material, the pinning centers are very strong. On the other hand, their counterpart amorphous material has weak pinning centers, which makes the movement of vortices very easy and hence allows the measurement of elastic constant, which is the main requirement in these doubly clamped beam structures [Otto, 2010].

Till now, there has been a lot of studies done on the dissipation due to movement of vortices by the vibrating reed method [Esquinazi and Brandt, 1987, Drulis et al., 1991, Brandt, 1992, De Long et al., 1996], which in a great deal discusses the experimental, theoretical part related to the vortices and pinning centers. There have also been very few studies on the non-linear dynamics of the vortices motion [Zhang et al., 1996]. The NEMS devices provide us with excellent sensitivity, where the dissipation studies of vortices can provide more insights. The NEMS devices are straightforward to drive non-linear, and this encourages us to study the non-linear dynamics of vortices motion. So far, the dissipation studied on type I superconductor has been studied by the NEMS device, which provided the evidence of dissipation due to normal electron even in the superconducting regime [Lulla et al., 2013]. There is a lot of space for the dissipation studies in the type II superconductors using NEMS devices.

6.2 Experimental Procedure

System under study

The material chosen for the study of dissipation in superconductor was Nb_3Ge . The Nb_3Ge was chosen because it is a well-known type II superconductor since

one of our aims was to study the dissipation due to the flux line or vortices. It is well known that the vortices in the Nb_3Ge is not strongly pinned and can be moved easily [Otto, 2010]. It is easier to introduce the vortices in Nb_3Ge by the application of a magnetic field. The Nb_3Ge was grown by the co-sputtering of both Nb and Ge simultaneously by the combination of DC+RF sputtering.

After the growth of the film on the Si/SiO_2 substrate, the NEMS devices (also called beam) were made by using the combination of e beam lithography (EBL), the reactive ion etching (RIE) followed by the releasing the beam using wet etching (HF). The fabricated devices are basically designed as bridge devices to minimize the background, making it easier to look for the resonance of the device. The two beams have different lengths that correspond to 2.5μ and 1.5μ respectively, both of the devices have the same width, which corresponds to around $\sim 275 - 300\text{nm}$, and the thickness of the deposited film was around 60nm .

Figure 6.1 (a-d) shows the fabricated device by the combination of e beam lithography and RIE. The final image of the beam is shown in the figure 6.1.

Experimental setup and measurements

One can also calculate the fundamental mode of the device by finite element method, for which some commercial software is available, and one such software is COMSOL [Littmarck, 2020]. Using the material properties and device dimensions mentioned above, one can calculate the fundamental and other modes of the doubly clamped beams.

Please note that the finite element simulation was done without considering relative thermal contraction of Nb_3Ge (as reliable data is not available) and Si at the cryogenic temperature. The predicted fundamental resonance frequency of the device by finite element method is ~ 55.4 MHz without tension.

It must be noted that it is tough to determine the value of the young's modulus of Nb_3Ge , which varies depending upon the ratio of Nb and Ge. This gives an uncertainty in the measurement of the resonance frequency. It is also important to note that the thermal contraction of Nb_3Ge is very not well known, which is another source of uncertainty in predicting the fundamental resonance frequency Nb_3Ge .

The transition temperature of the device was measured by using a high-frequency lockin amplifier (SRS 844) [System, 1980], by employing the transmission method. A detailed discussion on the transmission method using a high-frequency lockin amplifier is given in **chapter 3**. Our triton 200 dilution refrigerator is equipped with a vector magnet, in which we can apply 9T in the z-direction and 1T in the x-direction.

The resonance frequency of the device was measure by using the frequency response analyzer module of the Moku [Shaddock, 2021] in the presence of the magnetic field (also known as magnetomotive method [Cleland and Roukes, 1999]), which is a transmission measurement very similar to a high-frequency

Figure 6.1: The SEM image of the device, (a) shows the full image of the device, which includes both beam and the pads. (b) zoomed view (rectangular box) of the (a), which shows the two independent beams. (c) zoomed view (rectangular box) of the (b), which shows the single beam with the pad as well as a clear cutout area. (c) shows the single beam with pads

Figure 6.2: Transmission measurement for the estimation of critical temperature with magnetic field. The measurement was done with high frequency lock in amplifier (SRS 844). The magnetic field was applied parallel to the plain of the beam and the driving frequency was 200 MHz at the 0.5 Vrms stimulus

lockin amplifier. The detail about the measurement setup is given in the **chapter 3**.

6.3 Results and Discussions

6.3.1 Transmission measurement to find critical temperature and critical magnetic field

The transition temperature of the Nb_3Ge was measured by the high-frequency transmission method. One can argue the best way to determine the superconductivity is by doing DC measurement. Still, it turns out that doing both high frequency and low-frequency measurement is very tricky. Nevertheless, one can also determine the critical temperature and critical magnetic field by performing high-frequency transmission measurement [Dobrovolskiy et al., 2015].

Response of the device for various temperature and magnetic field

We measured the transmission of the device at 200 MHz using SR844 lock in amplifier. It must be noted that the applied magnetic field is parallel to the plane of the beam.

Figure 6.2 shows the transmission of the device with the varying temperature at fixed magnetic field. The measurement at 200 MHz shows the transition temperature of around 212 mK at 6T.

6.3.2 Dissipation and resonance frequency measurement with magnetic field and temperature

After establishing the transition temperature of the Nb_3Ge of around 1K, at the application of 0.9T. By the finite element method (FEM) simulation the fundamental resonance frequency of one device should be around 43 MHz and around 77 MHz for the other device. The observed resonance frequency in our cases was around 1.1067 MHz, while we could not find the resonance frequency of the other device. The difference between the expected and observed resonance frequency is significant. We think that there can be a lot of factor for this observed discrepancy.

- The reliable data for the relative thermal contraction of Nb_3Ge is not available. This can lead to a decrease in fundamental resonance frequency.
- The young's modulus of Nb_3Ge depends upon the ratio of Nb/Ge ratio, which can be another reason for the reduction in the fundamental resonance frequency.

Dissipation and resonance frequency measurement with magnetic field

We know that the magnetic field application generates additional dissipation, which is due to the Eddy current, which should be directly proportional to the B^2 . This plot of dissipation versus B^2 is used to calculate a quantity called α which tells us the dependence of dissipation with B^2 . This has been discussed in the **chapter 2** of the thesis. It has been observed from the figure 4.5(i) that one cannot simply fit the B^2 dependence because of the additional dissipation present due to the vortices.

Similarly, we get the resonance frequency of the device, which is also get loaded by the application of magnetic field and has quadratic B dependence. This information can be gauged by a quantity called β and this has been discussed in **chapter 2** of the thesis. The figure 4.5(ii) shows the variation of f_l^2 with the B^2 . Now in case of metals it has linear dependence but in case of superconductors, it seems to deviate from the linearity.

This value of α and β is used to get the device's intrinsic quality factor and resonance frequency.

It is essential to point that the above relations for α and β is valid for the metals, and in the case of superconductors, it can be quite different. This can

be drastically different in the type II superconductors because their dissipation is associated with the movement of vortices.

Figure 6.3(i) shows the variation of the loaded dissipation with B^2 . Clearly, we see that in the case of superconductors, the relation between is violated, and we see some saturation between 0.7T and 0.8T. We believe that this is due to the competition between the increase in dissipation due to the movement of vortices and the decrease in dissipation due to the increase in superfluid density.

The figure 6.3(ii) shows the variation of the f_l^2 with B^2 . It clearly shows the behaviour of superconducting beam is different from the metallic beams. In the case of metallic beam, the resonance frequency of the device decrease [Venkatesan et al., 2010, Rebari et al., 2017] with the increase in magnetic field, which means the beam softens upon the application of magnetic field. In the case of a superconducting beam, the resonance frequency of the device increase with the increase of magnetic field. This means that the beam stiffens upon the application of magnetic field. The overall data represents that dissipation in superconductors is very different from the metallic counterpart.

Dissipation and resonance frequency measurement with temperature

Figure 6.4(i) shows the dissipation variation with temperature. It is clear from the figure 6.4(i) that dissipation stays constant above 1K. Then dissipation decreases (it is important to point out that transition temperature is around 1K by the transmission measurement at 0.9T). The decrease in dissipation continues till 400 mK and after that it saturates again but at somewhat higher values than the lowest dissipation. The dissipation transition, which onsets at 1K, is quite broad compare to the measurement by transmission. We believe that this can be due to the movement of the vortices, which creates extra dissipation; it is well established that measurement of the change in mechanical properties makes this method more sensitive than any other method [Esquinazi, 1991].

The figure 6.4(ii) shows the resonance frequency variation with temperature. It is clear from the figure 6.4(ii) that resonance frequency stays constant above 1K (which is transition temperature as measured by the transmission measurement). Below 1K, the resonance frequency of the device starts increasing, which means that beam is becoming stiffer. The resonance frequency of the metallic devices tends to decrease with a decrease in temperature below 1K; this was attributed to the existence of the two-level system [Venkatesan et al., 2010, Rebari et al., 2017]. In that way, the case of a superconductor is completely different to the metallic case.

We are still measuring more device, which will provide us with the concrete results on the dissipation and the frequency shift of the doubly clamped beams. As mentioned earlier, the origin of this increase in resonance frequency has been attributed to the increase in the magnetic restoring force due to the

Figure 6.3: (i) The loaded dissipation of the beam with square of magnetic field (B^2). The measurement was done at 75mK and applied magnetic field was perpendicular to the plain beam. This measurement was done to estimate α which can help us to calculate the intrinsic dissipation. (ii) The f_l^2 of the beam with square of magnetic field (B^2). The measurement was done at 75mK and applied magnetic field was perpendicular to the plain of beam. This measurement was done to estimate β , which help us to calculate the intrinsic resonance frequency of the device

Figure 6.4: (i) The loaded dissipation of the beam with the temperature. Applied magnetic field was perpendicular to the plain of the beam and applied magnitude was 0.9T. (ii) The loaded resonance frequency of the beam with temperature. The applied magnetic field was perpendicular to the plain of the beam and applied magnitude was 0.9T.

perfect diamagnetic behaviour of the vibrating structure in the presence of firmly pinned vortices. If the vortices are allowed to move now, the perfect diamagnetism reduces. As a consequence of that, resonance frequency also decreases [Brandt et al., 1986b, Esquinazi et al., 1986], which also leads to the peak in the dissipation below the upper critical field [Brandt et al., 1986b].

6.4 Conclusions

First of all, we measured the transition temperature of amorphous Nb_3Ge , with the high-frequency transmission method, and we could also show the magnetic field dependence of the transition temperature. We also measured the frequency dependence of the transition temperature, and till 200 MHz, we were able to find consistent transition temperature.

Then we studied the dissipation and resonance frequency variation of the amorphous Nb_3Ge with the magnetic field. We found that dissipation increases with the increase in strength of the magnetic field, and the resonance frequency increase with the increase in the magnetic field.

Lastly, we measured the resonance frequency and dissipation of the amorphous Nb_3Ge with the variation in temperature. We have found an increase in resonance frequency below the H_{c2} , which is due to the movement of vortices. We also observed an overall decrease in dissipation across the transition, which can be explained by the reduction in diamagnetism by the movement of vortices.

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Outlook

7.1 Conclusions

This thesis focus on the dissipation measurement in the superconducting and metallic system at cryogenic tempertaure, normally below 1K. We have focussed here the non-linear dissipation in the Palladium(Pd)- H_2 NEMS device as the linear dissipation has been studied in detail already [Rebari et al., 2017]. We have observed the novel non-linear dissipation phenomena observed in these system called non-linear Akhizier damping. The non-linear damping due to this mechanism is supposed to decrease with increase in temperature [Atalaya et al., 2016]. We have verified this fact by using three different routes to find non-linear dissipation. The non-linear dissipation values agree with each other very well within an order of magnitude [Miao et al., 2014, Eichler et al., 2011, Imboden and Mohanty, 2014].

As we already mentioned, our studied model system was Pd NEMS device soaked in the H_2 atmosphere. In one of the sets of our experiments, we kept on increasing the concentration of H_2 in the Pd beams. We found that for very low pressure of H_2 , the Pd beams behaved very well. After increasing the pressure of H_2 inside the Pd beam, we found the behaviour of beam become erratic, and we observed erratic behaviour in the dissipation and frequency measurement. This we assign as an anomalous diffusion of H_2 in the Pd beam. We also know that H_2 becomes solid at 13K in normal environmental condition and theoretically predicted superfluid transition temperature for H_2 is around 5K [Ginzburg and Sobyenin, 1972]. We also know that H_2 is supposed to sit inside Pd's interstitial sites. This provides us with a unique opportunity to study the superfluidity in $Pd - H_2$ system by minimizing the interactions between them. The thermal gap calculated for the excitation of H_2 from localized state to excited state is the same order as calculated for Helium and H_2 in other system [Makiuchi et al., 2018].

We have also studied the friction measurement over the superconducting surface. In this case, our resonator was 10 MHz Quartz crystals and over

which a superconducting film of tantalum (Ta) was coated. This kind of setup can help to find the dissipation contribution by normal electrons. Here we soaked our Ta superconducting film in H_2 atmosphere. After this, we cooled down our system below and above the transition temperature and measured the dissipation. We have observed the same effect of sliding friction as observed by Dayo et al. [Dayo et al., 1998].

7.2 Outlook

There have been many studies on the dissipation of the metallic system at very low temperatures. One may understand dissipation's observed behaviour at very low temperature using phenomenological two-level system model in metals. Still, there have been very few studies on the dissipation due to the movement of vortices. To study the dissipation due to the vortices movement, one has to use the type-II superconductors, where with the application of the field, vortices can be created. It must be noted that the choice of the superconducting material is unique. The choice of the material is made in such a way that so that flux pinning is minimal, which means the movement of vortices is easy. Nb_3Ge and Mo_3Ge is the best choice for these kinds of studies because flux pinning in these materials is very minimal. Nb_3Ge or Mo_3Ge is normally superconductor below 1K; there will be no question of the dissipation due to electron-phonon and electron-electron interactions. It means that after applying the magnetic field, one can study the dissipation due to vortices.

We also pointed out that observation of non-linear Akhizier damping in Palladium NEMS devices in the presence of H_2 atmosphere. We also predicted that Akhizier type non-linear damping is strong in these systems due to their larger grain size and it would be weaker in their alloys counterparts due to smaller grain size. It will be quite interesting to study the non-linear dissipation in Au-Pd NEMS device. We predict that Akhizier type non-linear damping will not be present in Au-Pd system.

Appendix A

Characterization of thin film palladium (Pd) doped ($Bi_{2-x}Sb_xSe_3$) topological superconductor by transport measurement

The topological superconductors provides a possibility to host the Majorana fermions. The quantum information can be encoded with the help of these particles which have unusually long coherence times. The first proposed topological insulator Bi_2Se_3 doped with Copper has found to be topological superconductor. Here we have doped thin films of ($Bi_{2-x}Sb_xSe_3$) by depositing Palladium over it and then annealing it. We have characterized these annealed materials with transport measurements and found that the transition temperature of around 1.3K and critical field of 1.1 T. We also found the very peculiar behaviour in IV and dV/dI characteristics in the unannealed material, where the vortex mobility decrease with increasing frequencies. We have also observed the superconductivity in unannealed samples although it is weak when compared to annealed counterpart, here in these unannealed materials we have observed classical peak effect which has been observed in type II materials.

A.1 Introduction

The second revolution in the computing industry is in progress; we call it quantum computation. Transistors realize the classical bit by turning them on and off with gate voltage. The realization of the quantum bit is very tricky, and a lot of work has to be done before we have a quantum computer in our hand. The qubits can be realized by using charge qubit, phase qubit, flux qubit, and there are many other ways [Krantz et al., 2019].

One of the main problems we face today is the coherence time of qubits which tends to be very small due to the coupling with the environment, although best efforts have been tried to decouple them from the environment. The qubits are normally operated at the lowest temperature and pressure available on the earth. The idea to solve the problem is to use non-local qubits as the perturbations that tend to destroy coherence are local operators. That is where the topological material comes into the picture because in topological material, properties can be destroyed by global operations. It is immune to the local perturbation, which is the reason why Microsoft [TU delft, 2021] have heavily invested in the qubit based on this method.

Let us try to understand the topological phase [Thouless et al., 1982], Take the example of integer quantum hall effect [Klitzing et al., 1980]. We know that in the presence of the magnetic field, current flows through the edges (also known as the skipping orbitals), and bulk does not contribute to the conductance, which is shown in the figure A.1 this gives rise to the non-trivial edge state and the trivial insulating phase. The example of the materials exhibiting the quantum hall effect became one of the first to show the topological phase. It turns out that time-reversal symmetry (TRS) is not present. These topological phases are a very robust system in the sense quantities like conductivity, charge, ground state degeneracies cannot be changed by the disorder and interactions. In 2005 [Kane and Mele, 2005] it was realized that other topological phases could be there which have time-reversal invariance, and these systems were named later on topological insulators. The topological insulator has a property very similar to the quantum hall effect in that both of them have gap-less edge states.

Figure A.1: The schematic to realize the topological phase in the material which shows the Quantum Hall effect

By introducing superconductivity in the topological phase of matter, one can obtain what we know today as topological superconductor [Kitaev, 2001,

[Beenakker, 2013, Leijnse and Flensberg, 2012, Stanescu and Tewari, 2013]. Topological superconductors by themselves are very exotic material in which one meets both unconventional superconductivity and topological phase of the matter. The superconducting gap in the topological superconductor can be closed by the symmetry protected surface state of the topological phase, in turn, which may support the Majorana fermions [Beenakker, 2013]. There required algorithm has been proposed to do quantum computation using Majorana fermions [Beenakker, 2013].

Recently Cu, Nb, Sr doping in the topological insulator Bi_2Se_3 has attracted a lot of attention as doping with these materials could induce superconductivity in the topological insulator. It is proposed that Cu doped Bi_2Se_3 is a topological superconductor [Fu and Berg, 2010]. The specific heat measurement on the Cu doped Bi_2Se_3 has shown it is a bulk superconductor with full pairing gap [Kriener et al., 2011]. The point contact measurement on the Cu doped Bi_2Se_3 has shown the existence of Andreev bound state [Sasaki et al., 2011]. Mlack *et.al.* have even found that doping Bi_2Se_3 with Palladium (Pd) can introduce superconductivity and they can be patterned into devices very easily [Mlack et al., 2017]. We will be following a somewhat similar path to search for a topological superconductor.

In this chapter we have, we have tried to introduce superconductivity in the thin film of $(Bi_{2-x}Sb_xSe_3)$ by depositing Pd over it, which acts as doping if we annealed the materials and even bombarding with energetic palladium might also do the job. Then we have tried to characterize the material by transport measurements.

A.2 Experimental Procedure

System under study

The system under study is thin films of Sb doped Bi_2Se_3 made by physical layer deposition (PLD). Then over these films, 100nm of palladium was deposited by thermal evaporation with the help of a stencil shaped in the form of a Hall bar. Then some of the samples were annealed in the N_2 atmosphere at 523K for almost 60 minutes and then let cool down on their own. Before annealing, the chamber was pumped to 5×10^{-3} Torr and then flushed with N_2 ; this process was repeated three times before starting the annealing process. Bases on the annealing, two types of samples were studied. They were classified as:

- Annealed: These samples were annealed as described above
- Unannealed: These samples were not annealed

The unannealed samples offer an advantage in the sense that it makes it easier to fabricate devices. Since the process only involves depositing Palladium and no additional heating is involved.

Experimental setup and measurements

The resistance of the sample is measured by the standard hall probe geometry using a lock-in amplifier (LI-7265 Signal Recovery with input noise of $2\text{nv}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ at this BJT configuration. In all the measurement, the driving frequency was set at 8.321 Hz. The 8.321 Hz was found suitable for the measurement as measured low noise power spectral density was low at this frequency. The contacts to the hall bar were made by depositing the Ti(3nm)/Au(50nm) using the stencils. The contacts from the sample to the PCB are made by using $50\mu\text{m}$ Au with the help of Indium (In).

Figure A.2: The schematic for the $\frac{dV}{dI}$ (differential resistance) measurement

The differential resistance of the sample was measured with the circuit as shown in the figure A.2. The circuit has a 10^5 divider for the AC circuit, and $\sim 10^3$ divider for the DC circuit and the capacitor was used so that DC does not reach the AC supply. Then both AC and DC were added and fed to the sample. The DC was varied to perform the dI/dV measurements, and the lock-in amplifier response was observed. The superconducting transition of the annealed samples was also measured with high-frequency transmission method *i.e.* by measuring S_{21} . For the high-frequency transmission measurements, we used a high-frequency RF lock-in amplifier (SRS 844), and more detail about the measurement setup can be found in the chapter3 of this thesis.

A.3 Results and Discussions

One of the first aims was to study the topological material's superconducting transitions and characterize the H_c and T_c of the material. This was done by both the high-frequency transmission method as well as four probes low-frequency method. We will discuss this in detail.

A.3.1 High frequency transmission method for T_c and H_c measurements

Figure A.3 shows the transmission (S_{21}) of the annealed sample with the variation in temperature at various magnetic fields. The driving frequency was set at 1MHz for these measurements. One can use this two probe method to determine the H_c and T_c as it is done by the low frequency four-probe method.

Figure A.3: The temperature dependence of the annealed sample's transmission (S_{21}) at 1MHz. Figure shows the transmission measurement of the sample at various magnetic field. This high frequency RF transmission method can be used for the determination of T_c and H_c of the sample

This can be explained as follows; we know that normal state resistance is high, so the transmission tends to be low (essentially, it should be zero). Now, as the sample goes superconducting, the normal state resistance decreases, which increases the transmission. The saturation in the transmission on the left side of the plot indicates the maximum transmission possible in the superconductor, which is very similar to the lowest resistance measured by the low frequency method. The critical temperature at 0T is around 800mK using the high frequency method.

Figure A.4: The temperature dependence of the annealed sample's transmission at 10 MHz and 200 MHz. At 200 MHz the transition is broad as compared to the 10MHz.

Figure A.4 shows the transmission (S_{21}) response of the sample with the variation in temperature at two different driving frequencies. The transition becomes broader when the measurements are done at 200 MHz compared to the measurements done at 1MHz. It can also notice that signal in the 200 MHz measurements is 18 times smaller than the measurements done at 1MHz. This can be explained by the fact that the sample was not fabricated into microstrip or co planer wave-guides geometries. The measurement was done on the simple thin film, which may result in this artefact.

A.4 Low frequency measurements

A.4.1 DC-Voltage versus Current

The DC current versus voltage was done to determine the I_c of the annealed sample as a function of temperature and magnetic field. The DC IV measurements were done with the help of Keithley source meter (Keithley-2400).

Figure A.5: The DC voltage versus DC current characteristics of the annealed sample at various temperature. The data was taken at 0T.

Figure A.5 shows the DC IV characteristic of the annealed sample at various temperatures. The measurement was done in 0T. The asymmetry in the curve, which is the area under the curve for the left side of the plot, is more than that of the plot's right side. Figure A.5 shows the typical characteristics of a superconductor which is the voltage across the sample stays zero until a specific amount of DC is applied. After the I_c , the voltage vs current follows the normal ohm's law. The critical current is around 1.3 mA when the temperature is stabilized at 700mK, and the applied magnetic field is set at 0T.

Figure A.6: The DC voltage versus DC current characteristics of the annealed sample at various magnetic field. The data was taken at 0.7K.

Figure A.5 shows the DC IV characteristic of the annealed sample at various magnetic fields. For the measurements, the temperature was stabilized with the error of 50mK at maximum. The asymmetry in the curve, which is the area under the curve for the left side of the plot, is more than that of the plot's right side. Figure A.5 shows the sweep in only one direction.

Figure A.7: The DC voltage versus DC current characteristics of the annealed sample at 0.7K. The applied field was 0T. The arrow indicated the direction of the sweeping current. The apparent hysteresis is both function of temperature as well as magnetic field.

Figure A.7 shows the hysteresis in DC versus voltage sweep. The black arrows indicated the direction of the sweep. For the measurements, the temperature was stabilized with the error of 50mK at maximum. The hysteric behaviour of the annealed device can be described as follows. We can consider that the grain boundaries of our annealed film form a tiny under-damped Josephson junction. In the under-damped Josephson junction, there is no voltage drop till I_c because the phase particle is trapped in a local minimum. At I_c , the voltage increases discontinuously to some value; at this state, phase particle is running *i.e.* particle is sliding down the washboard potential. If you start decreasing the bias current, the drop voltage becomes zero at current called re-trapping current I_r , which is much larger than the I_c . This has been attributed to the damping associated with phase particle as energy supplied by the bias current is not dissipated fast enough due to the small damping [Tinkham, 2004].

A.4.2 AC-Voltage versus Current

The measurements were done with low frequency lock in amplifier (7265 Signal Recovery) at the driving frequency of 8.321 Hz.

Figure A.8: The AC voltage versus AC current characteristics of the annealed sample at various magnetic field. The temperature was stabilized at 0.7K.

Figure A.8 shows the AC IV characteristic of the annealed sample at the various magnetic field. For the measurements, the temperature was stabilized at 700mK with the error of 50mK at maximum. Figure A.8 shows the typical characteristics of a superconductor which is the voltage across the sample stays zero until a specific amount of AC is applied. After the I_c , the voltage vs current follows the normal ohm's law. The log-log plot of the curve can be used to find the slope, and from the slope, one can find the BTK transition temperature for very thin films [Daptary et al., 2017].

A.4.3 Low frequency Resistance versus Temperature

Figure A.9: The annealed sample's longitudinal resistance versus temperature at various magnetic field.

We have also performed the low frequency measurement to observe the T_c and H_c as it is one of the standard methods. The applied current during these measurements was $5\mu\text{A}$.

Figure A.9 shows the Resistance with the temperature variation at different magnetic fields. The T_c of these annealed films is around 1.1K, and H_c is around 1.3T for the lowest temperature we can achieve in our dilution refrigerator.

Figure A.10: The annealed sample's longitudinal resistance versus magnetic field at various temperatures.

Figure A.10 shows the resistance with the magnetic field variation at different temperatures. The information provided by the figure A.9 and figure A.10 is very similar, and they can be clubbed together to produce a high-quality

contour plot, which makes the visualization of T_c and H_c lot easier, which is shown in the figure A.11.

Figure A.11: The contour plot of the annealed sample's resistance with the variation in the magnetic field as well as temperature. The X-axis represents the applied magnetic field, and the Y-axis represents the temperature. The colour of the plot shows the resistance. The vertical bar of the right-hand side shows the resistance values.

A.4.4 Differential Resistance measurements (dV-dI)

As already pointed out that differential resistance measurements can give us information about the density of states. In superconductors, the system has a gap, but it is different from the insulator in the sense that it is occupied by the cooper pairs and not the normal electrons. As a result, one should be getting zero resistance across the gap and then normal state resistance after crossing the gap.

Figure A.12: The annealed sample's longitudinal differential resistance ($\frac{dV}{dI}$) versus applied DC current at various temperatures. The magnetic field was set at 0T.

Figure A.12 shows the differential resistance with varying driving DC current at different temperatures. The way these differential measurements are done is equivalent to taking the mathematical derivative of the IV plot. Since at the onset of the normal state from the superconducting state, the slope of the IV plot changes, this results in the peak in the differential measurements. These measurements give us information about the gap in the superconducting system.

Figure A.13: The annealed sample's longitudinal differential resistance ($\frac{dV}{dI}$) versus applied DC current at various magnetic fields. The temperature was stabilized at 0.7K.

Figure A.13 shows the differential resistance with varying driving DC current at different magnetic fields. The information provided by the figure A.12 and figure A.13 is very similar. The figure A.13 can be represented in the contour plot also which marked the appearance of gap and peaks very visible as shown in the figure A.14.

Figure A.14: The contour plot of the annealed sample's differential resistance ($(\frac{dV}{dI})$) with the variation in applied DC current at 0.7K. The X axis represents the applied DC current and Y axis represents the magnetic field. The colour of plot shows the differential resistance. The vertical bar of the right hand side shows the differential resistance values.

A.4.5 Magneto-resistance measurements

We also performed the magnetoresistance measurement to look for the Shubnikov – De Haas oscillation in the sample. The maximum applied magnetic field in our case was 8T. The applied current during these measurements was $5\mu\text{A}$.

Figure A.15: The magneto-resistance of the annealed sample at various temperature. The sample in the normal state shows the weak anti localization behaviour.

Figure A.15 shows the magneto-resistance measurement on the annealed sample up to 8T at different temperatures. The Subnikov-De Hass oscillation was not observed as seen in their single crystal counterpart [Devidas et al., 2017]. However, it can be seen that after suppressing the superconductivity in these annealed films by the application of temperature, a clear weak anti localization signature can be seen, which is present up to 10K. The sample starts to show the classical magneto-resistance after the application of a magnetic field equivalent to 2T.

A.5 Vortex dynamics studies by IV measurement

Here we have studied the IV and dV/dI characteristics of the annealed sample with the variation in the frequency. For dV/dI measurements, the V_{ac} tends to decrease with the increase in the frequency and a large out of phase of the signal is also observed, which is monotonous. For pure AC IV measurements, the V_{ac} tends to decrease with an increase in frequency.

A.5.1 Introduction

The IV and dV/dI measurement has been used consistently to identify the phase of the vortex matter, especially the shape of these characteristics have attracted a lot attention [Garten et al., 1995, Higgins and Bhattacharya, 1996, Bhattacharya and Higgins, 1993]. The peak in the differential resistance measurement has been attributed to the plastic vortex depinning. Here we have shown the vortex mobility decrease with increasing frequency in both IV as well as dV/dI

measurements, which is quite the opposite to the apparent increase in vortex mobility as it has been studied here [Henderson et al., 1998, Kawamura et al., 2017]. This gives us a hint that the system is getting more stuck if we are trying to nudge the system. The measurements have been performed at 0.15T, and the temperature was stabilized at 500 mK with the maximum fluctuation of 5mK. It must be noted that during these measurements, the 50/100 Hz filtering option in the lock-in amplifier was turned off to avoid the cut off in amplitude due to the filters.

Figure A.16: The AC voltage versus AC current characteristics of the annealed sample at various driving frequencies. The temperature was stabilized at 0.5K and applied magnetic field was around 0.15T.

Figure A.16 shows the voltage with the variation in current at different frequencies. The IV characteristics are different from what has been observed in other systems where the vortex mobility enhances with increasing frequency [Kawamura et al., 2017, Paltiel et al., 2002].

Figure A.17: The In-phase differential resistance (X part of the lock in amplifier) of the annealed sample at various driving frequencies. The right side of the figure (the black solid line) shows the DC resistance with applied DC current. The data was taken at 0.15T and stabilized temperature was 500mK.

Figure A.17 shows the in-phase component of the differential resistance measurement at different frequencies. It has been observed that the peak in the differential resistance decays in amplitude with increasing frequencies; this is again consistent with the observation from the figure A.16 that V_{ac} decrease with increasing frequency. The decay in the peak amplitude in in-phase differential resistance is very fast; by the time we reach 31 Hz, peak amplitude becomes almost half of its maximum value. The measurements done at 111 Hz almost shows no peak in the differential measurement.

Figure A.18: The out-phase differential resistance (Y-part of the lock in amplifier) of the annealed sample at various driving frequencies. The right side of the figure (the black solid line) shows the DC resistance with applied DC current. The data was taken at 0.15T and stabilized temperature was 500mK.

The figure shows the A.18 shows the out of phase component of differential

resistance measurement with the variation in frequency. The observed trend in the peak shows the most puzzling trend here. It has been observed that the amplitude grows as we tune the frequency from 1Hz to 41 Hz, and then it starts to decrease again with the increase in frequency. The peak is almost zero at both high and low frequencies, and it peaks at intermediate frequencies, in this case, 41 Hz.

Figure A.19: The frequency dependence of in phase (X part of lock in amplifier) and out phase (Y-part of lock in amplifier) from differential response of the annealed sample. The DC current was set at 795mA which is the peak of the above figure, AC current was set at 100 μ . The set magnetic field was 0.15T and stabilized temperature was 500mK.

Figure A.19 shows the in-phase and out of phase component of differential resistance with varying frequency. The I_{ac} and I_{dc} for the measurement is chosen from the figure A.17, where the peak in amplitude occurs. In this case it turns out to be $I_{ac} = 100\mu A$ and $I_{dc}=795\mu A$.

These measurements point to an observation that with increasing applied frequency, we are moving our system from a weakly pinned region to the strongly pinned region in the H-T phase diagram. Some detailed analysis needs to be done to understand the observation as mentioned above shown by the sample.

A.6 Peak effect in unannealed sample

The main aim of this section is to study the observation of peak effect [Tomy et al., 1997, Bhattacharya and Higgins, 1994, Wördenweber and Kes, 1989] in the unannealed samples. Let us, first of all, understand the meaning of the peak effect. It has been observed that many type II superconducting material

have more ability to carry high current just below H_{c2} compared to the current carried by them at a lower magnetic field than H_{c2} . The reason for occurrence of this phenomenon is pointed out due to the softening of vortices [Pippard, 1969].

It is interesting to point out that palladium (Pd) deposited on $(Bi_{2-x}Sb_xSe_3)$ film became superconductor even without annealing. The superconductivity was observed at the cost of a decrease in H_c and T_c . It is also important to note that the peak effect was not observed in the annealed samples, and we could see the peak effect only in the unannealed sample, which points that defects play quite a role in this effect. In this section, we will be characterizing the T_c and H_c and I_c of the unannealed sample before studying the peak effect.

A.6.1 DC voltage versus current measurement

The DC versus voltage was done to determine the I_c of the unannealed sample as a function of temperature and magnetic field. The DC IV measurements were done with the help of Keithley source meter (Keithley-2400).

Figure A.20: The DC voltage versus DC current characteristics of the unannealed sample at various magnetic field. The temperature was stabilized at 0.1K. The measurement was done to find the voltage vs current slope to find the BTK transition

Figure A.20 shows the DC IV characteristic of the unannealed sample at the various magnetic field, for the temperature of the measurement, was stabilized at 100mK with the error 5mK at maximum. Figure A.20 shows the typical characteristics of a superconductor which is the voltage across the sample stays zero until a specific amount of DC is applied. After the I_c , the voltage vs current follows the normal ohm's law. The log-log plot of the curve can be used to find

the slope, and from the slope, one can find the BTK transition temperature for very thin films [Daptary et al., 2017]. The critical current I_c at 0T is around $200 \mu\text{A}$ when the temperature is stabilized at 100 mK.

A.6.2 Resistance versus Temperature measurement

The low frequency transport measurement was performed to observe the T_c and H_c of the unannealed samples. In these measurements, the applied driving current was set at $1 \mu\text{A}$.

Figure A.21: The unannealed sample's longitudinal resistance versus temperature at various magnetic fields.

Figure A.21 shows the Resistance with the temperature variation at different magnetic fields. The T_c of the unannealed film is around 900mK, and H_c is around 1.0T for the lowest temperature we can achieve in our dilution refrigerator.

Figure A.22: The unannealed sample's longitudinal resistance versus magnetic field at various temperatures.

Figure A.22 shows the resistance with the magnetic field variation at different temperatures. The information provided by figure A.21 and figure A.22 is similar, one can extract the information about H_c and T_c from any of those two mentioned measurements.

A.6.3 Differential Resistance measurements (dV-dI)

As already pointed out that differential resistance measurements can give us information about the density of states. In superconductors, the system has a gap, but it is different from the insulator in the sense that it is occupied by the cooper pairs and not the normal electrons. As a result, one should be getting zero resistance across the gap and then normal state resistance after crossing the gap.

Figure A.23: The unannealed sample's longitudinal differential resistance ($\frac{dV}{dI}$) versus applied DC current at various magnetic fields. The temperature was stabilized at 100mK.

Figure A.23 shows the differential resistance with varying driving DC current at different temperatures. The way these differential measurements are done is equivalent to taking the mathematical derivative of the IV plot. Since at the onset of the normal state from the superconducting state, the slope of the IV plot changes, this results in the peak in the differential measurements. These measurements give us information about the gap in the superconducting system.

A.6.4 Observation of peak effect

The peak effect is defined as the increase in the ability to carry current near to H_{c2} as compared to the lower fields. This can be observed as an anomaly

in the resistance. The observation of the peak effect can be a non-trivial task, and one might miss the peak effect, *Steingart et al.* [Steingart et al., 1973] has observed the peak effect can be enhanced if the sample is cooled in a magnetic field along with maximum applicable current without suppressing superconductivity. Figure A.24 shows the variation in resistance with the variation in magnetic field at different temperatures. It must be pointed out the applied driving current was $100\mu\text{A}$. The peak in the resistance can be seen shifting towards the left side of the plot (towards lower magnetic field values) as we are increasing the temperature.

Figure A.24: The magneto-resistance of the unannealed sample at various temperature. The figure shows peak in the resistance before it tends towards zero

A similar resistance anomaly can be seen by varying the current instead of varying the temperature, as shown in the figure A.25. It has been observed that with the increasing current the peak in resistance grows as it is easier to observe the peak effect by increasing the current rather than changing the current. It is important to note that increasing the driving current increases typically the temperature, which is why we could not go beyond $100\mu\text{A}$ as the fridge starts warming up. For these measurements, the temperature of the sample was stabilized at 130 mK with a maximum fluctuation of 5mK.

Figure A.25: The magneto-resistance of the unannealed sample at various driving currents. The figure shows peak in the resistance before it tends towards zero

The next task was to look for the critical current I_c as a function of the magnetic field. To study that critical current was defined as the driving current at which voltage develops across the sample becomes $1\mu\text{V}$. The right axis of the figure A.26 shows the critical current with the variation in a magnetic field, and the left axis of the figure shows the resistance with the variation in the magnetic field. The sample's temperature was stabilized at 100 mK with the maximum fluctuation temperature less than 5mK.

Figure A.26: The left axis of the figure shows the resistance of unannealed sample with the variation in magnetic field at 100mK. There is small peak in the resistance before the resistance tends to zero. The right axis of the figure shows the critical current variation I_c with magnetic field.

A.7 Conclusions

We have established that superconductivity can be induced in $(Bi_{2-x}Sb_xSe_3)$ by the thermal evaporation of Palladium (Pd) over it. The superconductivity appears to be stronger in annealed films as compared to the unannealed samples. The annealed sample shows very peculiar IV and dV-dI characteristics with the variation in frequency, where the vortex mobility decreases with increasing frequency. Usually, enhancement in the vortex mobility has been seen with increasing driving frequency. We have also observed the typical peak effect behaviour in the unannealed samples, and this behaviour was not observed in the annealed samples.

Appendix B

Ferromagnetic Resonance

The Ferromagnetic Resonance (FMR) technique can provide information on the magnetization, magnetic anisotropy, dynamic exchange/dipolar energies, relaxation times, and the damping in the magnetization dynamics.

FMR can be understood very easily with microscopic and from a macroscopic point of view.

From a macroscopic point of view, the applied static magnetic field H_0 causes the total magnetic moment to precess around the direction of the local field H_{eff} , before relaxation processes damp this precession, and the magnetization aligns with H_{eff} . If the rf frequency coincides with the precessional frequency, the resonance condition is fulfilled, and the sample absorbs the microwave power.

Microscopically, the H field creates a Zeeman splitting of the energy levels, and the microwave excites magnetic dipole transitions between these split levels. Since it is difficult to vary the microwave frequency over larger ranges, the magnetic field H_0 is varied.

Usually, the absorption derivative is measured. The resonance signal resembles a Lorentzian lineshape. The resonance field position H_{res} depends on the angles, anisotropy parameters, g-factor, and the sample's magnetization [Kittel et al., 1996, Kittel, 1948].

The magnetic moment of a single electron is defined as equation (B.1)

$$\mu = I * A \tag{B.1}$$

where A is the circle area. The magnetic moment is written as follows

$$\mu = \frac{-e}{2*m_e} * L \tag{B.2}$$

where as $\gamma = e/2*m_e$ is the gyromagnetic (magneto-mechanical or magneto-gyric) ratio. Therefore, the magnetic moment is obtained from Eq. as below

$$\mu = -\gamma * L \tag{B.3}$$

The following expression is obtained when derivative of above equation

$$d\mu + \gamma dL + Ld\gamma = 0 \quad (\text{B.4})$$

since γ is constant so we get $d\mu + \gamma dL = 0$

The derivative of time of this equation, the equation of motion for magnetic moments of an electron is found as below

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{d\mu}{dt} = \frac{dL}{dt} = \tau \quad (\text{B.5})$$

When an electron is placed in an applied magnetic field H the magnetic field will produce a torque. The equation of motion for magnetic moment is found by equating the torque as below

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{d\mu}{dt} = \mu \times H \quad (\text{B.6})$$

The magnetic materials contain a large number of atomic magnetic moment in general. Net atomic magnetic moment can be calculated by $M = N * \mu$. Where, N is the number of atomic magnetic moment in materials [Yalçın, 2013, Holladay, 2018].

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} \frac{dM}{dt} = M \times H_{eff} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Now H_{eff} can be written as equation (B.8)

$$H_{eff} = H_0 + H_{ani} + H_{demag} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Here $H_0 = \mu_0 B_0$, H_{ani} is the anisotropic field and H_{demag} is the demagnetization field, which depends on the shape of sample.

This precession movement continues indefinitely would take forever when there is no damping force. The damping term may be introduced in different ways since the details of the damping mechanism in a ferromagnet have not been entirely resolved, various mathematical forms for the damping have been suggested. One of the forms have been suggested as in equation (B.9)

$$\frac{\alpha}{M_s} M \times \frac{dM}{dt} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Here α is the Gilbert damping parameter which is commonly used to describe the relaxation. The linewidth is directly connected to the relaxation processes. But several other possible relaxation paths are also known, e.g., two-magnon scattering, spin-pumping effect, etc., which can contribute to the linewidth. M_s is the saturation magnetization.

The combination of the equation (B.7) and equation (B.9) is known as the Landau-Lifshitz-Gilbert (LLG) equation. Solving the LLG equation for the static field in the z-direction can be written as:

$$f_{res}^2 = \gamma^2 [B_0 + (N_y - N_z)\mu_0 M] [B_0 + (N_x - N_z)\mu_0 M] \quad (\text{B.10})$$

The equation (B.10) is also known as Kittel equation. When the magnetic field is applied in the plain of sample so that $N_x = N_z = 0$ and $N_y = 1$, then FMR can be written as:

$$f_{res} = \gamma \sqrt{B_0(B_0 + \mu_0 M)} \quad (\text{B.11})$$

when the magnetic field is applied out of plain of sample $N_x = N_y = 0$ and $N_z = 1$, then FMR can be written as:

$$f_{res} = \gamma(B_0 - \mu_0 M) \quad (\text{B.12})$$

B.0.1 Theory for frequency swept FMR

The resonance frequency depends on both the magnetic field and frequency. It means that one can get FMR by varying field or frequency. With the help of VNA, it is straightforward to change the frequency. In these measurements field is kept at constant value and frequency is varied until one get the resonance. In the VNA measurements, we require a different resonant analysis as data is obtained in the frequency domain rather than the conventional field domain.

In field modulation Gilbert damping model, the damping constant α relates to the full-width half-maximum (FWHM) of the resonance peak as

$$\Delta H = \Delta H_0 + \frac{4f\alpha\pi}{\gamma} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

Here ΔH_0 is the inhomogenous broadening in the sample due to imperfections in it. It is zero for the ideal sample. To extract α from linewidth in the frequency domain as found in VNA, it must be converted into a frequency linewidth by differentiating the Kittel equation which is given by

$$\Delta f = \Delta H \frac{\partial f_{kittel}(H_{eff})}{\partial H_{eff}} \quad (\text{B.14})$$

If one is working with microwave frequency, one has to be very careful with impedance mismatch. Otherwise, losses will be too much, and the signal might become very weak to detect, so for that, we designed a grounded coplanar waveguide (CPW) to minimize the losses in the signal.

Figure B.1: The final version of the finished CPW with Rosenberger PCB-end connectors

B.0.2 Measurements

The schematic for the measurements of FMR is shown in the figure B.2, here we have shown both of the in plain and out of plain geometry

Figure B.2: The schematics for measurement of FMR, (a) for the measurement of in plain geometry, (b) for the measurement of out of plain geometry

We used permalloy as a sample, and the thickness of the film used was 40 nm. It was deposited over Si/SiO_2 substrate, and it was thermally evaporated.

The way we measured these samples was that S21 is taken at 2A (which can be converted into the field), which corresponds to around 1T. This data

Figure B.3: Top part of the image shows the raw data taken with VNA and below part of the image shows that data after subtracting 1T data from the raw data

was taken as a reference, and all other data were subtracted from this data.

The most critical step in getting the data is the calibration of the VNA before the calibration, and after subtracting, we can clearly find out the resonance as shown in figure B.3. It is also vital to see that the background is very high, and the primary resonance is underneath the main data. Generally, it also makes a difference that you have subtracted the data at other magnetic fields from zero-field data or the maximum field data for some reasons which are not clear to me; data subtracted from the higher field looks good.

The figure B.4 shows the change in the resonance frequency with the change in the magnetic field. We were able to achieve our goal of looking for the resonance in the ferromagnetic material and the next aim is to improve the signal to noise ratio. We also want to get rid of the subtracting part which is not a nicer way to take the data, because anything wrong with your sample curve can lead to total destruction of the whole set. One way to achieve good signal to noise ratio is by balancing the signal *i.e.* to send two signal out of phase and detect the output at the other port and this is kind of interferometry. This work is still under progress and we have already designed 3 port and 4 port interferometers which are shown in the figure B.5.

Figure B.4: FMR of the Permalloy sample, shift in the resonance frequency with increasing magnetic field is clearly visible

Figure B.5: The various CPW and microstrip designed using eagle CAD for FMR interferometry measurement with both SMA and SMP connectors.

Appendix C

Heat-sink, PCB design for the future work

In a low temperature condensed matter community, the role of the heat sink is to dump the heat, which is carried from room temperature to the lower temperature. This is of paramount importance in the case of dilution refrigerators as the cooling power of dilution refrigerators is very low (*e.g* the one we are working (Oxford Triton 200) has a cooling power of 200 μW at 100 mK) The RF wiring, which happens to be a semirigid coax cable, is connected to the room temperature. This semirigid cable is connected to every stage of the dilution refrigerator. This means there is a considerable amount of heat load from outside to the dilution refrigerator's mixing chamber, resulting in an increase in temperature. To minimize the heating carried by these semirigid cables, we need to heat sink at every stage. For this purpose, we use sapphire crystal because of its high thermal conductivity at low temperatures [White, 1987]. We know that heat transfer is related to the temperature difference through the thermal conductivity as given by eqn. (C.1) where κ is thermal conductivity, Q is the heat, and ∇T is the temperature gradient.

$$Q = -\kappa \nabla T \tag{C.1}$$

It must be clear to us now that if we increase the material's thermal conductivity, we can effectively dump the heat carried by the phonon at various stages of the dilution refrigerator.

This sapphire crystal was housed in the small OHFC copper case (again, the OHFC copper has one of the highest thermal conductivity at low temperature), having both SMA and SMP connector. FigureC.1 shows the CAD image of the heat sink with SMA connector.

Figure C.1: CAD design for the sma heat sink

FigureC.2 shows the machined SMA connector

Figure C.2: machined sma heat sink

FigureC.1 shows the CAD image of the heat sink with SMP connector.

Figure C.3: CAD design for the smp heat sink

Figure C.2 shows the machined SMP connector

Figure C.4: machined smp heat sink

Since the dilution refrigerators have smaller cooling power, we have to attenuate the signal quite a lot. If we attenuate the power so much at room temperature, it leads to a very noisy signal, which is not suitable for the measurements. To overcome this problem, we have to attenuate the signal at the cold stages of the dilution refrigerator, leading to overall noise reduction

because thermal noise decrease with temperature. The required attenuator design can be fabricated by depositing Nichrome and controlling it's thickness. One can also use the commercial SMD attenuator, which is available easily. We are in the process of making our cryogenic attenuator. It must be noted that when we are working with microwaves, the power has to be matched at every joint to minimize the reflections. This can be done with the help of CPW (Coplanar Waveguide) or microstrip. We fabricate the Stainless Steel (which was made using laser cut) shadow mask for the deposition of nichrome in the microstrip or CPW geometry. Figure C.5 shows the microstrip designed by Solidworks and the fabricated shadow mask.

Figure C.5: Microstrip geometry. The left hand side of the figure shows the CAD design of microstrip geometry and right hand side of the figure shows the fabricated SS shadow mask

The figures C.6 shows the microstrip designed by Solidworks and the fabricated shadow mask.

Figure C.6: CPW geometry. The left hand side of the figure shows the CAD design of CPW geometry and right hand side of the figure shows the fabricated SS shadow mask

C.1 PCB

To measure the sample, which can incorporate both RF and DC measurement, we have designed PCB using Eagle CAD. One has to design a customized PCB for doing both RF and DC measurements; one such design is shown in

the figure C.7(a). Figure C.7(b) also shows one such design for doing FMR measurements.

Figure C.7: (a) PCB designed for both RF as well as DC measurements using Eagle CAD (B) PCB designed for FMR (Ferromagnetic Resonance) measurements using Eagle CAD.

Appendix D

Fixing the gauge controller of Triton 200

ULTP lab in IISER Mohali is equipped with a dilution refrigerator manufactured by Oxford instruments (Triton 200). After quite a bit of operation, we observed that Leybold Centre Three gauge controller was not working. This gauge controller, as shown in figure D.1 reads the pressure of still line (also called P3), pressure behind turbo (also called P4) and Outer vacuum chamber (also called OVC). The left-hand side of the figure D.1 shows the schematics of Oxford dilution refrigerator, which shows the position of P3, P4 and OVC. Since the gauge controller was not working, we could not start the fridge because it is crucial to know P3 and P4 during condensing and high-temperature operation of the fridge. Also, one needs to know OVC pressure to prevent icing inside or any other calamity occurring due to a bad vacuum. The new Leybold Centre Three cost is around 6 Lakh INR from the oxford instrument, which is quite expensive.

The still pressure gauge (P3) is called THERMOVAC TTR 101, and P4 is called THERMOVAC TTR 100, which is based on the Pirani combined with Capacitance diaphragm method. These gauges can measure pressure ranging from 1000 mbar to 1×10^{-5} mbar, and these gauges are manufactured by Leybold [Leybold, 2019a]. The OVC gauge, which is called PTR 90N is a combination of Pirani and Penning gauge, which works in the range between 1000mbar to 1×10^{-9} mbar. Leybold also manufactures these gauges. The advantageous situation for us is that all the measurement are standard 4-probe. This means that we need three power supplies and three differential voltmeters for the measurements. Fortunately, in our old Leybold Centre Three, we observed that all the 24V DC power supplies were working fine, saving a lot of hassle. We needed three voltmeters to measure the voltage. For measuring the voltages, we use NI DAQ 6210, which has eight differential channel, which means it has eight differential voltmeters [Truchard, 2019].

The connection diagram of the Pirani gauges (P3 and P4) is given in their respective manuals [Leybold, 2019b, Leybold, 2019c]. The connections were

Figure D.1: The left figure show the schematics of the Oxford instrument software, indicating the position of various gauges and the right figure shows the Leybold Center Three gauge controller in the working condition

made through the CAT-V(Ethernet cable). It can be seen from the figure D.2 that we have used a 24V DC power supply from Leybold Center Three, which can be easily accessed by 15 pin D type connector. The voltage is read through NI 6210, which is enclosed in an Aluminium box (to avoid the EMI).

The manual was also important because both types of gauges use the thermal conductivity of gases. Normally all the gauges are calibrated for the Nitrogen gas; since we are interested in Helium gas, we have to introduce the respective correction factor. The correction factor can be easily found in their respective manuals. To automate the readings, we used NI Labview and created an executable file. The front panel of the Labview programme is shown in figure D.3.

Figure D.2: The Left figure shows the backside of the Leybold Center 3 which has been used as 24V DC power supply and the right figure shows the NI 6210 enclosed in aluminum box which has been used to read voltages from OVC,P3 and P4

Figure D.3: The front panel of the labview program which display the pressure of all three gauges.

It must be noted that the front panel shows the voltages; in order to convert the voltages to pressure, the formula has been given in the manuals. The manuals also provide the correction factor to be included for various kind of gases.

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